

UNIVERSITY OF
LIVERPOOL

**ICT big size projects in Outsourcing with BPR. The agile scenario.
Academic vs actual dynamics and effectiveness in a prone to
uncertainty environment.**

By

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A DISSERTATION

Submitted to

The University of Liverpool

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

Master of Project Management

2014

**DECLARATION
A Dissertation
Entitled**

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Academic vs actual dynamics and effectiveness in a prone to
uncertainty environment.**

By

Giorgio Bellinger

We hereby certify that this Dissertation submitted by Giorgio Bellinger conforms to acceptable standards, and as such is fully adequate in scope and quality. It is therefore approved as the fulfillment of the Dissertation requirements for the degree of Master of Business Administration.

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**The University of Liverpool
2014**

CERTIFICATION STATEMENT

I hereby certify that this paper constitutes my own product, that where the language of others is set forth, quotation marks so indicate, and that appropriate credit is given where I have used the language, ideas, expressions or writings of another.

Signed Giorgio Bellinger

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Giorgio Bellinger". The signature is written in a cursive style with a prominent vertical stroke at the beginning of the first name.

ABSTRACT

Significance and Background

Nowadays, many organizations know and extensively apply outsourcing practices. The reasons that should justify the adoption of this practice dwell on the search for lowering labour costs, for accessing not available expertise, for achieving flexibility and, more in general, for pursuing competitive advantage. Although a huge amount of failures seems to indicate as this practice is not as proficient as expected, no one seems to tackle the preconception related to its suitability. It could indicate an under-evaluation of the real impact of the outsourcing practice by organizations and, in turn, it could indicate the limits of the process aimed to evaluate “the how” (meant as tactics). It is ascribable to a decision-making process that very likely is inspired to the quantitative business management perspective. Unfortunately, the complexity of the real scenarios could really strain the reduction of their “whole” into many, single, manageable chunks of work. It could be particularly true in an ICT context. Also ICT employees (as member of a supportive element of the value chain) well know how this practice can impact themselves so that motivating them could be nonsense in several situations.

Within the above boundaries, our interest concerns the dynamics of Outsourcing practices applied to ICT (i.e. Information and Communication Technologies) SW (i.e. software) Solutions with BPR (i.e. business process reengineering). Uncertainty and next complexity of the proposed scenario would not justify a per “best-practices” approach so that they are additional reasons for investigation. They further constrain Project Managers to adopt an Agile paradigm. Knowledge Areas of PM practices will be also considered.

Aims

With this research we would like to range over many topics like: the role of ICT as no longer limited to the supportive activities of the value chain; the fact that Outsourcing is a deliberate loss of differentiation, doubtful benefits in terms of costs and harbinger of serious risks like lock-in and loss of intellectual property; the ICT employees approach to Outsourcing; consequences of uncertainty and complexity on PM practices. In our opinion, all of above are elements to consider while deciding whether to undertake or not the practice in scope for the research in the given scenario. We consider as initial driver and responsible of such decision a defective, reductionist, quantitative decision-making process used to justify the cost-benefit-ROI analysis. Results of this misleading process are lack of viability for every organization living in a continuously changing, challenging and complex environment. The analysis of the results of the quantitative decisional process versus a mixed one and consequences on employees is our main scope.

Key findings

Despite not decisive, our findings foster reasonable doubts related to the effectiveness and efficiency of the quantitative decision-making approach when it is applied to the typology of projects in scope for the research. As per hypotheses, the consequent lack in terms of competitive advantage (due also to a debatable role assigned to the ICT) impacts strategies and viability of the organization.

Results could be reasonably extended in order to justify further research belonging to fields of knowledge and/or dualisms like “holism, complexity, customization, quality, differentiation, localization, loyalty, ...” as opposite to “reductionism, standardization, quantity, globalization, independency, ...”.

Acknowledgement

I would like to thank the:

Steering committee:

dr. Dimitris Folinis and dr. Paolo Zaza

Core Team:

Mrs Johanna Rothman, Mrs Penelope Manigrasso, dr.Stefano Ronchi, dr.Marco Alemanni, dr.Aldo Lattuada, dr.Carlo Zorzoli, dr Jacopo Mazzolin, Mr Michael John Walton

Project Team:

John Rigler, Leonardo Costantini, Roberto Speretta, Villy Kjær Gravengaard, Maurizio Berti, Antony Morling, Agostino Angeloni, Irappa Arabhavi, John Barel, Luca Bassetto, Adolfo Battiston, Stefano Bellinger, Julie Brock, Sateesh Chandrasekaran, Maurizio Corda, Michele Dalla Valle, Kira de Pellegrin, Lars Devero, Antonio di Bartolo, Guglielmo di Bisceglie, Antonio Doni, Maurizio Fanin, Corrado Fischer, Giancarlo Gregoratti, Mauro Lot, Piero Luchesi, Elisabetta Magagnin, Dionigio Franchi, Mauro Marchi, Massimo Masat, Peter David Medley, Fabrizio Montino, Elio Panegai, Giuliana Pigozzo, Matteo Piovesan, Jane Pollard, Matteo Raffin, Laura Riganti, Ako Sabir, Giovanna Sandoval, Ghaleb Sanjakdar, Alberto Savani, Franco Scolari, Sandro Severoni, Massimo Spada, Alain Swaelens, David Thomas, Anoop Venugopal, Diego Visentin, Gerhard Weber, Monika Laszlo and all the others who I annoyed with my questionings

Sponsors:

Nicolò, Anita, Messalina, Maria, Claudio, Bertilla, Ernesto, Stefano

Shareholders:

Nicolò Bellinger, Anita Bellinger, Messalina Bottega

The final special thanks to my Dissertation Advisor dr Dimitris Folinis for his ability to instil motivation

dubitatio ultima spes

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Systems thinking and cybernetics show how organizations are comparable to living systems that, in order to survive and thanks to feedback loops, adapt themselves to an environment that is continuously challenging their viability. At a higher detail level, organizations themselves are environments where strategic business units adapt in order to survive and to allow the organization itself to survive. In organizations, this internal adaptation is governed thanks to organizational structures, via processes, hierarchies and all the assets available to maintain the claimed viability. However, at the end of the “chain of viability” there are people acting and reacting (in the aforementioned scenario) in order to maintain the viability of their own organizations.

Thanks to development and distribution of technologies, in the last decades ICT technologies (and SBUs supporting ICTs in organizations) have known an astonishing success; one of the reasons could be that ICT technologies are supportive against the whole value chain and enable changes in creating, renewing or adapting so to leverage new business opportunities. Nevertheless this dynamism shows how ICT technologies impact and cross the whole aforementioned “chain of viability” (or value chain) from the strategies to the human resources via SBUs and leveraging on the mentioned assets; in that way related costs could suddenly appear as relevant. From there (and also thanks to the assumption that ICT is an enabler and not a “member” of the value chain), it arises that there is a need to control and reduce investments in that direction.

With that purpose, among the many best-practices adopted one of the most popular is the adoption of the outsourcing practice. However experience, evidence and literature seem not to justify always that choice since many related projects fail. But projects are just the final result of the company’s adaptation to the environment, an adaptation that passes throughout decision-making processes, business cases, cost-benefit-ROI analyses and in general quantitative screenings.

From the above introduction we get the hints for our questions. At a glance these are: is our decisional process really supported by proper elements while deciding for the adoption of the mentioned practice in ICT? Since human resources are a crucial part of the “chain of viability”, may we reduce the understanding of the impact of their commitment on the project to quantitative factors? Is it possible to hypothesize a model for the cost-benefit-ROI analysis that can better explain/forecast the results by considering also qualitative factors?

1.2 Background

1.2.1 *From Systems to Companies and Strategies*

Systems Thinking and the Viable System Model

Systems Thinking (Armson and Ison, 2004) is a methodology or approach aimed to understand behaviour of systems (like organizations) and their outcomes by looking at systems as a whole entity and not as “just” the aggregation of the behaviour and outcomes of the system’s components. This is the holistic view of Systems: a System is more than just the sum of its parts.

Systems dynamics deal with the communications among components of a system and their impact on the behaviour of the system itself. The holistic approach is aimed to understand how, from the mentioned interactions, emergence arises where emergence is an unpredictable outcome that cannot be read by natural sciences. Complexity and communications are the main characteristics of Systems.

In the 1970s, Stafford Beer (1985 cited in Zimmer and Chapman, 2004, p.5) applied the Systems Thinking approach to organizations. The result of his study is the Viable System Model (VSM). In Stafford's model, organizations are defined as purposeful, complex, recursive, learning, self-adaptive and autonomous Systems. Such organizations live in environments that continuously challenge the achievement of their objectives and the ability of an organization to adapt to these challenges (in order to maintain its equilibrium and achieve its objective) is known as the "viability of the organization". Viability depends on structure, communications and processes (Zlatanović, 2012):

- structure refers to the components of which the organization itself is made up and the way they frame the organization
- communications refer to the internal and external interactions of the components of the organization and they are:
 - internal to the organization while included within its boundaries
 - external while overcoming the boundaries to allow the organization itself to interact with the environment
- processes refer to the management and coordination of the components of the organization.

In order to be viable, organizations have to communicate internally and externally to/from their boundaries, interpret messages and plan controlled counter actions to reinstate their equilibrium. Feedback loops (Atufunwa, 2009) are the means of communications and the means that organizations have to empirically verify counter actions. The reference to feedback loops underlines how cybernetics inspire this model (Ericson, 1972 and Zenko, 2013). The picture below shows a rough VSM:

Figure 1 - Viable System Model (Zimmer and Chapman, 2004 p.26)

VSM is a starting point to understand dynamics at the basis of the creation of the strategies and their meaning as: plans to sustain the organizations' viability. Here, similarities with business management jargon and meaning are quite evident so that we can map organization to company, scope to business, govern to "strategies and/or management", self-adaptation to "change and project" and so on.

Two relevant topics arise from this introduction:

- reasons (Atufunwa, 2009) and high level process to define strategies
- environment and organization form a unique context

From the second point above, it arises that given strategies respond to the criteria of (Morris and Pinto, 2007) effectiveness (the right thing and so "the what") and efficiency (the thing right and so "the how") only in a given environment and for a given organization; it means that the same strategies risk not making sense in different contexts or for a different organization.

Strategies and Competitive Advantage

In the previous section we depicted how, because of environmental challenges, organizations adapt in order to maintain their viability and we also sustained that the decision related to what to adapt is a matter of strategies for an organization in a given environment. In the 1980s Professor Porter provided "guidelines" and an organizational model with the purpose of explaining how organizations can follow strategies to survive (be viable) to competitors and environmental challenges:

- Competitive Advantage Theory (Porter, 1985) corresponds to named "guidelines"
- the Value Chain (IMA, 1996) corresponds to the named model

In Porter's theory the advantage over competitors could be achieved by acting on costs and/or differentiation so that "costs and differentiation are the means by which we leverage in order to implement the changes needed to pursue strategies aimed to maintain the organization's viability". As said, Porter provided also a process oriented model of company organization (very likely inspired to the classical view of management); that model is known as the Value Chain and it is arranged as a sequence of processes that are supported by primary activities and supportive activities. Purpose of the organizational structure, processes, primary and secondary activities is to deliver outcomes related to the "core business" of each company.

Putting together the value chain model and the competitive advantage theory, we conclude that each process of the value chain and/or the value chain as a whole (i.e. as a System and via the contribution of primary and/or supportive activities) can contribute to the competitive advantage of a company by leveraging on costs and/or differentiation. The picture below shows the value chain:

Figure 2 - Value Chain (IMA, 2009 p.3)

Last but not least, in the Value Chain technologies are classified as supportive activities (we would exclude here companies whose core business belongs to the technological field) so that technologies do not deliver competitive advantage to the company directly and in strict terms; also ICT, as technology, stand within the boundaries of the supportive activities and that “secondary order of relevance” announces some consequences that we will try to highlight in the next sections.

1.2.2 ICT and Competitive Advantage

Having defined the concepts of strategies and competitive advantage and having framed the role of technologies against the value chain, we now need to depict the role of ICT in supporting a company’s strategies. It is immediate to infer that, as member of the supportive activities of the Value Chain, ICTs can indirectly provide support to strategies acting on competitive advantage in terms of costs and differentiation. Anyhow, perhaps because ICT is a member of the supportive activities (how can it differentiate if it is a supportive activity?), further constrained by the classical view of management (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2012), ICTs are mostly managed (Tarhan and Demirors, 2012) in quantitative/rational/cost terms (Galliers, 2009, p.10).

In our opinion this aprioristic quantitative approach is reductionist (Harth, 2004) and it clashes with the idea of uncertainty, differentiation, uncertainty joined to differentiation (Cheng, 2014) and the aforementioned Systems perspective. It has often “relegated” the contribution of ICT to Competitive Advantage as a declination of the cost paradigm and rarely a declination of the differentiation paradigm (evidence of it is sometimes given by the CIO-to-CFO direct report in cost oriented organizations - Banker et al., 2011 -).

Based on all the above, with our research we would like to approach the topic of the “ICT contribution to the competitive advantage” from the aforementioned perspective and

applying that perspective to the ICT SW Solutions Outsourcing projects of big-size. Big-size refers to the field where companies could also point to differentiate (Silvestro and Westley, 2002) and where ICT is expected to provide strategic support (Harmon and Davenport, 2007): business process reengineering (Galliers, 2009, p.10). The choice for Outsourcing is justified by the claimed flexibility (i.e. management of uncertainty and differentiation) that this practice should provide (*“freeing up one’s own resources, improving flexibility, gaining access to capital, access to new markets, or changing the rules of competition”* - PWC, 2007, p.3 -) in order to cope with uncertainty.

1.2.3 Outsourcing and competitive advantage

We need now to further develop the concept of outsourcing and, to do that, we would like to investigate the service providers’ perspective. So, what is the meaning of “outsourcing” for the service provider? If for the customer outsourcing is a de-facto standard and the *“strategic use of outside resources to perform activities that are usually handled by internal staff and resources”* (Elmuti, Grunewald and Abebe, 2010), what is the perspective of the service provider?

First of all we think that outsourcing is a service (the name “service provider” eases that interpretation). Services have their own characteristics so that, in order to be “viable” and “valuable” for a service provider, they should respect some principles. Here we consider the SOA paradigm as a “reliable enough” set of principles in order to understand service characteristics and we further extend the applicability of SOA principles to services in general because of their actual use in other fields than just ICT (Kaparang, Utomo and Manongga, 2013 and Sandkuhl et al. 2013). SOA principles (i.e. service principles) are (Erl, 2008) loss of coupling, abstraction, reusability, autonomy, statelessness, discoverability and composability. Perhaps that some of these principles make sense only in the ICT world like “discoverability” but, in general, they are “reusable” and they give us the idea of abstraction. Abstraction is a key point here because, if it is possible to abstract, the service supplier can leverage scale economies by delivering the same service to many customers; the only clear constraint, in order to succeed with abstraction, is that the related service contains common value for customers in focus.

If, on the one hand, abstraction and reusability are guidelines for the service provider in order to exploit scale economies, on the other hand we have seen as Harmon and Davenport (2007, p.15) sustain that the more important the business process the more likely the need for customization. It is clear that customization counters abstraction (and reusability) and vice versa. Nevertheless customization is needed in strategic processes because of the uniqueness of the “container” made up of “organization and environment”. So how is it possible to encompass both perspectives? The answer is not so difficult from the service provider perspective, since customization will be considered as an exception/extra-cost with respect to the standard service delivered and, in effect, it is not unusual to engage service providers that offer customization services at low price (but, we would add, longer time – Rothman, 2010 -) to complement their main services (and sometimes the mentioned complement becomes the business of the SP).

The consequences for the customer’s strategic business processes (customized processes) in the above scenario are evident since the customer has:

1. either to accept the provided standard
2. or to lavish additional financial efforts to customize the standard service

In terms of competitive advantage we think that the first point above is harbinger of two things:

- it is a deliberate renunciation to differentiate
- it is an improper adaptation of business processes to the combination “environment-organization” and the change can impact values such as profits, goodwill, corporate culture...

On the other hand, the second point above means:

- high cost in the long term (needed for the customization) and/or
- short duration of the differentiation or efficiency because the SP (service provider) will, over time:
 - acquire new reusable knowledge
 - include that customization among its delivered standards services (if services demonstrate common value)
 - try to reduce its cost via:
 - delivering of customization by leveraging, for instance, off-shoring (low price but longer time)
 - trying to reduce the quality of the delivered service
 - try to push against exceptions (i.e. extra costs) all the required activities
- BP knowledge related transfer from the customer to the supplier
 - transfer of intellectual property from the customer to the supplier
 - customer lock-in

So we think that from the customer perspective, in the former case, they are facing a deliberate loss of differentiation whereas in the latter case it is difficult to understand the success level of the declination of the cost paradigm while compared to the in-sourcing practice. Moreover, in terms of flexibility (PWC, 2007, p.3), uncertainty and resources to cope with them, it seems that it is not possible to renounce to proper resources to customize but rather that resources are “just” moved from the customer to the service provider and/or vice versa without evident cost benefit (i.e. somewhere the costs are sustained and it is not the supplier’s role); but the relevant thing here, for the customer and human resources, is where the business process knowledge resides. Here we therefore argue the key point is related to the “where” we have to place boundaries of the management of uncertainty as customization/flexibility and that, independently of those boundaries, uncertainty (i.e. customization) will be always charged on the customer side. The Gartner (Smith, 2011) Pace Layer model is exactly a proposal aimed to “define boundaries/distinguish” repeatable services from others (and related layers in the Enterprise Architecture) so to evaluate which ones it could make sense to outsource (the Systems of Records services).

Furthermore, customization (that needs knowledge and flexibility) relies on employees and employees (Styhre, 1996), in outsourcing practices, are sometimes considered as “commodities”. Nevertheless they are the strategic “owners” of strategic business processes’ customizations so that a “pass-the-parcel” game, between the customer and the service provider, could have serious consequences in terms of their motivation and next viability of a company.

If it is acceptable, is it properly evaluated while companies decide to outsource ICT Solutions with BPR constraint? And since complexity, uncertainty and financial constraints

often push against “fast” but (thought to be) “reliable” decisions, recognized standard and best-practices (Foster and Levitan, 2006, Galliers, 2009 and Hayes, Hunton and Reck, 2001), do we really plan for outsourcing?

1.2.4 Conclusions

With previous sections in mind, we start here arguing that outsourcing of SW Solution with BPR constraints could be valuable but, during the decision making process, it should be considered that:

- by leveraging on cost (in the case of the adoption of a standard service) we adopt a deliberate reductionist approach to ICT, renounce to proper adaptation, reduce viability of company’s processes to environmental challenges and we access to mediocrity
- by leveraging on differentiation (in case of customization) we risk that
 - either, the difference from in-sourcing lacks of evidence in terms of costs
 - or, it could become a standard service for the SP
- employees, who own the BP knowledge, can seriously condition the project success and employee management is an ethical issue as well (University of Minnesota Duluth, 2006). A proper change process should be considered
- the decisional process is often constrained by many other factors that produce pressure, uncertainty and difficulties in quantifying/planning the related project so that, perhaps, we just opt for recognized best-practices

We think of having shown how business management is driven by a quantitative approach and how it clashes with uncertainty, differentiation (we argue here that differentiation is the qualitative attribute of the competitive advantage paradigm - Caves and Williamson, 1985, p.113 and Dirisu, Iyola and Ibiidunni, 2013, p.260-) and environmental pressure. The high level of uncertainty and the qualitative meaning of differentiation reinforce the never ending story, the discussion aimed to demonstrate pros or cons related to outsourcing practices with differentiation for BPR because of many debatable views and interests: suppliers claim for the effectiveness and efficacy of their services, academics evidence their openness and customers are continuously under pressure and often relying on solutions inspired to best-practices (Nixon, 2004).

1.3 Research Questions

Section 1.2 should have provided insights aimed to address questions that we think will arise naturally. For our purposes, the most relevant one is: do we really know what to evaluate while deciding to run a project with given characteristics? In cascade with respect to this first question: do we deal with a decision making process “aware” of the characteristics of project management in ICT, Outsourcing and risks of uncertainty? Is the cost-benefit-ROI analysis (considered here as the core of the quantitative decision making process) properly developed in order to explain and forecast the results of such projects? These questions are relevant because, despite an un-successful project could be irrelevant per itself, the situation could be different if we consider the project in the light of its role as “enabler of strategies” so that the whole viability of the company could be compromised by its failure.

However, due to constraints of resources we cannot extend our analysis to the evaluation of the strategic benefits that such projects can deliver. For that reason the questions to which this research will try to provide answers to (or just doubts) are:

1. Is the positivist and quantitative evaluation phase (i.e. a quantitative cost-benefit-ROI model), in the decision-making process aimed to choose an outsourcing solution for big-size ICT projects, effective?
2. Could a constructionist and qualitative evaluation phase, based on consequences of uncertainty, positively impact the forecast of the results?
3. Is there any additional more appropriate alternative to the above mentioned quantitative and/or qualitative model?

We understand that, although in above the questions we have tried to clearly segregate the quantitative, qualitative and mixed models, the results of the research could force us to consider the models as a continuum rather than as three discrete typologies; it means that it is possible that there is no evaluation phase either completely quantitative or qualitative rather it could be that there are evaluation phases where quantitative factors are dominant and others where they are not. We expect to find an answer to the third question as consequence of the answers to the first and second question.

1.4 Hypothesis

In agreement with the section, our assumptions are that Outsourcing of the implementation of SW solutions with BPR is a deliberate loss of differentiation (at least for the part of the project that is outsourced) and so, in the best hypothesis, it is often no more than a search for cost reduction (reductionist approach); search that in turn is a reaction to causes like: high level of financial pressure, uncertainty, quantitative approach to business management and access to best-practices as incontestable panaceas. Workforce is essential in that process, its reactions are unpredictable because sometimes it is the passive subject of an unethical approach that arises from an improper usage of the change management. That latter fact could impact and invalidate also the cost approach to outsourcing (it could be due to the resistance to change and following attitude of “victims” of outsourcing - Elmuti, Grunewald and Abebe, 2010). In that case neither the differentiation nor the cost paradigms could produce, at the end, advantages. Considering also the clash between uncertainty and quantitative approach (that could underline lack of knowledge), evidences of failures in terms of cost overrun (Qi and Chau 2012) and the fact that core business processes usually require high levels of customization (so in general not suitable for outsourcing purposes - Harmon and Davenport, 2007, p.15 -), failures seem to be announced.

Again, these projects are risky at least because of: absence of differentiation, high levels of uncertainty, psychological impact on workforce, past testified failures, maybe limited widespread knowledge. Therefore, why should we opt for something that should not differentiate, that evidence shows as failing in delivering costs advantage, that is difficult to know because uncertain and that condition in various ways the life of people who contribute to the company viability?

All of it allows us to think that applying just a quantitative approach (i.e. the dominant approach in business management in our hypothesis) to the evaluation phase (usually a cost-benefit-ROI analysis) of the decision making process is of doubtful effectiveness and efficiency and for that reason it could be not proper to understand what to do in order to

support strategies; in other words, shown constraints and failures could testify as the quantitative evaluation phase does not allow a sufficient understanding and/or forecast of the strategic contribution of our plans to the viability of the company.

If our findings will evidence better forecast abilities of the qualitative approach compared to the quantitative one (and remembering as outsourcing should be suitable to leverage on costs and/or to unchangeable assets) then we could argue that:

- the quantitative evaluation could be insufficient to properly forecast the impact of business plans against its strategies
- outsourcing impacts differentiation even if we do not plan for it (if the qualitative approach justifies the result better than the quantitative one it should mean that some qualitative factors have been impacted and they, in turn, have conditioned the result; but quality corresponds to differentiation in our assumptions so we impact on differentiation despite outsourcing should not be used for that reason);
- based on the previous point it could mean that, to the decision makers, boundaries are not clear and
- characteristics of ICT are not always properly considered and
- characteristics of uncertainty and its impact on projects are not always properly considered and
- characteristics of Outsourcing are not always properly considered and
- best-practices (that are based on external benchmarks) adopted “as they are” could be unsuitable for each business case (“...*the more popular a particular generalization in the social sciences, the less accurate will be the predictions it yields.*”; Kashyap, 2014) and
- so, at the end, we could not know how we are supporting strategies of the company
-

Moreover in absence of a developed maturity model and strategic cost accounting aimed to improve the decision making process, we would consider the chance that companies unconsciously renounce to learning so that lessons learned are lost and internal benchmarking is not possible.

The proposed scenario is deliberately complex as business management is; this is also due in order not to incur in a reductionist quantitative analysis that is limited while trying to explain social sciences.

We know that it is likely that in this dissertation we won't be able to demonstrate either one point among the ones stated above but, at least, we would like to support the freshening of a mixed and human resource oriented approach to business management.

1.5 Aims and Objectives

For the above-mentioned reason we would like to validate here the efficiency (not the effectiveness that is related to “the what” and support to strategies of the outcomes of a project) of the cost oriented approach (Latif, 2005, p.688) to business management, decision making process, decisional phase and cost-benefit-ROI analysis in forecasting the contribution of plans/projects to strategies. The validation will be tested against the success of the related projects.

The same validation as above will be then fulfilled with a qualitative model inspired to Agile PM (being the chosen case surrounded by high levels of uncertainty), Change management, ICT and Outsourcing practices. We will further try to underline the impact of the human factor on the success level of these projects.

A third validation devoted to a mixed approach will be tested.

Actual results of the research could contribute to the most proper choices in terms of “right things” (i.e. the proper change for the given strategies) and proper maintenance of the related project portfolio.

In general, we think that our final purpose is to try to provide additional hints to the positivism vs constructionism diatribe in business management via an approach aimed to unfold how reducing complexity could be a mistake if not counterproductive.

1.6 Methodology Applied and sources of data for the study

We will approach the study in a mixed mode. An initial qualitative research will be executed in order to better understand and frame the topic of the research with particular respect to the methodologies and reasons to outsource. Results from the first qualitative analysis will be part of the inputs for the creation of the model and next quantitative research aimed to evaluate effectiveness and efficiency of the models.

Interviews will be primary source of information for the qualitative research whereas web based surveys will be the main source of information for the quantitative approach

1.7 Structure of the Study

The study is made up of five chapters:

- The first chapter contains the backbone of the research; it will provide the view and so the context that surrounds us while doing our considerations and proceeding in a certain way
- The second chapter is aimed to refine the first one in terms of context via the literature review and the theoretical framework. Moreover it will act as source for the creation of the models of evaluation. First and second chapters will be thoroughly affected by the results of the qualitative part of the research (i.e. interviews)
- The third chapter further focuses on the topic of the research and it will provide the context related to the methodology and approach to the research
- The fourth chapter will be devoted to refine and detail methods for data collection and to analyse data itself
- The fifth chapter will be devoted to the considerations and conclusion based on the given context and the results of the data analysis

Chapter 2: Review of the Literature

2.1 Literature

Main scope of the dissertation is the creation of a model mainly (but not only) inspired to PMI knowledge areas and suitable to explain/evaluate the value that can be achieved in a project with next characteristics:

- related to an ICT SW Solution
- the scope considers the reengineering of a business process (BPR)
- use of outsourced resources

In that context we will pay particular attention to the impact of the project on internal employees and, in turn, the impact that the employees' feeling can have on the expected value.

We will proceed by explaining characteristics of Outsourcing and ICT SW Solution. Along the text, references to the impact that these topics exercise on employees and PM practices will be detailed so to finally explain the adaptation of the nine knowledge areas of PM to that scenario. The concept of uncertainty will be introduced as attribute of ICT SW Solutions as well as link toward PM to justify the adaptation of knowledge areas; we will try to explain how uncertainty is the driver that suggests the adoption of an Agile approach to PM and how it affects also the work of employees. Also the outsourcing practice provides its contribution to uncertainty in terms of virtual teams, scope definition, control, monitoring, contracts, and so on.

The above mentioned adaptation and characteristics of strongest points will be the source for the model and surveys. The next literature review will be aimed to put together the elements above in order to validate the model and depict the theoretical framework upon which the research is grounded on.

2.1.1 ICT SW Solutions

Oxford Dictionaries (n.d.) defines a “*solution*” as: “*Products or services designed to meet a particular need*”. In our context the “need” we have to meet is the reengineering of a business processes supported by an ICT SW solution and this reengineering must be fulfilled by accessing services in outsourcing. But the above definition uses also the plural form; it underlines how a solution could be made up of more than one component so that coordination and interdependence emerge by force. The analogy with Systems Thinking is also quite immediate so that concepts of complexity and feedback can be directly applied.

In the case of business processes, the complexity and interdependence of components are modelled from the concepts of the Enterprise Architecture. There is more than one framework aimed to draw up and manage enterprise architectures. Here we make reference to the Zachman's Enterprise Architecture (Zachman, 2008) model.

We use this model to trace the boundaries of assets in scope for the current research, considering an ICT solution as spread (and made up of all related assets) over all the layers of Zachman's Enterprise Architecture model with the exceptions of

- layers (or parts of them) that overlap with the “System of Records” of Gartner's Pace Layer model (Smith, 2011; at a glance this should be the ICT physical layer/s – and related assets - of the solution) and

- layers that do not belong to the ICT competence centre

Employees involved in maintaining, developing and supporting the solution (on the customer side) are included in mentioned boundaries and assets: they are the ones impacted from outsourcing practices, impacting the project success and in scope for that research.

2.1.2 Outsourcing

Accordingly to Elmuti, Grunewald and Abebe (2010), outsourcing is the “*strategic use of outside resources to perform activities that are usually handled by internal staff and resources*”. For our purposes, this corresponds to the usage of external resources to strategically support ICT projects related to the development of SW Solutions with concurrent BPR. Same authors write that “*outsourcing has created two kinds of victims: workers who have lost their jobs and suffered the hardship of trying to find new employment, and employees who have survived the outsourcing cuts but suffered the physical and psychological burdens of a downsized environment*”. In addition, Ulrich’s (2004) articles about intangible assets and capabilities, that are proper of human resources and defined as “*stable over time and more difficult for competitors to copy than capital market access, product strategy, or technology*” (this is differentiation!), further justifies the focus on employees’ attitudes in situations of outsourcing.

In any case, before accessing to outsourcing, customers should know what outsourcing is in order to properly evaluate the adoption of that practice. King (2009) suggests that knowledge could be explained in terms of know-why, know-what and know-how and this is the way we are going to adopt to analyse outsourcing.

Why (or why not): the pros and the cons

In agreement with Sriwongwana (2009), most common reasons to outsource are the search for cost effectiveness, for improving focus on core competencies by assigning non strategic activities to service suppliers and for delegating the management of HR functions (we think this is a reference to repeatable HR related activities). Elmuti and Kathawala (2001) further refine the boundaries evidencing the need to acquire last technologies at lower prices and to reduce financial risks. Many other reasons can encourage or discourage the approach to outsourcing. Among them we here mention the following ones:

1. Outsourcing could be applied to mechanical processes (i.e. activities that are not strategic and that do not need high customization) (Sriwongwana 2009).
2. Robinson and Kalakota (2004, cited in Sriwongwana, 2009) state that outsourcing often has plenty of hidden costs (updates, training, lack of skills) ,
3. Robinson and Kalakota (2004, cited in Sriwongwana, 2009) map outsourcing to bad feeling from employees as well as Kakabadse & Kakabadse (cited in Sriwongwana, 2009)
4. Sriwongwana (2009) further suggests to consider the impact of outsourcing the HR activities on the organisation because of its impact on the activities and employees that are not outsourced.
5. Kessler, Shapiro and Purcell (1999, cited in Sriwongwana, 2009) propose the point of view of employees that could be motivated if there are “career development opportunities; reward and training assessments; and organisational respect”.

6. Robinson and Kalakota (2004, cited in Sriwongwana, 2009) mention loss of confidential info and loss of control. Domberger (1998 cited in Sriwongwana, 2009, p.23-24) highlights the possibility of loss of skills and control.
7. Sriwongwana (2009, p.23-24) lists the needs of clarifying core competencies, paying attention to employees, taking time to “convert, integrate, compile and transfer” their activities. According to Marquez (2007b, cited in Sriwongwana, 2009, p.23-24), it is better if organisations try to develop their own HR activities before going for HR outsourcing. Herath and Kishore, R. (2009) map BPO to risks like loss of intellectual property and operational risks.
8. Logan, Faught and Ganster (2004, cited in Sriwongwana, 2009) suggest three pillars for a successful approach to outsourcing:
 - a. create a positive climate with respect to the provider’s perception
 - b. take care of employees’ satisfaction
 - c. empower communications between the decision-makers and the employees
9. As strategic choice outsourcing poses some other issues that as per Elmuti and Kathawala (2001) and Dhar and Balakrishnan (2006) could be:
 - a. Cultural clashes
 - b. Lack of objectives
 - c. Lack of coordination
 - d. Lack of trust
 - e. Customer Lock-in
10. Finally Qi and Chau (2012) involve relationships and trust as success factors (factors that we will find again along the research).
11. Sriwongwana (2011) points at some relevant consideration related to the choice to outsource:
 - (Klepper & Jones, 1998). These factors include; a lack of internal resource and knowledge, an organisation’s efforts to reduce and control HR activity costs, a focus on core competencies, and the ability to access the knowledge of the provider
 - Most HR practitioners recognise employees are the key for an organisation to gain a competitive advantage. Hence, it could be suggested that organisations should strongly consider the way in which employees are treated (Kessler, Shapiro & Purcell, 1999)
 - Given that it may cost organisations three to five times more to hire a new employee than to retain an existing employee (Bateson & Hoffman, 1999)

It is noticeable as no one of the above mentioned authors considers the delegation of core competencies or the possibility to get of differentiation via outsourcing. On the other hand, many of them focus on employees.

To summarize we conclude that, when we consider “the why” to outsourcing, we should:

1. Clarify what has to be outsourced:
 - a. are processes to be outsourced mechanical (so that they do not differentiate)?
2. Consider potential hidden costs like updates, training, lack of skills, ...
 - a. do we have previous experience or may we access external knowledge?
3. Consider impact on internal employees as:
 - a. What are the risks (for instance negative feelings)
 - b. What are the opportunities (for instance career development)

4. Evaluate how we will manage the change in terms of: creation of a positive climate against the outsourcer, care of employees, empowerment, reliability and trustworthiness of internal communications, cultural constraints, ...
5. Execute proper planning (due to objectives, coordination, ...) of the transformation in terms of processes and corporate culture
 - a. Are our processes suitable for outsourcing
 - b. What are the cultural changes we have to face?
6. Consider loss of internal skills, knowledge, intellectual property
 - a. May we protect the competitiveness of our business
7. Consider risks of customer lock-in
 - a. How to prevent that risk?

Answers to the questions above affect the budget of our project.

What

In our introduction we have tried to provide our view about the meaning of the relation between successful strategies and outsourcing. Our conclusion was that it is a mistake to outsource strategic assets (whatever we mean by assets) that are the ones sustaining strategic business processes. Even worse would be the outsourcing of strategic processes. Our conclusion was driven from the consideration that core processes are “different/unique” and if we differentiate via outsourcing we risk losing the control of our processes and their differentiation. The reasons are mainly two:

- because the strategic resource that is giving us differentiation reports to a different “business”
- because that difference will be of a short duration if recognized as valuable from the service provider

When we lose the control of our strategic processes we incur in the customer lock-in. If we perceive this situation then it means that we are no longer either autonomous and differentiating: we depend on the service provider and not differentiating because depending on standard services (if we want to maintain cost efficiency) and because the external provider will try to reuse our effective and efficient “differentiators” in case we want to go for a differentiating and costly path in outsourcing. So we should outsource “only” to reduce cost, acquire skills, freeing internal resources to allow them to focus on core competencies and so on.

But what is the effectiveness in terms of costs of an outsourcing project as the one in the scenario of this research? If the differentiation cannot be achieved via outsourcing, it seems that also benefits in terms of costs are difficult to be achieved while we want to outsource (for instance) the development of a SW solution to support a strategic business process. The reason is evident: this kind of process needs differentiation! This is a consequence of Harmon’s and Davenport’s (2007, p.15) idea of the relation between strategic process and need for customization: the more strategic a business process the higher the chance for a thorough customization (Harmon and Davenport, 2007, p.15). In addition, the handover to and from the service supplier, internal training, goodwill and other factors could be cause of additional unexpected costs.

So with respect to a core process (and having as scope its effectiveness and efficiency), it could be difficult to justify the outsourcing of strategic components and/or assets

(Sriwongwana, 2009) because of the difficulties related to justify benefits as differentiation (already explained) or costs (to be discussed in the research). It means that if a BPR should be adapted to a continuously challenging environment, it would not make sense to outsource assets that strategically support that change since benefits are not granted at all either in terms of differentiation or in terms of costs.

Mullur's model (cited in Sriwongwana, 2009) tries to simplify the choice related to "the what" to outsource and, in our opinion, it further confirms the hypothesis above:

Figure 3 - Mullur's model (cited in Sriwongwana, 2011)

The model is referred to competencies and people and we think it could be easily transformed and applied to business process so that the meaning is always:

- The corer a business process the lower the suitability for outsourcing (because of all the above mentioned issues: no differentiation, need for customization, no clear savings, risk of losing competencies, lock-in,...)
- The higher the need to manage the business process the lower the suitability for outsourcing (because of frequent changes and the points above)

This model is very similar, in terms of meaning, to Gartner's Pace Layer model and system of records as per Smith (2011).

Borrowing Prahalad and Hamel (1990): *"The embedded skills that give rise to the next generation of competitive products cannot be 'rented-in' by outsourcing. Too many companies have unknowingly relinquished their core competencies by cutting internal investment in what they mistakenly thought were 'cost centres' in favour of outside suppliers. Outsourcing may provide a shortcut to a more competitive product, but it typically contributes little to build the people-embodied skills that are needed to sustain future product leadership"*. We see the meaning of it as: if we outsource then we have to forget differentiation, get short term benefits and consider we won't get core or strategic skills; core/strategic skills (the ones that differentiate), competences, intellectual properties cannot be achieved via outsourcing and should not be surrendered to service providers.

All what above referred to what not to outsource is applicable to SW ICT Solutions and related assets that are supportive of such core processes.

To conclude, we think that it could be seen as a matter of control and value also in the following terms: when, for a customer, a service provider achieves value in terms of competitive advantage then it could mean the service supplier owns part of skills, knowledge, intellectual property that should be into the customer side as intangible assets (Ulrich, 2004) and strategic source of viability; that being the case, the customer is losing the control on its competitive advantage since differentiation and benefits in terms of costs in core business processes, are provided by all the assets (employees and intangible assets included) that provide customization, adaptation to the environment and viability.

How

In our research we would like to evidence how “the how” can impact employees and how, as a consequence, this impact heavily affects the project success. Many quantitative analyses try to explain employees’ dynamics in an outsourcing scenario by underlying the relation between employees’ motivation and outsourcing. Möhlmann and Groot (2013) relate outsourcing to the probability of loss of job. Roe, Smeelen and Hoefeld (2005) do the same though their analysis also includes opportunities. Nevertheless, accordingly to Herzberg’s theory (cited in Wong, 2007), we would classify the “possibility of being made redundant” as a factor belonging to the hygiene category so that an employer, while outsourcing, should consider proper ways to avoid that feeling in its employees.

Reading Sriwongwana (2011), bearing in mind what mentioned above and considering the impact that employees’ attitude can have on the project success we borrow Rothery’s and Robertson’s (1995, cited in Sriwongwana, 2011) typologies of outsourcing. In our opinion each one of them has a different impact on employees’ morale. They are:

1. full outsourcing: the name is self explanatory and underlines the outsourcing of a service at least in terms of implementation and maintenance. The impact on customer’s employees is evident. It is very complex and prone to uncertainty.
2. selective outsourcing: in that case some functionalities of a service are delivered internally to the customer and some others are outsourced; impact on employees should be less relevant than in the previous case
3. transitional outsourcing: this typology of outsourcing is accessed when obsolete and un-maintainable solutions require unavailable resources to be updated. Affected employees seem to be the ones taking care of the service in scope for outsourcing
4. transformational outsourcing: in that case the service provider acts as a tutor that enables the customer to move along a more valuable service. Customers’ employees will receive adequate training and skills for the support, maintenance and development activities. That kind of outsourcing could be reason for motivation

Who

Despite not in the knowledge definition as per King (2009) here we define “the who” as the “people impacted on the employer side from outsourcing”. Once more people impacted are the ones governing, supporting, maintaining and developing the ICT SW solution in scope for the BPR outsourcing; they are the ones present in all layers of the enterprise architecture for the given business process and belonging to the ICT department. Only

exceptions arise from the overlaps between the enterprise architecture and the system of records that are repeatable, static assets.

2.1.3 ICT and Uncertainty

Uncertainty (in business management)

Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson (2012) explain how, from an epistemological point of view, social sciences are a matter of constructionism, interpretation and uncertainty. Business management, as social science, is no exception. On cascade, the topic under investigation (as part of business management) inherits listed properties. Uncertainty is now a key point; Kashyap (2014) provides a definition of uncertainty in social sciences as: *“Any generalization in the social sciences cannot be both popular and continue to yield accurate predictions, or in other words, the more popular a particular generalization in the social sciences, the less accurate will be the predictions it yields”*. What we infer from that definition is that if we want to apply a certain rule to many situations to have as many users as possible adopt that rule then we have to abstract that rule and lose some precision; in that way we increase uncertainty. For our purposes, this is a way to say that best practices cannot guarantee certainty and so viability because, to be shared, they have to be driven from general (they seem to be proper for everybody but neither exactly effective nor efficient for anyone) principles that, being general, cannot produce certainties.

ICT and Uncertainty

There are no doubts that ICT management, per itself and as part of business management (Kashyap, 2014) is surrounded from a high level of uncertainty. In ICT project management the uncertainty pertains to both the outcome/s (i.e the what) and the way/s to reach the outcome/s (i.e the how). Willcocks (1993, cited in Galliers, 2009, p.221) underlines the relevance to assess the degree of uncertainty in ICT and the Royal Academy of Engineering (2004) mentions as there are no limits or scope constraints with respect to “the what” we can do with SW; rather there are limits in knowing what to do (Hall, Bodnar, cited in Royal Academy of Engineering, 2004)

So uncertainty is everywhere and extremely relevant in ICT because of the uncertain requirements and scope, continuous development of technologies and because changing, in ICT, costs much less than in other disciplines (i.e. re-framing a SW function costs less than re-building an elevator shaft).

In that context, Wysocki (2009) explains how to adapt project management in case of uncertainty. He distinguishes cases where uncertainty is related just to “the how” (i.e. agile PM) from cases where uncertainty is related to both “the how” and “the what” (i.e. extreme PM); examples provided by the author are related to software development (for the how) and pure research (for the what and the how). The author also details consequences and adaptive actions in terms of project management.

The agile paradigm: agility, uncertainty or risk management:

We have just mentioned as Wysocki (2009) sees the agile approach to project management under different levels of uncertainty. Here agile has the same meaning as flexible so that adopting an agile PM approach mainly means adopting “flexibility” and flexibility is what we need in situations of uncertainty. This is testified from many authors

who pair the two words (agile and flexible) in an interchangeable way. Both Thomke and Reinertsen (1998) and Mellis, Loebbecke and Baskerville (2011) claim for an agile/flexible approach in situations of uncertainty (even if the former in a field of competence different from ICT). With respect to ICT SW Solutions, they are just more prone to uncertainty than solutions belonging to other disciplines so that the level of agility has to be adapted in agreement.

At a glance, Agile PM is an iterative and adaptive methodology. Consequences go across project management and SDLC. In development of ICT SW solutions, agile SDLC (i.e. software development life cycle) is a common practice. Lientz (2011, pp.296-299) provides an overview of the SDLC methods' evolution, from waterfall (traditional and related to traditional PM) to SCRUM (just one among many agile approaches; SCRUMstudy, 2013). More in detail, in order to cope with uncertainty, the Agile PM owns a proper declination/paradigm which principles have been summarized in the agile manifesto by Beck et al. (2001). Gray (2010) also provides an interpretation of the twelve agile principles and it is interesting to read them in terms of risks. From that perspective it appears evident as the adoption of an agile approach is risks' management per itself (Ylimannela 2012). In the same order as per Gray (2010) risks are avoided via reduction of the:

1. customer dissatisfaction
2. impact of changes (to satisfy point above)
3. need to adapt interdependent components in case of changes and costs in case of mistakes (they are avoided via short iterations)
4. communication noise
5. interpersonal clashes by creating a proper work environment
6. risks arising from poor communications via face to face meetings
7. uncertainty on the customer side by continuously showing results obtained to the customer itself
8. bureaucracy, creation of lean processes (i.e. decision making) and autonomous teams
9. technical issues
10. complexity to support understanding
11. complexity in processes, communications, interpersonal relations
12. loss of information

From the above list of risks we infer that agile PM means: autonomy (since each iteration could claim for fast decisions), effective and efficient communications, team motivation (there is an implicit attempt of team building), lean decisional process; what the agile manifesto is trying to depict is an (as much as possible) autonomous project team in terms of decisions, scope and budget; a team able to work in a suitable environment where communications flows without noise. In other words this is a way of removing risks arising from lack of scope, budget, communications, motivation and decisional process that are crucial topics (in order to move on with projects) while changes are needed. We want just to stress further how the autonomy of the team is granted by putting customers and sponsors in close contact with (if not becoming members of) the project team and by creating proper processes; here the analogy with the outsourcing impact on processes is evident.

Nevertheless, there are also some issues related to the agile PM approach. In terms of agile SDLC, main obstacles to an agile approach could be identified in terms of rigidity and mobility (Leau, 2012) whereas in terms of agile PM they are difficulties in:

- locating and committing people with proper skills (because of the need for a fast delivery, learning cycle and technical excellence)
- maintaining trust, motivation and interpersonal relations
- arranging for autonomy and communications
- defining scope, budget and time (they are blurred concepts and consequence of uncertainty)

Once more, all the factors above underline, in our opinion, the purpose of proceeding despite changes: at each iteration the need for change is tested and, if the change is needed, dependent and proper adaptive counter actions are planned during the iteration: it claims for autonomy. To be effective and efficient, communications must be effective and efficient as well, so that co-located teams are more appropriate than virtual teams; in addition skills and trust must be adequate in order to proceed with the delivery; autonomy in terms of budget, schedule and requirement should be provided as well if we do not want to stop the delivery accessing “disconnected” processes for getting approvals; for that reason (without losing the control), all the stakeholders (sponsors included) must have a continuously open communication channel with the project team. Interesting is how, not like in traditional PM, it is no longer the project team that needs to “justify” the need for change but the customer itself that, being part of the uncertain situation, better understands the situation, supports adaptive actions and decides thanks to its constraints (i.e. priority, scope, budget and schedule). From that point of view this is a way to move responsibility from the project team to the /customer sponsor /business (Archerpoint, 2012, AgilePM Newsletter, 2008, Karlesky and Vander Voord, 2008).

A last mention is reserved to documentation; Karlesky and Vander Voord (2008) mention how documentation in agile PM must be flexible and agile. Source of documentation is the “source code” itself and unit tests. There is the need to document at a high level just processes and components that are unlikely to change.

Again, autonomy (Wang and Conboy, 2009 and Hodgson and Briand, 2013), adequate skills (because of the need for fast delivery), trust (Stasi, 2013), motivation, engaged stakeholders (from the sponsor to the technicians), proper processes and outcomes prone to change are key attribute for an agile project management. The agile approach is change (as risk) driven more than being just supportive with respect to changes; a lack of change (as risk) would justify the adoption of a traditional PM approach and waterfall SDLC method that allow more detailed expectations and planning in terms of golden triangle.

Other details related to agile PM, in terms also of SDLC, are (Miller, 2001) modularity, adaptability, proceeding pre increments, convergence, people-orientation and collaboration. Gorm Larsen, Fitzgerald and Wolff (2010) further add:

1. Individuals and Interactions over Processes and Tools
2. Working Software over Comprehensive Documentation
3. Customer Collaboration over Contract Negotiation
4. Responding to Change over Following a Plan

and:

1. as per Madaio (2011, p.33, own translation from the Italian text) the agile approach impacts the organization (it claims for the review of the concept of delegation at least)
2. scope, schedule and budget are uncertain concepts: if we pre-define budget and schedule then scope is uncertain on the other hand if we clearly define a scope budget and schedule cannot be pre-defined because of incurring changes and incremental management of the project.

With respect to that latter point, we think that literature is slightly “uncertain” here. For instance (and with respect to SCRUM), the concept of “frozen schedule” is related to the Sprints and not to the whole project and often we read that time and costs are given in agile PM. Our understanding is that this idea (i.e. fixed time and costs) is applicable to each iteration but not to whole project. The image below further clarifies that point considering time and budget as given within an iteration:

Figure 4 – Waterfall Vs SCRUM - Mahalakshmi and Sundararajan (2013)

At the end if the scope of the Project cannot change, we cannot forecast either budget or schedule (because we know the decisional elements will change at each iteration) so that we either have to leave them open to change or define at least one of them to give an end to the project (Balaji and Murugaiyan, 2012). Here we adopt (as previously written) the Wysocki (2009) definitions of:

- Agile: Scope (i.e. “the what”) is clear but the way (i.e. “the how”) to reach the scope is not
- Extreme: Scope and the way to reach the scope are not clear

From that perspective budget and time of the project cannot be pre-defined. The responsibility to finish the project “in” time and “within” budget is, if needed, at every cycle delegated to the customer and/or sponsor.

2.1.4 Project Management Knowledge areas

The next point to analyse is related to the nine knowledge areas of Project management. Here we would like to evaluate how mentioned areas, in literature usually bound to the traditional project management approach, are impacted and modified from an agile approach. Where and if appropriate, we will review these areas also in light of a project related to a SW Solution with BPR constraints.

Nine knowledge areas as per Project management Body of Knowledge (Wysocki, 2009 and Sanghera, 2010) are:

1. Integration: planning activities and execution
2. Scope: definition of the deliverables of the project
3. Time: definition of the duration and control
4. Cost: definition of the cost and control
5. Quality: planning assurance and control
6. HR: roles, skills, selection, motivation, relationships with functional manager and other HR related activities
7. Communications: toward stakeholders, project team and others
8. Risk: identification, assessment, mitigation, monitoring
9. Procurement: vendor selection, evaluation, management

Based on that list, the agile PM paradigm, and the typology of projects in scope, we think that:

- points 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 8 above have been already discussed in the section related to the agile methodology:
 1. Integration: each iteration could be considered as a complete cycle in a traditional PM approach (Sutherland and Ahmad 2011). So integration is maintained within each iteration (Wysocki, 2009). A new iteration is a new planning and new scenario for the integration knowledge area. There cannot be a project integration
 2. Scope: as per Mahalakshmi and Sundararajan (2013) we assume that the scope is given so no relevant changes can be evidenced with respect to the traditional project management approach
 3. Time: the choice of “the how”, that re-occurs at each iteration converging against the clear scope via an un-predictable (before its planning) iteration, and the need to re-plan, conditions the possibility to define the whole duration of a project since the project initiation. Time is uncertain while referred to the project
 4. Cost is uncertain; same consideration as per the time could be applied. Cost is uncertain while referred to the project
 5. Quality is verified at each iteration so it is clear in one single iteration, incremental and adaptive (eMids, 2007). It is uncertain as a whole
 8. Risks are higher than in traditional PM and agile PM is the response to them. In traditional risk management risks are regularly re-evaluated. In agile the review is further stressed from the purpose of the agile approach that is risk driven (Ylimannela, 2012).

We think that from points 3, 4, 5, 8 above and PM best practices, it arises the need for a contingency reserve in terms of time and budget that should be higher than the one needed in traditional PM. It could be justified if we want to have some plans different from being just hypothesis during the evaluation phase.

- With respect to the sixth knowledge area and as per Wang and Conboy (2009) and Hodgson and Briand (2013), we think there is the need to have and/or to plan for an HR management process that considers:
 6. Talent management (knowing who owns the right skills), motivation, autonomy, trust (Stasi, 2013) and clear info about the career (to avoid risks related to perception of redundancy) of employees

- Wysocki (2009) indicates how co-location is a pre-requisite in situations of high uncertainty. But this is not only a question of “how to communicate” so that Gray (2010) underlines as all the stakeholders (from the customers and sponsor to the team members) must be short circuited in order to speed up the process and guarantee its efficiency and effectiveness: if we want to deliver, the decisional infrastructure must be flexible (and autonomous.) and it must be properly spread in an agile project. Clearly it impacts the organization (Madaio, 2011):
 7. In that context communications gets the particular meaning of planning for co-location in order to support an agile approach and processes’ review

- The last point to consider is related to procurement and we would approach that point in terms of contracts. Sollish et al. (2011) explain how cost-plus contracts are the most suitable ones in situations of high uncertainty. They also tell us that, in order to motivate the supplier to contain or lower the costs, there is the need for a high level of trust that can be (for instance) achieved via promises for further collaborations, partnerships, joint ventures and so on. The impact of the proper contract on project success is further testified from Gopal et al. (2003) and Herath and Kishore (2009) who say that there is high uncertainty on contracts yet.
 9. In that context procurement means:
 - i. considering an uncertainty driven typology of contracts like cost-plus contract
 - ii. establishing a high level of trust between organizations (i.e. the customer and supplier ones)

Absolutely crucial is, independently of the knowledge area, the creation of a proper organization in order to create short-circuit decisions and processes. This is due (as seen) in order to provide decisional autonomy and foster an agile approach.

2.1.5 *Project success*

Since we need to know if the characteristics provided can condition the success or not of a project, we need to compare them against the project success that, seen the quantitative approach we follow and the fact that the business case considers usually quantitative metrics, will be defined as the variance between the initial scope, budget and time and the actual scope, budget and time.

2.1.6 *Conclusions – The model*

From the above described characteristics of outsourcing, uncertainty and agile approach, project management and SW ICT Solutions with BPR constraint we argue that many of them, despite qualitative characteristics, risk to have a relevant impact on the success of the project. For that reason, in order to better “understand” what success means, all of

them should be (in some way) considered during the evaluation phase of the decision-making process. This is what would like to measure.

2.2 Theoretical framework

Our theoretical framework relies on classical (Taylor, 1947 and Fayol, 1950, cited in Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2012) and human relations (Roethlisberger and Dickson, 1939 and Herzberg, Mausner and Snyderman, 1959, cited in Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2012) oriented views of business management, change management theory (Lewin, cited in Shirey, 2013 and Lippit, cited in Kritsonis, 2005), uncertainty reduction theory (Manderbach, 2011), communication theory (Lasswells' communication model - cited in Muhammadali, 2011 -, principles of cybernetics and DeVito - cited in Sosnoski, n.d. – for the feedback), rational decision-making process (Schoenfeld, 2011, cited in Lunenburg, 2010) and decision theory (Bernoulli, 1738 cited in Suhonen, 2007 and von Neumann and Morgenstern, 1944, cited in Suhonen, 2007).

We think that the classical view of business management (a still dominating theory that, as per Taylor and Fayol - cited in Parker and Lewisa, 1995 -, sees management and work as a branch of engineering in terms of interchangeable parts and possibility to reduce skilled activities in simple - and so interchangeable - ones) approaches that practice in terms of activities that can be planned and measured. Despite the “knowledge divide” between the current global world (and the increased uncertainty) and the “local” world in place while classical view of management was postulated, companies still use a scientific/classical/positivist approach while making decisions.

While deciding about the value of a project, companies create business cases around “expectations of clear facts” as ROI, pay-back or other financial indicators. Decisions are then taken throughout a rational decision making process (as per Schoenfeld, 2011, cited in Lunenburg, 2010) by evaluating alternatives and choosing the one that is considered to be the more valuable from a positivist perspective (Bernoulli, 1738 cited in Suhonen, 2007 and von Neumann and Morgenstern, 1944, cited in Suhonen, 2007).

In very complex and uncertain cases like the one under investigation (i.e. projects related to ICT SW Solutions in Outsourcing with BPR), companies need to share (sometimes they create with them) with the outsourcers the meaning of the value expected (and considered in the business case) and the way they have planned to reach the value. This sharing activity is due in order to reach a common view and attitude and to reduce uncertainty (Berger and Calabrese 1975, cited in Manderbach, 2011).

But how can companies share this view in a positivist and scientific way? Our hypothesis relies on formal documents. We consider here contracts and formal documents as a proper and factual place where to share the mentioned information: if within these factual sources of information nothing is reported in terms of expectation, values and view then, from a positivist point of view, the classical approach could be questionable. So, in our hypothesis, if classical approach means positivism then in turn positivism means facts and (in our case) facts mean clear (to measure the weight of which we will use Likert scales which the items are inspired by maturity models as per Farah - 2011 – and CMMI - 2011 -) statements in formal documents.

In terms of communication theory (Lasswells, cited in Muhammadali, 2011) the expected “how” is made up via the aforementioned formal documents as enablers of factual

(positivist) communications in order to allow feedback (as per the principles of cybernetics and viable systems) based on facts; factual feedback to allow the customer to check the viability of the project are out of our scope. Once more, feedback allowed from facts stated in contracts and produced from suppliers are, for the customers, the way to verify the effectiveness and efficiency of their choices and so the viability of the company. In that sense we are moving our communication theory against the one postulated by DeVito (cited in Sosnoski, n.d.). This need to clearly communicate is further underlined by the Uncertainty reduction theory (Berger and Calabrese 1975, cited in Manderbach, 2011) where we interpret this theory as “the higher the uncertainty the higher the need for clear (factual) communications ... in order to reduce uncertainty”.

But in our opinion (and due to claimed high ration of projects failures) this is not enough because financial indicators (used in business cases) are groups of indicators among which, “sometimes”, change is not considered so that they do not deal with well known obstacles that seriously affect the performances of projects. In accordance with Lewin’s theory of change (cited in Shirey, 2013), transition is something that “*involves coaching to overcome fears and clear communication to avoid losing sight of the desired target, which is a new and improved reality*”. Furthermore Lippit’s theory of change (cited in Kritsonis, 2005) considers the assessment of “*resources and motivation of the change agent. This includes the change agent’s commitment to change, power, and stamina*”. Above definitions are enough in agreement with the human resource view of management as per Mayo (1933, cited in Steers, Mowday and Shapiro, 2004) and Roethlisberger and Dickson (1939, cited in Steers, Mowday and Shapiro, 2004) which assumes a relation between motivation and productivity on one side and treatment on the other (the better the treatment the higher the possible productivity). So transition and commitment of human resources are crucial factors for a successful change as well as source of costs. For that reason, change and human resources must be part of the business case and part of the formal documentation.

Nevertheless change management and human resources are rarely properly considered in business cases being qualitative topics and for that reason difficult to “manage”.

But under this umbrella, what is failing in terms of project execution? Is the project failing or is the decisional positivist approach to business management (and related business cases lacking of proper details) failing?

Again, during the decisional process, companies do not consider change management, they reduce qualitative analysis into quantitative one (in order to be able to “manage”) but do not share facts that they expect to occur (neither with suppliers nor with staff), relying on a human resource view of management to fix that gap (the gap related to communication and actual management): so we decide in quantitative terms but act in qualitative or sometimes mixed ones.

All of it seems to us slightly inconsistent and this is what we would like to check by comparing business cases (part of them) with project success and trying to observe if some PM knowledge areas or HR insights can help in improving decisions justifying the results of the projects.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

Although nominalism and constructionism seem to be the proper approach for a research related to social sciences and although business management is a social science, many business managers approach business management itself with a perspective inspired by realism and positivism so that only rationale decision are considered as reliable. However, experience, evidence and literature testify a relevant number of unsuccessful decisions that can be ascribable to this approach. For that reason (and with respect of the topic object of this research) it could be interesting to verify if the cost-benefit-ROI analysis (which in the business case is the part used in the evaluation phase of our decision making process) is lacking relevant attributes aimed to foster a more reliable decision making process.

We need to clarify one point before proceeding; this point is related to the meaning of “big size projects” that we have reported in the title of the research. We used this acronym in order to give the research more chances in terms of impact on staff/employees on the customer side. Nevertheless during the development of the research we faced the issue of defining the mentioned “size”. Considering the direction of the research (i.e. also guaranteeing impact on human resources), we have thought to consider “big size projects with impact on human resources” as “projects related to business process reengineering”. The reasons for this decisions are supported by the definition we gave of the outsourcing as “internal to external shift” (so that something should change for internal staff) and the fact that in the Enterprise Architecture a business process is set at a very high level in the hierarchy of layers so that it is likely that a change implemented there will impact many lower levels and the related staff.

Based on the above assumptions, surveys and literature, a quantitative supportive model (the hypothesis is that the model will be supportive during the evaluation phase) and a mixed one (both aimed to validate the cost-benefit-ROI actual model) will be proposed: their scope is to compare their effectiveness and efficiency with the effectiveness of the related project whose execution depends on the decision consequent to the evaluation (in our case it is the execution of projects in the field of the ICT SW solution with BRP constraint and Outsourcing). Both models will be then populated via surveys and data collected from formal documentation. Being formal documentation a source of “facts” (and evidence of the communication between the customer and the service supplier as well as the evidence of needed resources), we hope in that way to maintain a close coherence with a positivist approach.

From a different perspective, the entire research is aimed to frame and evaluate effectiveness and efficiency of projects in scope for the research, comparing in various ways, during the evaluation, the inputs of the cost-benefit analysis (predictor variables) with the outputs that are the characteristics of the success of the project (dependent variables).

While the first qualitative part of the research will be aimed to frame the environment where the aforementioned projects are run, the second part of the research will consider inputs from the first part, the literature aimed to sustain the analysis of the qualitative research and additional literature in order to frame the model/s that we would like to validate (always related to big-size ICT outsourced projects with BPR) and the definition of

success. In turn the model/s will be the source for the surveys. The survey design is a mixed one between inferential and factual surveys:

- inferential because we would like to establish relations among concepts
- factual because we would like to collect information from facts that in our case are formal documents

Since it is not expected to find a huge amount of factual data sources available, the “issue” related to sampling will be mainly related to surveys. Responsibility to properly cluster the population and the next random sampling will rely on project managers and/or people filling-in the survey since data suppliers consider this typology of information as highly sensitive so that we cannot control it. The second part should answer the first question of the research.

The third part of the research will be driven as the first one with the difference that projects in scope will evidence attributes that belong to the field of competence of the constructionism and the model used will be a mixed one. The third part should answer the second question of the research.

4th The fourth part of the research will be a stage of synthesis of the second and third parts and it will be aimed to make a proposal of the most proper model arising from previous analysis. The fourth part should answer the third question of the research.

Two additional points deserve to be underlined here:

1. the whole research is not aimed to compare clear quantities of allocated resources against the success but how clearly these resources were considered and managed by both parties (i.e. the customer and the supplier) or, from a different perspective, if there is any maturity in that evaluation process. So we won't propose formulas for allocating a proper quantity of a certain resource in order to deal with a successful project we rather hope to be able to find some insight related to the awareness and maturity needed; in other words, the impact that our ability in defining proper resources has on project success.
2. we define the success of a project in terms of the canonical definition of PMI as scope, budget, duration and quality. This fact implicitly means that we do not “measure” the success of projects in terms of their benefits (that, in general, can be reasonably measured only after the delivery of the scope) so that the analysis of variables related to benefits belonging to the costs-benefit-ROI analysis is, in principle, inaccessible to us. For that reason we won't consider the “benefits” in the models despite in agile PM we could expect intermediate benefits per each delivery cycle. It would have caused an additional level of complexity that we won't manage in that research.

3.2 Research Design and Approach

The design approach will be framed around two main pillars:

- a qualitative pillar
- a quantitative pillar

so that we are going to approach the research with a mixed method as per Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson (2012, pp.61-62): the quantitative one will be the dominant approach that will follow the qualitative one. This is also referred as *handmaid* method where the qualitative research is aimed (together with other sources like literature) to sustain and develop the quantitative research. As initial insight, qualitative data collection will be approached via interviews and quantitative data collection via factual and inferential surveys.

The main purpose of qualitative investigation is getting knowledge and unfolding the practice of outsourcing. This is in agreement with the following assumptions:

- uncertainty is given (it is a fact) and it impacts the other topics of the research in different ways
- project management is a consolidated practice (although it is continuous improvement)
- uncertainty forces an agile approach to project management and, in ICT, agile approaches own a proper known paradigm
- change management theory owns a proper declination

All of it allows us to have enough elements to singularly and/or jointly analyze each of the aforementioned practice but nothing can be sustained about outsourcing without a qualitative and investigative pre analysis. In other words our purpose is to analyze outsourcing in situations of high uncertainty: why, what and how outsourcing is managed in a scenario like the one proposed as per the header of the research. It doesn't mean we won't consider evidence of emergences also in fields different from outsourcing and within the scope of our research.

Once the concept of outsourcing via supportive interviews and literature, we will then create the evaluation model/s and the model of the success. The evaluation model/s will be made up of key attributes related to the main areas that characterize the research: uncertainty, outsourcing, project management (and agile project management), ICT and change management.

Moreover, in order to find possible discrepancies or moderate answers to questions related to attributes of the model/s, just for the questions that will involve employees/staff (mainly related to change management), we will create a parallel survey for employees so to verify if "facts" in formal documents correspond to facts in the actual execution of the project.

After that, data collection and instances of the model/s and success will be available, we will then compare quantitative instances and mixed (made up of quantitative and qualitative attributes) instances among them and against their correspondent instances of success to observe:

- which ones are the most successful and
- which factors are the ones that mostly impact the success

From there we should infer answers to the first and second question.

At least two limits arise from that approach:

1. the choice of the attributes of the model/s is deliberate

2. the classification between quantitative and mixed models has to be clarified later on once we get actual instances of the model/s

The second point above is a crucial one for the research because the mentioned classification impacts the consequent results of the analysis related to finding relations between the actual instances of the models and their dependent variables (project success). Actually we think that it is very difficult to classify instances of the models without knowing the values of their attributes. It could be that, having instances, we have to deal with success related to quantitative or mixed models as a continuum rather than as discrete and classifiable concepts, being the plethora of combination of attributes and related values potentially very wide. This point has to be sorted out before starting with the quantitative analysis.

3.3 Justification for using Qualitative & Quantitative Approaches

As we have written, for some reasons that are allegedly ascribable to western culture, a social science like business management tends to be managed in quantitative reductionist terms. It is curious to notice as, in general, the higher the level of uncertainty the tougher the efforts provided in trying to reduce the understanding of uncertain scenarios via their reduction into “manageable” quantitative metrics. Nevertheless we believe that uncertainty is the mother of constructionism so that, perhaps, it could be proper not to reduce business management only to quantitative terms.

Management of ICT is not an exception and (if needed) it further testifies the above relation between uncertainty and quantitative approach: perhaps because of the fact that its lower communication layer is made up of sequences of 0 and 1 (that could reinforce the idea of ICT management in quantitative terms), over time ICT has been drawn up to natural sciences. Evidences of this quantitative approach are everywhere and they embrace theories (like the classical view of management) as well as many empirical corroborating evidences (Tarhan and Demirors, 2012 and Galliers, 2009, p.10)

But, if we have a look at the success rate of projects in the field of ICT, we can observe that the number of failures is relevant at least as much as the strengths provided in the adoption of the positivist approach (Qi and Chau, 2012 with particular respect to outsourcing, Roulstone and Burlington, 2008, p.6, Smith, Bruyns and Evans, 2011 and many other authors).

Failures pop up from everywhere but failures are a matter of success and success is a subjective concept (Basten, Joosten and Mellis, 2011) that cannot be justified only in terms of adherence to the planning.

So what does success mean in this context? We see here at least two different possible answers to this question (Shenhar, Levy and Dvir, 1997 and de Witt, 1988):

- Adherence to planning (the short term; the how or doing the thing right)
- Adherence to strategies (the long term; the what or doing the right thing)

With the expression “adherence to strategies” we do not mean that a project satisfies the customers’ expectations and respects quality criteria (that are common requirements in terms of success) rather we refer to this concept in terms of the benefits provided from the project outcomes in the long term, the benefits provided during the operational life-cycle of

the deliverables. From this perspective success corresponds to the benefits that the outcomes of the project deliver.

From a slightly different perspective a similar definition of success is adopted while managers make strategic decisions (and planning for changes and related projects) via business cases and within the cost-benefit-ROI analysis. Cost-benefit-ROI analysis is a forecast of expected “cons & pros”: where “the cons” (or costs) are “cacheable” facts having clear evidence during the project lifecycle (to simplify we will exclude running costs), “the pros” (or benefits) can be faced only after the delivery of the outcomes of the project so once the outcomes are operational and after the closure of the project itself. It means that the effectiveness of actual “pros” (their adherence to and effectiveness toward strategies) can be verified only after the delivery of the outcomes of a project (although in agile scenarios we could consider intermediate pros but we need to simplify here). Again, this is not a matter of customers’ expectations and quality of deliverables rather this is a matter of long term measures aimed to compare the expected results (the pros in the ROI) against the actual ones in order to validate the benefits for the strategies.

All of this forces us to define success as “*measured by product and project quality, timeliness, budget compliance, and degree of customer satisfaction*” (Project Management Institute 2008) and to set limits of our analysis to the point in time when the project is closed so that we cannot work on project effectiveness. The reasons are quite evident:

- Lack of information
- Lack of resources

But the part of the ROI that we consider more closely in relation to the aforementioned boundaries of the research (we consider costs as mainly related to project efficiency), is especially managed as a quantitative topic and/or in accordance with the classic view of management. We think that the reason for this is simple: cost estimates, although uncertain, are considered as facts (forecasts of future invoices) whereas benefits are expectations (intangible values during the evaluation). If needed, Roulstone and Burlington (2008) underline the relevance and meaning of the ROI as methodology, process and so, in final analysis, the relevance of the cost-benefit-ROI analysis as a quantitative matter (this is, in our opinion, also testified by Higgins, 2013 and Schottmuller, 2013).

From what stated above we infer that:

1. The approach to ICT management is quantitative
2. The decision-making process is rational (Schoenfeld, 2011, cited in Lunenburg, 2010)
3. The cost-benefit-ROI analysis is mainly quantitative
4. Success cannot be evaluated if not in terms of schedule, budget, deliverables and quality
5. Projects often fail in terms of success as per the above definition and thanks to quantitative decisions
6. We would like to falsify the quantitative approach

The above list summarises the reasons for a quantitative approach. This unflinching commitment to quantitative failure is the reason for the quantitative analysis (integrated with qualitative criteria) of the topic: since the approach is quantitative and it is plenty of failures, we would like to verify the validity of that approach comparing it with a mixed one by using a quantitative design (qualitative attributes will be managed in quantitative terms).

All of it is also (at least in part) the reason for the qualitative analysis that will be aimed to see if quality can in part explain failures once decisions are managed mainly in quantitative terms. In particular we think of having found in the ROI a proper starting point to justify the qualitative analysis.

In that sense our questions are: does it make sense to refine the quantitative approach? Wouldn't it be better to understand the dynamics behind a quantitative approach (that shows so many limits)? Isn't the ROI slightly ambiguous? We will answer the first question with a negative statement. In our opinion, enough work has been done in that direction. So we will proceed toward the traces depicted by the other questions.

With this purpose in mind we think that, at a glance, the cost-benefit-ROI analysis could also be seen as a quantitative analysis (Higgins, 2013, Schottmuller 2013) but we do not think it is the only interpretation since the ROI is an index (i.e. an aggregate of aggregated values).

Before providing some examples related to the point above, we need to explain how we see the relation among different SBUs (i.e. strategic business units), strategies, tactics and resources. We assume that the mission of a company could be defined in terms of "maintenance of its viability". Via given processes executives define strategies to maintain company viability so that for instance (Morris and Pinto, 2007):

1. The strategy that executives define answer to the question: what (strategy) should we adopt to maintain the company viable?
2. The answer provided could be: we must be flexible (this is the strategy)
3. The question to answer then should be: how (tactic) can we be flexible?
4. The answer to this question should involve relevant SBU representatives, the ones who will implement "the how" (this is the tactic).
5. The answer provided could be: we must outsource (or just ICT – one among many SBUs - must outsource).
6. Now, for the SBUs, "outsourcing" becomes the strategy to follow and they should understand how to outsource.
7. As seen, losing intellectual property is a risk in outsourcing so when SBUs answer the question "how (tactic) should we outsource?", they should know that they have to avoid the mentioned risk and allocate proper resources for that purpose.

From point 6 above it is clear that tactics sustain strategies and that, in order to be implemented, tactics claim for resources.

Moreover, the above cascade process is not limited to just two hierarchical levels in an organization but can continue along the hierarchy. We also think that this cascade effect could be applied to project teams as well, being them (in our understanding) comparable to temporary SBUs (Turner and Muller 2003).

This cascade effect is similar to the one proposed by Turner (2009)

Figure 5 – Cascade of objectives (Turner, 2009)

but applied to SBUs, strategies (“the what” of each SBU), tactics (“the how” of each SBU) and allocation of resources rather than portfolio, program, objectives, strategies and so on (the how of each SBU aimed to sustain its what).

To try to explain our understanding of the role of the resources, we further borrow from Turner (2009) the business planning process:

Figure 6 - Business Planning Process (Turner, 2009)

so that mixing our perspective to the two diagrams from Turner (2009), the cascade of objectives and the business planning process we obtain a picture that, we hope, can show the role of resources:

Figure 7 - Cascade of Strategies on Tactics and role of resources

As consequence it means that we can classify resources based on the strategy they have been allocated for. In our opinion this is relevant since, in this way, we can be aware of the relation between a given resource and the related strategy; on the other hand it doesn't say us anything about the method we have used to define the resources. So, how have we proceeded in order to allocate this resources? Do we have assigned a resource in a deliberate way? Is there any learning process in our "allocation process" that allow us to improve, over time, the allocation? In the sense we think that the "allocation process" the higher our maturity and for that reason our questionnaires will be inspired to a maturity model.

To further explain this point one example could be useful. As we know, the ROI is mainly made up of cost and benefits so that, among many costs, we can include an item related to "travels". But what is the addressee ("the what", the strategy we are going to support with that cost allocation) for which these resources have been allocated? In effect, in the same item, managers can include costs for many purposes; for instance, in the above example, they could have had included travels devoted to managing the change rather than travels to fulfill the actual work so that a strategic classification of allocation of the resources is useful to understand their ability in strategic planning of resources. It would also complicate the possibility of diverting resources from their strategic purpose.

"Knowing the strategy" (the what) to which a resource is related could be compared to the awareness (or maturity) of our decisions in supporting our strategies item by item and strategic point by strategic point and knowing how (i.e. by chance, deliberately, with a process,...) to chose the proper resources could correspond to the level of awareness (or maturity level).

We would hope to find such classifications (that in our assumption would be the fact that proves that business managers know – at least with respect to this topic - how they are supporting strategies – in every single strategic detail - and try to preserve strategies by clearly mapping allocated resources to related strategies in order to make the diversion of resources from their original strategic purpose harder) in formal documents (i.e. facts) always for the same reason: fostering communications and decreasing uncertainty.

The process we use to define resources testifies our maturity level in strategically managing the business case and the related project. This is the reason why we will connect the questions conveyed in terms of “the what(s)” to a maturity model; we are not going to consider (nor can argue about) the amount of resources allocated rather we are going to consider for which strategy and how they have been allocated so to understand if there is any maturity level to support strategies and a strategic learning process for the allocation of resources.

We have just seen an example of potential manipulation of the ROI but another similar case occurs when costs are too high to justify a certain choice (consider that the ROI is often the business opportunity - Higgins, 2013 -). If under the item “travel” we include travels for managing the change and the cost exceeds the benefits or do not justify the choice, it is possible that we will tend to consider costs for the change no longer relevant (Williams, 1972 and Higgins, 2013, p.29) in order to promote the business case. It is likely that we won't be chased for uncertain costs that cannot be classified as facts. If not enough, internal travel costs are easy to conceal because there are not perceivable as facts like external consultancies. So, if the ROI is not good enough, it is easy just not to declare these costs and, in that way, increase the profitability of the ROI itself to get the approval of the opportunity.

Abandoning the misapplication of the cost-benefit-ROI analysis, similar situations can occur while we state a scope that could conceal a different purpose. Companies often rely on standardized and industrialized processes and products in order to have an open door to outsourcing and/or being able to change the outsourcer facing a low impact. Remembering the characteristics of outsourcing, we think that locking-in the supplier could be a way to maintain the control on intellectual property (for instance) or control the supplier itself as potential competitor (Altenburg, 2006). Nevertheless it is evident that we cannot inform the supplier about this purpose and it clashes with the need for clear communications in situations of high uncertainty. So if a project is executed with that purpose what is the right perspective from which to evaluate the success? :

- The one of the outsourcing project that (perhaps) fails because it takes more budget and time than initially planned to conclude the project or
- The one of the achieved flexibility, preservation of intellectual property (by locking-in the supplier) and control of a potential competitor that has no real limits of budget and time because too relevant in terms of benefits/flexibility

What we think is that the understanding of the plethora of environments, strategies, tactics and politics needs a qualitative analysis since it is pure constructionism and interpretation. And the reason is simple: how can we hypothesize, envisage or abstract situations like the ones described above without knowing social dynamics of business environments. If in one hand (and for obvious reasons) we cannot manage the research with experimental or quasi-experimental design, on the other hand, how can we envisage an abstraction of something that is complex and unknown as the examples above? This is where qualitative research helps us with the collection of details thanks to which we can induce a holistic understanding of the reality using a bottom-up approach. Then this general understanding will be analyzed via a top-down deductive and quantitative path aimed to confirm relations among predictor and dependent variable of the understanding (i.e. the model) itself (Sage, 2007).

So findings of qualitative research are mandatory to develop, integrate and hopefully improve quantitative and/or mixed models.

3.4 Data Collection Methods

As more or less explicitly written, we will collect data mainly via interview and surveys. Addressees of surveys will be “people informed of the facts” so people who can have or have had access to factual sources of information: mainly project managers and CIOs.

Interviews will be managed via direct phone calls, equivalent voice systems like Skype or other IT related media (emails, chats and so on). We will try to have more than one interview with each project manager in order to get their trust and to obtain more valuable information and perspectives.

In our initial hypothesis we proposed to collect data from the supplier side (for the collection of the facts related to the decisional process and project) and from the customer side (for the collection of the data related to the management of the change and next impact on staff). We proposed it convinced that the supplier is the one that really knows the outsourcing practices.

However we faced serious issues in collecting data from staff and data related to the attributes of the success so that, by force, we have had to accept the possibility of allowing the customers to fill in the surveys related to the project and decisional process. Always with respect to the surveys, we have already mentioned how we are going to use two web based questionnaires:

- The first aimed to collect info about project success, change management and outsourcing
- The second aimed to collect data related to the change management, filled in from customer staff and useful to moderate or weigh answers received in the first survey

We have also stressed the idea of using factual sources of information to fill in the data (like contracts and formal documents) so to maintain an extreme positivist approach.

3.5 Application of Interview for Primary Data Collection

Interviews will be managed via open in-depth interviews which in turn will be analyzed with a content analysis methodology in order to evaluate instances of emergent words of phrases so to get a proper understanding of the topic within the scope of this research. As per paragraph 3.3 (i.e. “*Justification for using Qualitative & Quantitative Approaches*”) above, interviews (the qualitative approach) are aimed to understand scenarios like the ones in the just referenced section and in focus for this research, so to unfold complexity. We will apply interview as it follows in order to:

- evaluate the complexity
- give a frame to the mixed approach
- create proper surveys
- analyze the results
- evaluate limits of the research
- suggest further scenarios
- propose topics for further research
- other

3.6 Conclusion

We start from the evidence that many decisions taken on the basis of a quantitative approach do not justify project failures (or alleged ones). Then we take that chance to see if different evaluation models can justify results by trying to compare quantitative instances with mixed ones. We further assume that evaluations are fulfilled via a specific element of the business case that is the cost-benefit-ROI analysis (that many times coincides with the business case itself - Higgins, 2013 -). Not yet satisfied, we further close the scope of the research to the cost part of the cost-benefit analysis as it arises from the definition itself of the success and limits of the research. To maintain a positivist, fact-based approach also during the data collection, we ask the data suppliers to fill in the surveys with data collected from formal documents agreed between the customer and the service supplier.

To create qualitative and mixed models we will rely on interviews and web based questionnaires: the former to better understand the topic under investigation and, with the additional support of literature, to create the model/s; the latter to instantiate the model/s.

Questions in the surveys won't ask for quantities but, being inspired by maturity models and framed via Likert scales, will ask for awareness and processes in order to try to show the degree of awareness/maturity that sustains each decision related to the scenario under evaluation. Furthermore, questions will try to verify which is the strategy (“the what”) that each allocated resource should support: we will ask “what is the strategic topic we are considering while allocating the related resource and do we have a procedure to evaluate the proper resource to sustain that topic?”. Considering that “the what” corresponds to strategies, we are asking for a classification of costs/resources per strategic topic (i.e. what is the strategy we are supporting by allocating a certain resources?). In that way we classify costs/resources per strategic need. Each resource is strategic because resources sustain (in various ways) the strategies of the company and we would like to map the whole resources-strategies chain at a level of granularity that should allow us to understand the consequences of made decisions. We see it as a kind of strategic allocation of resources or strategic cost accounting (Perkins, 2005).

In other words, this research could be seen as an assessment of the maturity level of the evaluation phase in the decision-making process in terms of strategic allocation of resources; outcomes from the evaluation phase will be used as basis for the comparison of the success of the project in terms of strategic allocation of resources and maturity level in the determination and allocation of such resources.

Chapter 4: Analysis and discussion of Data

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter we would like to explain the methodologies applied to data collection and frame the results of qualitative and quantitative data analysis. We would also like to further try to explain interdependence between qualitative and quantitative analysis.

Before starting, we need to admit that the header of the research contains several explicit and implicit topics so that, sometimes, we are not sure about the most proper answers to questions like “What is the scope of the research? What is the dominating one?”. We think that topics per se like Project Management, Agile Project Management, Outsourcing, Human resources management, Change Management and Uncertainty (the implicit topic and perhaps key driver) are not easy subjects to approach. Putting them all together could just cause additional confusion.

Among all the above topics, the one we most felt lacked proper knowledge was the Outsourcing one and for that reason we focused most of the research on this topic, particularly on interviews. In other words we have implicitly considered topics under discussion as follows:

- as given or static:
 - uncertainty
 - agile project management
 - change management
- as unknown or dynamic:
 - outsourcing

We began with the idea of studying the impact of the outsourcing practice on internal resources/staff (and vice versa) then we added the attributes related to ICT Software Solutions and BPR to the scenario:

- the former (i.e. ICT SW Solutions) to guarantee uncertainty and related consequences on project management
- the latter (i.e. BPR) to guarantee impact on customer staff and need for change management (at least we consider it as an assumption)

Based on this assumption, we can say that the current research has been driven by a handmaid method (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2012) where the qualitative analysis has been used mainly to refine the understanding of the Outsourcing practice. Details related to other areas of investigation have been inferred from some interviews and literature. The understanding of Outsourcing itself has been refined via a thorough search of literature.

Finally, the knowledge achieved as described above has been the input for the creation of the qualitative and quantitative models used for creating the questionnaires and data collection. Actual instances of the models (retrieved via the questionnaires) have given form to the basis of the quantitative versus mixed approach analysis.

4.2 Qualitative analysis

There should be no discontinuity between the results of the analysis in this section and the 1st Chapter of the Dissertation since the latter should be the result of our hypotheses, which have been reviewed and refined in the light of interviews: we began proposing our thoughts to interviewees and with their contribution we got additional insights in order to change or confirm ideas.

Over time, we got in touch with more than a hundred people working mainly in the ICT field, coming from multiple countries and holding different roles: we went from CEOs to employees via project managers and CIOs without disregarding representatives of Trade Unions.

Due to the different focuses and so views represented by interviewees, we had to adapt our approach to addressees accordingly so that to company representatives we have underlined the chance to get, thanks to the results of the dissertation, additional insight potentially useful for a better decisional model; on the other hand, to trade union representatives we have underlined the possibility of getting additional insight related to company dynamics and impact on employees.

We think that the level of trust achieved was quite good mainly because of the chosen topic (i.e. outsourcing). The wide net of relationships that we were able to create and the fact that no one asked for the signature of an NDA are the evidence of it. Nevertheless we not always succeeded with an in-depth approach with interviews because of lack of resources, distance and actual availability.

We proceeded with open and closed questions. The main question/s was/were: "What is outsourcing, what is its impact on customer staff and what should we consider while opting for this practice?" Answers included documents and references to additional stakeholders as potential interviewees and other forms of collaboration.

Interviewees (denaturalized interviews are reported in the Appendix) had the chance to review the result of the ongoing activity by receiving a copy of the 1st Chapter or analogous document for preview and explicit or implicit validation. Interviews were sustained either via speakerphone or, in some unlucky cases, by e-mail.

The same text related to denaturalized interviews (and reported in the Appendix) was framed via NVivo. Despite we were interested in getting quantitative insight, we used NVivo to code parts of our text in order to classify them, thus observing which concepts were emerging more frequently than others. The fact of dealing with denaturalized text definitely excluded the chance (together with time availability and other constraints) for a grounded analysis; due to the above mentioned reasons, NVivo was used mainly for quantifying the number of instances in which a coded concept was popping up during interviews.

The result of the analysis appears as follows:

Figure 8 - Nodes compared by number of items coded

Momentarily disregarding the main container (i.e. “Company viability”), that is no more than the result of a structure/classification given to the various codes, the following codes (or nodes, concepts) appear in the diagram:

1. Competitive Advantage
 - 1.1. Costs and Outsourcing
 - 1.2. Differentiation and Opportunity
 - 1.3. Differentiation and Standard service
2. Decisional Model
3. Projects and Strategies
 - 3.1. Change, Outsourcing and Employees
 - 3.2. Concealed Purposes
 - 3.3. Contracts
 - 3.4. ICT Outsourcing

All above concepts can be found “as they are” in the 1st chapter:

- competitive advantage as the backbone of viability, the objective to consider while making strategic decisions. To that point we linked our perplexities related to outsource for differentiation and/or cost
- decisional model as the key point in our decisional process. This is the point where we chose what strategies and how they have to be supported (although in our case – a project - “the how” seems to be the most relevant topic)
- Projects and Strategies: projects as “the how” related to our strategies as “the what” (Morris and Pinto, 2007)

The next picture shows the hierarchy or structure/classification we have hypothesized to group and relate the above concepts:

Figure 9 - Hierarchy of concepts

As summary:

- the same concepts can be found in the 1st chapter of the current dissertation that is the result of our qualitative analysis
- the same concepts have been used for the literature review and the creation of the evaluation model/s
- the same reviewed and refined concepts are used in the chapter related to the conclusions of the dissertation

4.3 Questionnaires, meaning of the data and questions, data types and statistical methods

4.3.1 Questionnaires and Models

As it should be clear now, the above qualitative analysis was mainly aimed to refine our understanding of the concept of Outsourcing. Then, to the topic of Outsourcing and thanks also to the literature, we further associated the characteristics belonging to the macro areas which make up “ICT SW Projects with BPR”: Uncertainty, Agile PM, Knowledge Areas, Change management, Quantitative Decisional Model and Success factors were progressively integrated in order to create an as complete as possible scenario for the subject of the research. From these bases, we developed the questionnaires (copy of the questionnaires is available in the Appendix of the Dissertation). Where possible, sections in the questionnaires reflected the membership of the question to the above mentioned areas of knowledge.

Two versions of the questionnaires were developed. Since the first one was considered as being too long, we looked for similar questions linked to different areas: we looked for multiple instances of the same (or very similar) characteristics connected to more than one area. These questions were then grouped to form a “shared” group. Obviously it was possible because in some cases characteristics belonging to different “macro areas” (as above referenced) were identical. For instance “fostering communications and trust” were characteristics belonging to both Outsourcing and Agile PM.

From this activity two questionnaires arose:

- The first questionnaire was made up of 30 questions; subjects of the questions were the characteristics of the already referenced macro areas (i.e. Outsourcing, Agile PM, Uncertainty, Quantitative Decisional Model, Success factors). These were the characteristics we chose as key for the decision making process (as known, we would like to fulfill this evaluation by comparing them with the level of the project success). Addressees of this questionnaire were people with proper information to answer: project managers, CIOs,
- The second questionnaire was made up of 10 questions and it considered the same questions related to change management as the first one. In this case, addressees were employees who “suffered” the outsourcing practice.

As outcome of this activity, questions belonging to the extended questionnaire result classified in various sections that should respect the “areas of knowledge/macro areas” already mentioned:

- General purpose
- Outsourcing (why, what and how)
- Agile Project Management
- Outsourcing and Uncertainty (Agile PM)
- Knowledge areas (not considered in above sections)
- Initial decisional drivers
- Success

Reiterating that the 2nd chapter (related to literature review) is made up of the following sections:

- ICT SW Solutions
- Outsourcing
- ICT and Uncertainty
- Project Management Knowledge areas
- Project success

we can observe how groups in the questionnaire roughly correspond to the structure of the 2nd Chapter (i.e. review of the literature).

More in detail we grouped questions as follows:

General:	Q1 to Q3
Related to Outsourcing:	Q4 to Q12
Related to Agile PM:	Q13 to Q18
Related to PM Knowledge Areas:	Q15 and Q18
	Q21 to Q23
	Q26 to Q30
Common to both Agile PM and Outsourcing:	Q19 to Q21
Related to Change model:	Q_9 to Q_14
	Q_17
	Q_19 to Q_21
Related to Quantitative model:	Q24 and Q25
Related to Success and probe:	Q27 to Q30

Questions Q_9, Q_10, Q_11, Q_12, Q_13, Q_14, Q_17, Q_19, Q_20, Q_21 are the ones we considered as related to change management. Question 24 and question 25 are a hypothesis of the quantitative cost-benefit-ROI analysis; they were inferred from Stewart and Hrenewich (2009), Cresswell (2004, p.23), Nicol and Coen (2003, p.50), Baker, Energy and Roos (2000) and AGIMO (2012, pp.35-38).

Questions from Q_4 to Q_25 correspond to the “mixed model”. Correspondences between questions belonging to the extended and reduced questionnaires can be found in the Appendix.

Q_30 is considered as a probe question in terms of “the higher the number of run projects in the short term to adjust the scope of the project of reference, the higher the level of failure of the project of reference”.

Questions and their descriptions are shown in the table below:

Acronym	Question	Description
G_PJN	Q_1	Project name to map suppliers and customer staff answers
G_IND	Q_2	Industrial classification of the customer
G_CIO	Q_3	Report chain of the CIO
O_RES	Q_4	Resistance to change from customer staff
O_CAC	Q_5	Reason related to competitive advantage that pushed the choice
O_BND	Q_6	Clear definition of the scope/boundaries to/of outsource
O_LKN	Q_7	Lock-in considered and managed
O_HDC	Q_8	Hidden costs considered and managed
O_TYP	Q_9	Typology of outsourcing
O_IHV	Q_10	Implicit handover considered and managed
O_STR	Q_11	Transformation of internal staff considered and managed
O_SCP	Q_12	Clarification of the scope considered and managed
A_AUT	Q_13	Autonomy to agile team considered and managed
A_CLT	Q_14	Co-location of agile considered and managed
A_CTR	Q_15	Contingency reserve to deal with flexible schedule, budget and risk considered and managed
A_AHD	Q_16	Ad-hoc documentation for agile team considered and managed
A_TST	Q_17	Trust for agile team considered and managed
A_TMP	Q_18	Existence of a talent management process
C_MTV	Q_19	Motivation of agile team considered and managed
C_PRC	Q_20	Review of internal processes to foster agile team considered and managed
C_CMM	Q_21	Agile communications to foster agile team considered and managed
C_LTC	Q_22	Long term collaboration between the customer and the supplier considered and managed
C_QTY	Q_23	Qualitative metrics to cope with uncertainty considered and managed
C_OTH	Q_24	Other factors of cost
C_TXT	Q_25	Other factors of cost free text
C_CTR	Q_26	Typology of the contract
S_BDG	Q_27	Degree of success in terms of budget
S_DRT	Q_28	Degree of success in terms of duration
S_SC1	Q_29	Degree of success in terms of scope technical check
S_SC2	Q_30	Degree of success in terms of scope functional check

Whereas detailed grouping per area of knowledge is shown in the table below:

Groups	Vectors	KnAreas	Questions	Attribute
<u>General & Check</u>	N/A		Q_1	G_PJN
			Q_2	G_IND
			Q_3	G_CIO
<u>Outsourcing</u>	Input		Q_4	O_RES
			Q_5	O_CAC
			Q_6	O_BND
			Q_7	O_LKN
			Q_8	O_HDC
			Q_10	O_IHV
			Q_9	O_TYP
			Q_11	O_STR
			Q_12	O_SCP
			Q_13	A_AUT
<u>Agile</u>	Input		Q_14	A_CLT
		1,8	Q_15	A_CTR
			Q_16	A_AHD
			Q_17	A_TST
		6	Q_18	A_TMP
			Q_19	C_MTV
<u>Outsourcing & Agile</u>	Input		Q_20	C_PRC
		7	Q_21	C_CMM
<u>Other KA</u>	Input		Q_26	C_CTR
		9	Q_22	C_LTC
		5	Q_23	C_QTY
<u>KA Group</u>	N/A		Q_26	C_CTR
			Q_22	C_LTC
		5	Q_23	C_QTY
		1,8	Q_15	A_CTR
		6	Q_18	A_TMP
		7	Q_21	C_CMM
		4	Q_27	S_BDG
		3	Q_28	S_DRT
		2	Q_29	S_SC1
		2	Q_30	S_SC2
<u>Success</u>	Output		Q_27	S_BDG
			Q_28	S_DRT
			Q_29	S_SC1
			Q_30	S_SC2

4.4 Reasons for the approach to the statistical analysis

4.4.1 How to interpret the questions

In referencing qualitative (i.e. constructionist) and quantitative (i.e. positivist) cost-benefit analysis (and efficacy and efficiency of related supportive models as main scope of this research), we involuntarily wrote accordingly to Kaye, Rogers and Boymal (2008, p.8) where they observe that: *“A qualitative cost benefit analysis differs from quantitative cost benefit analysis in drawing on a range of evidence of costs and benefits, not all converted to monetary value, and therefore not producing a final ratio of costs to benefits. Instead relationships between costs and benefits are considered.”*

In that sense we here underline how:

- Via the questionnaires we have submitted to “interviewees” both a set of qualitative questions and a set of quantitative questions in agreement with the above statement
- all the questions refer to a generic term “resources”. It means that just the fact of writing *“we have to consider this specific qualitative/quantitative factor/attribute and acted in agreement”* means we have allocated resources because we have thought and made a deliberate decision about it. It is not always relevant what consequent actions are but the “deliberate” action is
- we wanted to evaluate the “quality/strength” of above referenced thoughts thanks to maturity levels. We did it via Likert scales that we considered as strongly coupled to maturity levels that, in turn, could be seen as a consequence of learning cycles (Baan, 2013, p.20). In that sense all questions were written in a way through which we tried to get an understanding of the “maturity levels/learning cycles” in use in a given company and related to the evaluation process for resources (i.e. qualitative and quantitative characteristics of areas of knowledge in our context); “maturity levels/learning cycles” were then aimed to measure and, over time and via processes (see at Vlahovic, Milanovic and Skrinjar, 2010), refine measures related to a given factor/attribute (either quantitative or qualitative). In that sense we have stressed the idea of processes to determine resources as means to evaluate “the quality of the thoughts”
- specificity of the description of each factor/attribute was finally introduced in order to guarantee the degree of awareness of the “role of a resource” against strategies (i.e. how a given resource supports strategies; this corresponds to the strategic cost accounting of Perkins, 2005)

All of it was aimed to evaluate the awareness level (above also referred as “deliberate action”), learning attitude and their effectiveness via the results of the projects.

The elements above are crucial for a proper understanding of the questionnaires.

4.4.2 Statistical methods

Likert scales were used also (in addition to the purpose of evaluation of the learning cycles and maturity levels) in order to ease the filling of the web-based questionnaires. The main drawback of this approach was that the resultant variables were ordinal or nominal and this fact constrained the choice of applicable statistical methods. The table below summarizes and explains the meaning of the mentioned variables (Miller and Salkind, 2002, pp.383-385):

Level	Qualities	Examples	Defining Characteristic
Nominal	Assignment of labels to categories	Preference (like or dislike) Voting record (for or against)	Each observation belongs in its own category
Ordinal	Assignment of relative values along some continuum	Rank in college Social class relative to others	One observation is ranked above or below another
Interval	Equal distances between points	Intelligence test scores Temperature	One score differs from another on some measure that has equal-appearing intervals
Ratio	Absolute zero point	Age Weight Time	Ratios of scale values are meaningful, so that one value can be said to be twice as large as another or have some other ratio, and it is possible for none of the quantity measured to exist

In addition to that, data collected did not follow a normal distribution and normality is a prerequisite for parametric statistics (based on Markham, n.d. both skew and Kurtosis should be ~ 1.0 to consider a variable as normally distributed; distributions of variables in scope are highlighted in the Appendix).

Note: we accepted these constraints despite some authors argue against this “preconception” (Knapp, 1990 and Norman 2010) and as Norman (2010) openly states: “*If Jamieson and others are right and we cannot use parametric methods on Likert scale data, and we have to prove that our data are exactly normally distributed, then we can effectively trash about 75% of our research on educational, health status and quality of life assessment...*”

Nevertheless, the above assumptions forced us to consider non-parametric statistics as the most suitable ones to analyze the data collected. In particular we used:

- Chi-square to evaluate dependencies between nominal and ordinal variables (American Education, n.d., Statistical Solutions, 2010 and Mehta and Patel, 2010)
- Gamma (American Education, n.d. and Mehta and Patel, 2010) to evaluate relationships between ordinal variables
- MonteCarlo simulation to try to deal with the limited size sample issue (Mehta and Patel, 2010)

Note: As it should be already clear now, data were retrieved via web-based questionnaires; limits related to the size of the sample do not allow a multivariate analysis; we used SPSS for the statistical analysis.

4.4.3 Interpretation of statistical methods

The next step in our path toward the statistical analysis is the explanation of the “rules” that in the next sections we use to interpret the results of the statistical measures. These rules (i.e. guidelines for evaluations) are below summarized and classified per statistical method:

- 1) Chi-Square (American Education, n.d., Statistical Solutions, 2010 and Mehta and Patel, 2010): it is a technique that evaluates the existence of a relationship between two ordinal variables, two nominal variables, or between an ordinal and a nominal variable (all of them interpreted as categorical). With Chi-square we test the independence of the two variables. A null and an alternate hypothesis are formulated. The null hypothesis states that variables are independent; the alternate hypothesis sustains that variables are not independent.

Measures and interpretation:

- i) The p-value (“Asymp.Sig.” in SPSS reports) is the significant measure: if it is less than .05 then the null hypothesis is rejected.

The chi-square poses problems of validity with small samples and situations where “cell size is below five occurrences” (Statistical Solutions, 2010 p.22 and Mehta and Patel, 2010, p.16).

- 2) Gamma (Western University, n.d, The University of Texas at Austin, n.d. and Harding University, n.d.): it evaluates the existence, strength and direction of a relationship between two ordinal variables. Also in that case the null and alternate hypothesis approach is followed.

Measures and interpretation:

- i) The result of the measure can vary between -1.0 and +1.0. “Zero” means absence of association. The evaluation of the relationship strength is based on the following table (The University of Texas at Austin, n.d.):
 - a. ± 0.0 to ± 0.2 = very weak
 - b. ± 0.2 to ± 0.4 = weak
 - c. ± 0.4 to ± 0.6 = moderate
 - d. ± 0.6 to ± 0.8 = strong
 - e. ± 0.8 to ± 1.0 = very strong
 - f. ± 1.0 = perfect relationship
- ii) The sign of the result indicates the direction of the relationship
- iii) Considerations related to *p-value* are the same already discussed for chi-square: if the p-value (“Approx. Sig.” in SPSS; Harding University) is less than .05 then the null hypothesis is rejected.

From Mehta and Patel (2010, pp.187-188) we understand that Gamma poses the same problems as chi-square where cell size is below five occurrences.

- 3) In order to try to cope with the sample size and related issue of cells size below 5 we have applied the MonteCarlo simulation (Garth, 2008, pp.49-50 for a more thorough justification and Mehta and Patel, 2010 for similarities between Exact and MonteCarlo simulation) to both Chi-square and Gamma.

4.5 Quantitative analysis

This section is devoted to the statistical analysis of the data collected. Here we would like to try, at first, to analyze the “success level” of the projects whose the data have been collected and then we would like also to try also to verify if qualitative and quantitative “decisional variables” (i.e. independent variables) could be considered as predictive with respect to the result of the projects themselves (i.e. dependent variables).

Results are constrained by the fact that we collected just 25 answers to the main questionnaire.

4.5.1 Analysis of the success level

In this section we are going to analyze via frequency tables “how successful” the projects belonging to the sample were. As written in section 4.3.1, questions belonging to the “level of success” are the questions from number 27 to number 30:

- S_BDG - Q_27: Degree of success in terms of budget
- S_DRT - Q_28: Degree of success in terms of duration
- S_SC1 - Q_29: Degree of success in terms of scope technical check
- S_SC2 - Q_30: Degree of success in terms of scope functional check

Their related frequency tables are:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0%	7	28.0	28.0	28.0
from 1% to 10%	8	32.0	32.0	60.0
from 11% to 25%	8	32.0	32.0	92.0
Valid 26% to 50%	1	4.0	4.0	96.0
more than 50%	1	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0%	7	28.0	28.0	28.0
from 1% to 10%	5	20.0	20.0	48.0
from 11% to 25%	5	20.0	20.0	68.0
Valid 26% to 50%	5	20.0	20.0	88.0
more than 50%	3	12.0	12.0	100.0
Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S_SC1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0%	5	20.0	20.0	20.0
from 1% to 10%	17	68.0	68.0	88.0
from 11% to 25%	1	4.0	4.0	92.0
Valid 26% to 50%	1	4.0	4.0	96.0
more than 50%	1	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	25	100.0	100.0	

End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S_SC2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No, end users didn't claim for changes	3	12.0	12.0	12.0
We ran some analyses due to some defects	7	28.0	28.0	40.0
Yes, one maintenance project was run	3	12.0	12.0	52.0
Valid				
Yes, more than one maintenance project was run	7	28.0	28.0	80.0
Yes, we had to thoroughly review the project deliverables	5	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	25	100.0	100.0	

As we can see, just the following percentages can be considered as successful in terms of:

- 28% in terms of budget
- 28% in terms of duration
- 20% in terms of scope
- 12% in terms of quality

Here we need to reiterate how we have assumed (as per Mahalakshmi and Sundararajan, 2013) that, in Agile projects, the scope is given whereas (being in an Agile scenario) time and cost could vary (Section 2.1.4) so that if we can in some way accept deviances from budget and duration, it is slightly more difficult to justify a deviance related to the scope.

Moreover we stated that we consider question number 30 as a probe question so that parallel projects run during the execution period of the reference project or during the first year after its delivery and aimed to fix mistakes, to add new requirements or to adapt to unpredicted changes, could be considered as “additional indexes of failure” being they, reasonably, “changes” of the project of reference that were managed as new projects. If it is acceptable, merging the results of the projects success in terms of scope with the result of the project success in terms of quality (question number 30), we can achieve a different idea of the success level from the resultant frequency table.

In effect, under this perspective, the percentage of success drops dramatically to 4% (i.e. S_SC1 + S_SC2):

S_SC1 + S_SC2 - S_SC1_PLUS_SC2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
2	1	4.0	4.0	4.0
3	3	12.0	12.0	16.0
4	7	28.0	28.0	44.0
5	2	8.0	8.0	52.0
Valid 6	6	24.0	24.0	76.0
7	5	20.0	20.0	96.0
10	1	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	25	100.0	100.0	

The table above deserves some comments:

in each instance of the sample we have added the values of success level in terms of scope to the success level in terms of quality (i.e. end users requests for changes).

From there, possible results can range from 2 to 10. For instance:

- where the scope deviance was 0 (so that the answer was worth 1) and there were no end user requests for changes (so that the answer was worth 1) the value of that resulting cell was set to 2 (i.e. 1+1; neither scope nor quality creeps)
- on the other extremity, where the scope deviance was higher than 50% (so that the answer was worth 5) and project deliverables were thoroughly reviewed (so that the answer was worth 5) the value of that resulting cell was set to 10 (i.e. 5+5; serious scope and quality creeps)
- in the middle between the two extremities there are all possible combinations

If it is acceptable then the success rate is quite poor.

4.5.2 Data Analysis

Such success rate is one of the reasons that give meaning to this research since, at the end, we would like to verify if the factors considered during the decisional process aimed to approve or reject a project with characteristics aligned to the ones within scope of our research, are the proper ones in order to forecast the project execution results or not. As previously said failing the project execution is per itself a failure in terms of strategic support for two reasons at least:

- the usage of unpredicted resources impact other activities/projects (in competition for the same resources)
- a wrong estimate of the resources could cause relevant changes in the actual value of the project and, as consequence, a wrong management of the project portfolio

Both reasons above cause lack of effectiveness and efficiency and impact on strategies.

Believing in a “business driven by quantities” and convinced of finding creeps in such quantitatively inspired decision making process, we further evaluate here both quantitative factors used during this phase and qualitative factors inferred from the already mentioned macro areas (i.e. Uncertainty, Agile Project Management, Outsourcing and Change management, ...). The evaluation is done by relating these factors to the success factors previously analyzed.

The results of the activity of evaluation are shown in the next sections.

4.5.3 Quantitative model (the cause) vs Success rate (the effect)

In section 4.3.1 we referenced the literature used to propose a quantitative model. The purpose of the resulting quantitative model, made up of 5 elements (i.e. infrastructure, software licenses, internal staff, training, outsourcing service provider), was to stimulate the data supplier to weight the contained element (shown in Q_24) and to continue the model by filling in Question 25 that was set as a free text area.

Unfortunately, despite the fact that most respondents filled in the proposed model in Q_24, via Q_25 we collected very limited indications of additional elements belonging to the quantitative model and used during the decision making process. For that reason we can now try to find a statistical relationship just between the quantitative model we proposed as precompiled (i.e. Q_24) and the success factors.

Question we are going to analyze via statistical means are:

1. C_TXT Q_24 Other factors of cost

related to

1. S_BDG Q_27 Degree of success in terms of budget
2. S_DRT Q_28 Degree of success in terms of duration
3. S_SC1 Q_29 Degree of success in terms of scope technical check
4. S_SC2 Q_30 Degree of success in terms of scope functional check

Being Q_25 made up of 5 different categories (i.e. hardware, software, internal staff, training, outsourcer), we apply a bivariate analysis using both Pearson chi-square and Gamma with MonteCarlo simulation to 20 different combinations of independent variables vs dependent variables.

The full result of this analysis has been attached in the Appendix whereas below we evidence the relevant outcomes:

Cost of the SW - C OTH SW* Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1

Symmetric Measures – C_OTH_SW ⇨ S_SC1

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.652	.242	2.037	.042	.073 ^c	.066	.080

Cost of internal staff (FTE) - C OTH STAFF* End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S SC2

Symmetric Measures – C_OTH_STAFF ⇨ S_SC2

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.400	.178	2.190	.029	.084 ^c	.077	.091

Cost of the Service Provider - C_OTH_OSP * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S_BDG

Symmetric Measures – C_OTH_OSP ⇨ S_BDG

	Value	Asymp. Error ^a	Std. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.493	.246	1.927	.054	.044 ^c	.039	.049

Cost of the HW - C_OTH_HW * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S_SC2

Symmetric Measures – C_OTH_HW ⇨ S_SC2

	Value	Asymp. Error ^a	Std. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.564	.197	2.620	.009	.023 ^c	.019	.027

Based on mentioned guidelines for interpretation and interpretation matrix that is (Section 4.4.3):

- a. ±0.0 to ±0.2 = very weak
- b. ±0.2 to ±0.4 = weak
- c. ±0.4 to ±0.6 = moderate
- d. ±0.6 to ±0.8 = strong
- e. ±0.8 to ±1.0 = very strong
- f. ±1.0 = perfect relationship

we can state that there is:

- a Strong direct relationship between “Cost of the SW - C_OTH_SW * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S_SC1”

- a Moderate direct relationship between “Cost of internal staff (FTE) - C_OTH_STAFF * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S_SC2”
- a Moderate direct relationship between “Cost of the Service Provider - C_OTH_OSP * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S_BDG”
- a Moderate direct relationship between “Cost of the HW - C_OTH_HW * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S_SC2”

We need to add three observations here:

1. despite the description of causal variables makes reference to “Costs”, the questions were made in terms of “processes/efforts” so, in some way, they were referred to the level of accuracy we use while determining the costs, reasonably because we expect them to have an impact on the subject of our decision making process (we made implicit reference to a maturity model via Likert scales; maturity model that in turn can be seen as stage of a learning cycle)
2. in this case if for causal variables the higher the value the higher the level of maturity, for the dependent ones the higher the values the higher the level of failure (i.e. success level factors could be worth starting from 1 – success- up to 5 – more than 50% of “failure”-)
3. based on point 2 above, in the current case the “stronger” the process to determine resources corresponding to the quantitative factors, the higher the level of failure since the relation is direct

4.5.4 Qualitative model (the cause) vs Success rate (the effect): the Outsourcing paradigm subset

The second chunk of independent variables whose the effect we would like to compare with the success, is the one of the variables related to the Outsourcing paradigm/area of knowledge. These variables are:

- | | | |
|-----------|------|--|
| 1. O_RES | Q_4 | Resistance to change from customer staff |
| 2. O_CAC | Q_5 | Reason related to competitive advantage that pushed the choice |
| 3. O_BND | Q_6 | Clear definition of the scope/boundaries to/of outsource |
| 4. O_LKN | Q_7 | Lock-in considered and managed |
| 5. O_HDC | Q_8 | Hidden costs considered and managed |
| 6. O_TYP | Q_9 | Typology of outsourcing |
| 7. O_IHV | Q_10 | Implicit handover considered and managed |
| 8. O_STR | Q_11 | Transformation of internal staff considered and managed |
| 9. O_SCP | Q_12 | Clarification of the scope considered and managed |
| 10. C_MTV | Q_19 | Motivation of agile team considered and managed |
| 11. C_PRC | Q_20 | Review of internal processes to foster agile team considered and managed |
| 12. C_CMM | Q_21 | Agile communications to foster agile team considered and managed |

they are always compared to success variables:

- | | | |
|----------|------|--|
| 1. S_BDG | Q_27 | Degree of success in terms of budget |
| 2. S_DRT | Q_28 | Degree of success in terms of duration |
| 3. S_SC1 | Q_29 | Degree of success in terms of scope technical check |
| 4. S_SC2 | Q_30 | Degree of success in terms of scope functional check |

Also in this case we apply a bivariate analysis using both Pearson chi-square and Gamma with MonteCarlo simulation to 48 different combinations of independent variables vs dependent variables.

Relevant findings are shown below:

*Allocation of resources to transform internal staff - O STR * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1*

Chi-Square Tests – O_STR ⇔ S_SC1

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
				Pearson Chi-Square	20.971 ^a	12	.051	.012 ^b	.009

*Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT*

Chi-Square Tests – C_PRC ⇔ S_DRT

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
				Pearson Chi-Square	25.941 ^a	16	.055	.029 ^b	.024

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C_CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT

Chi-Square Tests – C_CMM ↔ S_DRT

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)	
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	Sig.	99% Confidence Interval
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	27.103 ^a	16	.040	.032 ^b	.028	.037	

Based on our guidelines for interpretation (Section 4.4.3), we can state that variables as per the following combinations:

- Allocation of resources to transform internal staff - O_STR * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S_SC1
- Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C_PRC * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT
- Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C_CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT

are NOT independent.

4.5.5 Qualitative model (the cause) vs Success rate (the effect): the Agile Project Management subset

The third chunk of independent variables to compare with the success variables is the one of the variables related to the Agile paradigm. These variables are:

- 1. A_AUT Q_13 Autonomy to agile team considered and managed
- 2. A_CLT Q_14 Co-location of agile considered and managed
- 3. A_CTR Q_15 Contingency reserve to deal with flexible schedule, budget and risk considered and managed
- 4. A_AHD Q_16 Ad-hoc documentation for agile team considered and managed
- 5. A_TST Q_17 Trust for agile team considered and managed
- 6. A_TMP Q_18 Existence of a talent management process
- 7. C_MTV Q_19 Motivation of agile team considered and managed
- 8. C_PRC Q_20 Review of internal processes to foster agile team considered and managed
- 9. C_CMM Q_21 Agile communications to foster agile team considered and managed

and they are compared always with success variables:

- 1. S_BDG Q_27 Degree of success in terms of budget
- 2. S_DRT Q_28 Degree of success in terms of duration
- 3. S_SC1 Q_29 Degree of success in terms of scope technical check
- 4. S_SC2 Q_30 Degree of success in terms of scope functional check

Again we apply a bivariate analysis using both Pearson chi-square and Gamma with MonteCarlo simulation to 36 different combinations of independent variables vs dependent variables.

Relevant findings are shown below:

Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT *
Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Symmetric Measures – A_AUT ⇔ S_BDG

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.503	.210	-2.220	.026	.025 ^c	.021	.029

Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT *
Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Symmetric Measures – A_AUT ⇔ S_DRT

	Value	Asymp. Error ^a	Std. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.427	.200	-2.056	.040	.040 ^c	.035	.045

Allocation of resources for ad-hoc documentation - A AHD *
Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests – A_AHD ⇔ S_BDG

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)		
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
								Lower Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	22.421 ^a	12	.033	.017 ^b	.014	.020		

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests – C_CMM ⇔ S_DRT

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)	
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	Sig.	99% Confidence Interval
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	27.103 ^a	16	.040	.029 ^b	.024	.033	

Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests – C_PRC ⇔ S_DRT

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)	
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	Sig.	99% Confidence Interval
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	25.941 ^a	16	.055	.032 ^b	.027	.037	

Thanks to the interpretation guidelines (Section 4.4.3) and above evidences, in this case we can state that there is:

- A moderate inverse relationship between “Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A_AUT * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S_BDG”
- A moderate inverse relationship between “Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A_AUT * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT”

Moreover variables as per the following combinations:

- Allocation of resources for ad-hoc documentation - A_AHD * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S_BDG
- Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C_CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT
- Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C_PRC * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT

are NOT independent.

4.5.6 Qualitative model (the cause) vs Success rate (the effect): the PM Knowledge Areas subset

The fourth group of independent variables to compare with the success variables is the one of the variables related to the PM Knowledge Areas. These variables are:

- | | | |
|----------|------|--|
| 1. A_CTR | Q_15 | Contingency reserve to deal with flexible schedule, budget and risk considered and managed |
| 2. A_TMP | Q_18 | Existence of a talent management process |
| 3. C_CMM | Q_21 | Agile communications to foster agile team considered and managed |
| 4. C_LTC | Q_22 | Long term collaboration between the customer and the supplier considered and managed |
| 5. C_QTY | Q_23 | Qualitative metrics to cope with uncertainty considered and managed |
| 6. C_CTR | Q_26 | Typology of the contract |

and, as usual, they are compared always with success variables:

- | | | |
|----------|------|--|
| 1. S_BDG | Q_27 | Degree of success in terms of budget |
| 2. S_DRT | Q_28 | Degree of success in terms of duration |
| 3. S_SC1 | Q_29 | Degree of success in terms of scope technical check |
| 4. S_SC2 | Q_30 | Degree of success in terms of scope functional check |

For the fourth time we apply a bivariate analysis using both Pearson chi-square and Gamma with MonteCarlo simulation to 24 different combinations of independent variables vs dependent variables.

Relevant findings are shown below:

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests – C_CMM ⇔ S_DRT

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	27.103 ^a	16	.040	.029 ^b	.024	.033			

Use of qualitative metrics to evaluate the service levels - C QTY * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests – C_QTY ⇔ S_BDG

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	28.780 ^a	16	.025	.079 ^b	.072	.086			

Typology of the contract - C_CTR * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S_SC1

Chi-Square Tests – C_CTR ⇔ S_SC1

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)	
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	Sig.	99% Confidence Interval
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.826 ^a	8	.045	.054 ^b	.048	.060	

Typology of the contract - C_CTR * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S_BDG

Chi-Square Tests – C_CTR ⇔ S_BDG

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)	
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	Sig.	99% Confidence Interval
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.272 ^a	8	.054	.050 ^b	.045	.056	

With reference to our guidelines for interpretation (Section 4.4.3) and above evidences, we can state that variables as per the following combinations:

- Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C_CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT
- Use of qualitative metrics to evaluate the service levels - C_QTY * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S_BDG
- Typology of the contract - C_CTR * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S_SC1
- Typology of the contract - C_CTR * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S_BDG

are NOT independent.

4.5.7 Qualitative model (the cause) vs Success rate (the effect): the Change management subset

The last group of independent variables we compared with the success variables is the one of the variables related to the Change Management area. These variables are:

- | | | |
|-----------|------|--|
| 1. O_IHV | Q_10 | Implicit handover considered and managed |
| 2. O_STR | Q_11 | Transformation of internal staff considered and managed |
| 3. O_SCP | Q_12 | Clarification of the scope considered and managed |
| 4. A_AUT | Q_13 | Autonomy to agile team considered and managed |
| 5. A_CLT | Q_14 | Co-location of agile considered and managed |
| 6. A_TST | Q_17 | Trust for agile team considered and managed |
| 7. C_MTV | Q_19 | Motivation of agile team considered and managed |
| 8. C_PRC | Q_20 | Review of internal processes to foster agile team considered and managed |
| 9. C_CMM | Q_21 | Agile communications to foster agile team considered and managed |
| 10. O_TYP | Q_9 | Typology of outsourcing |

and they are always compared with success variables:

- | | | |
|----------|------|--|
| 1. S_BDG | Q_27 | Degree of success in terms of budget |
| 2. S_DRT | Q_28 | Degree of success in terms of duration |
| 3. S_SC1 | Q_29 | Degree of success in terms of scope technical check |
| 4. S_SC2 | Q_30 | Degree of success in terms of scope functional check |

For the last time we apply a bivariate analysis using both Pearson chi-square and Gamma with MonteCarlo simulation to 40 different combinations of independent variables vs dependent variables.

Relevant findings are shown below:

Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT*
Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Symmetric Measures - A_AUT ⇔ S_BDG

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.503	.210	-2.220	.026	.022 ^c	.018	.026

Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT*
Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Symmetric Measures – A_AUT ⇔ S_DRT

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.427	.200	-2.056	.040	.038 ^c	.033	.043

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests C_CMM ⇔ S_DRT

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
				Pearson Chi-Square	27.103 ^a	16	.040	.031 ^b	.027

Allocation of resources to transform internal staff - O STR * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1

Chi-Square Tests – O_STR ⇔ S_SC1

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
				Pearson Chi-Square	20.971 ^a	12	.051	.011 ^b	.008

Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C_PRC *
Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT

Chi-Square Tests – C_PRC ⇔ S_DRT

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2- sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1- sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
				Pearson Chi-Square	25.941 ^a	16	.055	.033 ^b	.028

For the last time and always thanks to the guidelines for interpretation (Section 4.4.3) and above evidences, we can state that there is:

- A moderate inverse relationship between “Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A_AUT * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S_BDG”
- A moderate inverse relationship between “Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A_AUT * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT”

Moreover variables as per the following combinations:

- Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C_CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT
- Allocation of resources to transform internal staff - O_STR * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S_SC1
- Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C_PRC * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT

are NOT independent.

4.6 Summary

To conclude this chapter we would like to present here a table where the main findings and their statistical characteristics are summarized. The table below suits this purpose:

Model Group	First Variable	Direction of the dependency (IV => DV)	Second Variable	Type of analysis	Direction of the relationship	Strenght
AG Count	A_AHD	N/A	S_BDG	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent 1
OS	C_CMM	N/A	S_DRT	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent
AG	C_CMM	N/A	S_DRT	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent
KA	C_CMM	N/A	S_DRT	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent
CH Count	C_CMM	N/A	S_DRT	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent 4
KA Count	C_CTR	N/A	S_BDG	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent 1
KA Count	C_CTR	N/A	S_SC1	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent 1
OS	C_PRC	N/A	S_DRT	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent
AG	C_PRC	N/A	S_DRT	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent
CH Count	C_PRC	N/A	S_DRT	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent 3
KA Count	C_QTY	N/A	S_BDG	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent 1
OS	O_STR	N/A	S_SC1	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent
CH Count	O_STR	N/A	S_SC1	Chi-Square	N/A	NOT Independent 2
AG	A_AUT	→	S_BDG	Gamma	Inverse	Moderate
CH Count	A_AUT	→	S_BDG	Gamma	Inverse	Moderate 2
AG	A_AUT	→	S_DRT	Gamma	Inverse	Moderate
CH Count	A_AUT	→	S_DRT	Gamma	Inverse	Moderate 2
QT	C_OTH_HW	→	S_SC2	Gamma	Direct	Moderate 1
QT Count	C_OTH_OSP	→	S_BDG	Gamma	Direct	Moderate 1
QT Count	C_OTH_STAFF	→	S_SC2	Gamma	Direct	Moderate 1
QT Count	C_OTH_SW	→	S_SC1	Gamma	Direct	Strong 1

We need to underline how we can find the same variable in different groups so that the same “outcomes” could have been evidenced more than once during the analysis in the above sections. The meaning of this multiple association is justified by the need to reduce the number of the questions in the questionnaires and the fact that the same characteristics apply to more than just one “group of questions/macro area” (i.e. proper communications belong to both the outsourcing and agile paradigms). The “association activity” (of the factors/variables to the quantitative and qualitative groups/areas), despite

debatable, was aimed also to the purpose of providing different perspectives for the analysis.

Chapter 5: Conclusions

5.1 Introduction

We open the conclusions by summarizing the “logical path” (per topic) that we followed during the research. It is the following one:

- Challenges that the environment submits to the organizations
- Viability as scope of a company (as organization) acting in a given environment
- Strategies (often referenced as “the what”) and Tactics (often referenced as “the how”) as plans and actions to maintain the viability
- Competitive advantage as “point of reference” to define strategies and then tactics
- Decision making process as process to evaluate proper changes and so to chose proper tactics
- Quantitative versus qualitative approach of the evaluation phase of the decision making process
- Cost-benefit-ROI analysis as quantitative approach to decisions (in our research we explored mainly the cost paradigm; it means that we did not evaluate the benefits paradigm)
- Maturity levels as “the ability” to properly define the value (often referenced as “cost” - because of the quantitative approach - or “resource” in order to abstract the concept and approach the qualitative view) of the factors considered during the evaluation phase; it is an indicator of the awareness aimed to sustain effectiveness and efficiency of our decisions
- Strategic cost accounting as the metric and measure of the above mentioned maturity levels; it is a way to map resources against strategies and so to maintain the focus on this relationship in order not to lose the direction
- Concepts and characteristics of Outsourcing, Agile PM, ICT, BPR, Change, Communications, HR Management as topics of the research and drivers for the definition of the factors to consider during the evaluation phase of the decisional process; actually they are the inputs of the decision making process related to ICT Software Solution Project in Outsourcing with BPR
- Other topics were considered like: contracts and/or formal documents as facts were to find the mapping between decisions and communication of the decisions (as it should be in a fact based quantitative approach), best-practices as standard and not suitable points of reference for a detailed or qualitative approach, others.

This approach was motivated by the desire of facing a scenario that was as realistic as possible and so complex (despite not yet complete), thus avoiding the reductionist “traps”.

The next sections contain the analysis of the statistics applied to the answers to a web based questionnaire that interviewees provided after having been (in various ways) “informed” of the above perspective.

5.2 Quantitative model analysis: answer to the first question

In this section we should answer the first question of the research: *“Is the positivist and quantitative evaluation phase (i.e. a quantitative cost-benefit-ROI model), in the decision-making process aimed to choose an outsourcing solution for big-size ICT projects, effective?”*

As seen in Chapter 4, by comparing quantitative factors with the “level of success” factors, we got the next outcomes:

- the higher the efforts/maturity to define the costs of the Software, the higher the deviance of the scope (strong direct relationship)
- the higher the efforts/maturity to define the costs of the Staff, the higher the number of requests for change (moderate direct relationship)
- the higher the efforts/maturity to define the costs of the Service Provider, the higher the deviance of the budget (moderate direct relationship)
- the higher the efforts/maturity to define the costs of the Hardware, the higher the number of requests for change (moderate direct relationship)

Despite not being comparable to a Copernican revolution, four quantitative attributes out of five statistically do not support the forecast of the actual results of the project. Just four combinations out of twenty candidates provided positive results; nevertheless we think that the results evidence as, during the cost-benefit-ROI analysis, we tend to give the quantitative model (i.e. factors) more relevance than it is due; it is a kind of “over expectation” toward this model. We see here an indication to point also somewhere else for a proper evaluation.

5.3 Qualitative model analysis: answer to the second question

The second question of the research is: *“Could a constructionist and qualitative evaluation phase, based on consequences of uncertainty, positively impact the forecast of the results?”*

The analysis of the relationships of the factors belonging to the next qualitative areas

- Outsourcing
- Agile PM
- PM Knowledge Areas
- Change model

with the “factors of success”, provided the following results:

- the higher the efforts/maturity to define resources aimed to provide autonomy to the project team, the lower the deviance of the project budget (moderate inverse relationship)
- the higher the efforts/maturity to define resources aimed to provide autonomy to the project team, the lower the deviance of the project duration (moderate inverse relationship)

Reiterating that our scenario assumes a given (and so un-changeable) scope (as per Mahalakshmi and Sundararajan, 2013), we want to notice as the higher the autonomy of the project the more likely the possibility of concluding the project in time and within the budget but the scope is not impacted. Even if the latter is an intriguing view (i.e. scope not impacted), we have to consider as it could be also due to a lack of proper or enough data since there is no statistical significance at all.

In addition, statistics evidenced the following combinations of variables as being not independent:

- the strength/maturity of the process to define resources for ad-hoc documentation and the deviance of the project budget
- the strength/maturity of the process to define resources for proper communications and the deviance of the project duration
- the contract typology and the deviance of the project budget
- the contract typology and the deviance of the deliverables
- the strength/maturity of the activity aimed to review the processes to foster the agile team and the deviance of the project duration
- the strength/maturity of the process to define qualitative metrics to evaluate deliverable and service level of the outsourcer and the deviance of the project budget
- the strength/maturity of the process to cope with the transformation of the internal staff and the deviance of the project deliverables

In that case, we cannot infer any direction or strength related to the above relationships but, in our opinion, considering that they have been found and adding the previous results to them, we think we are allowed to write that the proposed qualitative model deserves additional investigation.

From the above results, the most potentially fruitful areas of investigation seem to be: documentation, communications, contracts, processes, qualitative metrics and transformation of internal staff (isn't the last one directly related to change change?). Reiterating here that the factors/variables that are variously linked to one or more of the above mentioned qualitative areas are the characteristics of the qualitative areas themselves, we have to admit that the lack of clear coupling factors/areas (i.e. between factors belonging to a specific qualitative model and factors related to the project success area) frustrates the chances of clearly supporting the hypotheses that the various models (agile, outsourcing, change or combinations of them) could, in turn, clearly explain or forecast the results of the given project.

Nevertheless (and again), we think that it is acceptable to state that the analysis provides more than a good single reason to continue the investigation. In other words, the results justify further attention toward the qualitative model.

We throw our last two cents to the factors characterizing outsourcing. They seem to be absent from the statistical analysis so that we need to understand it. Our hypotheses are that the result could be due to:

- Limited sample size

- The fact that unlike agile (or in general other) factors their effects could pertain or could be more visible in a different phase of the tactics execution that is after the project closure when the project deliverable explicit their benefits

How can we interpret the last point while dipped into the context/perspective of the benefit paradigm of our cost-benefit-ROI based decision making process? In this case, we think it could make sense to evaluate and control such factors not only during the project lifecycle phase but also after this phase and so during the operational lifecycle of the project deliverables. For instance: the risks of lock-in or loss of intellectual property (characteristics of outsourcing) should be considered, evaluated and controlled during the evaluation phase of the decision making process and the project lifecycle execution; proper resources should be, as consequence, allocated in agreement with the actions of evaluation and control. But the mentioned risks do not stop their effects once the outcomes become operational and the project is closed rather they persist and (perhaps) reinforce after the project closure while deliverables are operational. On the contrary, we do not think the same mindset could be applied to factors affecting (for instance) agility like team autonomy, proper documentation and/or all the others.

5.4 Which better model: answer to the third question

In this section we propose an answer to the last question of the research that is: *“Is there any additional more appropriate alternative to the above mentioned quantitative and/or qualitative model?”*

In our initial intent this answer should have been no more than a synthesis of the previous ones. Anyhow, actual results, although promising, do not allow the expected conclusion and this is the reason why we just “propose” an answer.

Based on the previous discussion, we here hypothesize a direction toward which drive the choice of the factors to consider while deciding for a go/no go action related to the typology of projects in scope for this research. In this sense, the statistical results provide some indications to promote a qualitative approach to the detriment of the quantitative one since, in spite of the limited sample, we found some insightful and statistically significant evidence of:

- the over-expectations that our quantitative business management approach relies on quantitative factors
- the relationships between the qualitative factors and the result of our tactics

This latter point is further supported (even if indirectly and with cautious interpretation) by the Spearman’s Rho that we, by chance, executed among variables belonging to the agile model. The next table shows the matrix of found relationships:

		A AUT	A CLT	A CTR	A AHD	A TST	C MTV	C PRC	C CMM
Spearman's rho	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,401*	,235	,161	,202	-,183	,025	,301
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,047	,259	,443	,332	,382	,904	,144
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
	Correlation Coefficient	,401*	1,000	,663**	,084	,429*	,038	,307	,291
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,047	,000	,688	,033	,858	,136	,158
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
	Correlation Coefficient	,235	,663**	1,000	,008	,460*	,084	,163	,247
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,259	,000	,969	,021	,691	,436	,233
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
	Correlation Coefficient	,161	,084	,008	1,000	,439*	,441*	,475*	,540**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,443	,688	,969	,028	,027	,016	,005
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
	Correlation Coefficient	,202	,429*	,460*	,439*	1,000	,279	,303	,265
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,332	,033	,021	,028	,176	,140	,200
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
	Correlation Coefficient	-,183	,038	,084	,441*	,279	1,000	,636**	,390
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,382	,858	,691	,027	,176	,001	,054
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
	Correlation Coefficient	,025	,307	,163	,475*	,303	,636**	1,000	,661**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,904	,136	,436	,016	,140	,001	,000
N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	
Correlation Coefficient	,301	,291	,247	,540**	,265	,390	,661**	1,000	
Sig. (2-tailed)		,144	,158	,233	,005	,200	,054	,000	
N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Statistically relevant relationships appear in both crossed and hierarchically distributed patterns. Reiterating that the autonomy of the team was the only factor found as relevant while we compared the agile model with the success factors via Gamma, we think that the fact that the other agile qualitative variables result as being related to the team autonomy but not to the success factors (i.e. if “b” is causal with respect to “c” and “a” is causal with respect to “b”, how is it possible that “a” is not causal with respect to “c”?) could depend on:

- sample size
- different trend of the functions representing the relationships
- a combination of the two reasons above

Anyhow, we think that this syllogism constitutes an additional source of reasonable doubts that should nourish the desire for further research in this direction.

The resulting context gives us the shamelessness of arguing that, in general, we should invest additional resources to the foster learning cycles aimed to increase the maturity levels that are proper to evaluate qualitative factors. It doesn't mean that we have to forget quantitative factors but this research highlights limits of their applicability in very complex situations.

5.5 Change Management

Many times we referenced a secondary questionnaire for employees. Our intention was to compare answers from data suppliers (employers/customers or outsourcing service providers) related to change management with the correspondent perception of change management by the employees. The second questionnaire was actually devoted to collect the employees' perception. Questions that we thought as being related to the feeling/interpretation from employees were the ones we classified as belonging to change management and so the ones impacting their attitude toward the project. This choice was deliberate and so debatable. Prerequisite for this analysis was to relate answers from data suppliers related to a given project with answers from employees engaged in the same project. Unlikely, in no case were we ever authorized to collect data by directly submitting the surveys to employees so that this analysis could not be fulfilled. This paragraph is aimed to close this topic.

5.6 Conclusions, Limits and further Opportunities

5.6.1 Conclusions

The fact that the focus of the research is related to the qualitative approach of the decision making process and the advantages of this approach in a complex scenario, could be interpreted as a tautology. If we can sustain the existence of a quantitative and reductionist approach as opposite to a qualitative, holistic and complex one (Verschuren, 2001), considering a complex scenario is equivalent to consider “qualities” as drivers so that, in the context provided along the research, “quantities” are no more than a “sparring partner”. From this point of view the research just stresses and tries to re-validate the association between complexity and quality in spite of a specious association between complexity and quantity.

Nevertheless this figure of speech, once proved outside its own boundaries (as we did by comparing qualities and quantities in a complex situation), is foreboding of some interesting insights that sustain “qualities” and debunk “quantities”. For instance, if we look at the results from a Project Portfolio Office perspective we can hypothesize that, if (in the given context and statistics) we promote a project in spite of another one thanks to a quantitative decisions making process based on a quantitative cost-benefit-ROI analysis, we risk not providing strategic support to the company. We see here two kinds of risks: the risk of running the “project wrong” (Morris and Pinto, 2007) because the assumptions were wrong, as its value in supporting strategies, and the risk of running the wrong project, thus excluding more valuable projects.

In terms of Competitive advantage, having assumed that quality is differentiation and outsourcing is loss of differentiation (Sections 1.2.4 and 1.4, Caves and Williamson, 1985, p.113, Dirisu, Iyiola and Ibidunni, 2013, p.260), we think that if qualitative variables could somewhat explain the results then it means that the projects in scope for the research have impacted on the corporate differentiation. It clashes with our assumption of outsourcing as a practice to adopt only and apply only to unchangeable and static assets (Section 2.1.2 and Sriwongwana 2009) because it would be difficult to sustain differentiation and unchangeable as synonyms. From there the question is: what is our level of awareness while outsourcing ICT SW Solution with BPR constraint (and from there the idea related to the maturity levels in the questionnaires)? The question makes sense, in our opinion, also because we think that it could be reasonable to outsource “differentiation” but we need to properly decide. And when we decide about differentiation we cannot use quantities (as per the above assumptions). So it is something that the quantitative business management approach cannot explain because quantitative does not match differentiation. Interviewees further testified this wavering approach to differentiation and outsourcing by forswearing the intention to outsource only repeatable assets, components, processes....nevertheless, as seen above, results are not explained by quantities.

For our final consideration we want to point at change management and people. As we know, employees own the skills to customize (Prahalad and Hamel, 1990), if we outsource (as the research evidences) our differentiation, quality and so customization then we directly and heavily risk to impact them. But if it is acceptable, what kind of collaboration and motivation could we expect from employees? If we revoke their responsibilities and change their roles, should they indefatigably act as practitioners? Reiterating that, whatever kind of outsourcing we choose, employees are considered as commodities (Section 2.1.2, Prahalad and Hamel, 1990 and Section 1.2.3, Styhre, 1996), here we once again claim for the need to consider reactions from employees who support corporate differentiation and strategies thanks to their skills and corporate knowledge. The research results confirm the above possibilities.

Linking what stated to our hypothesis (Section 1.4) we think that provided (despite limited) evidence reasonably supports the hypothesis itself and fosters doubts that can justify further investigation related to the same or similar topics. In this sense we conclude that the research partially confirms:

- The best-practice approach is inaccurate (Kashyap, 2014) so not sustaining viability and difficult to predict
- The effectiveness and efficiency of quantitative decisional process related to the scenario in scope is doubtful for effectiveness and efficiency

- ICT Outsourcing projects with BRP are often misunderstood and Outsourcing practices are, as consequence, misused so that
- We impact differentiation and employees
- Awareness is limited and impacts on strategies are unpredictable

Finally we want to once again stress the idea of the awareness, that is: it doesn't mean that outsourcing also while differentiating is not a proper approach per se, it rather means that companies must be aware of the consequences of their choices and that these consequences cannot be always explained in quantitative terms because of the surrounding complexity. Learning cycles and maturity levels could support awareness. Losing intellectual property could not be an issue if we are aware and responsible for our choice. But was the decision really deliberate? Or, on the other hand, aren't we losing corporate viability because we do not apply "right choices right"?

The existence of the mentioned effects seems to be supported by the current research while applied to ICT SW Solutions Project in Outsourcing with BPR and an improper decision-making process seems to be accountable for it.

The final result of this "misbehavior" is a wrong feedback to the environment (Chapter 1, Section 5.1) achieved via a doubtful decision-making process, ineffective and/or inefficient tactics (change and projects), improper understanding of "cost/differentiation/competitive advantage", loss of strategic support, poor execution of strategies and finally lack of viability. From a theoretical standpoint, it should impact the others strategies.

In our opinion, this could be a "not uncommon" scenario of a quantitative business management approach to ICT practices that can no longer be classified as belonging to the "supportive activities" stream of the value chain.

5.6.2 *Limits*

Although interviewees showed relevant interest, the research followed a very difficult pattern (shortly listed in Section 5.1) and this fact was the cause of some misunderstandings. The questionnaires themselves were tricky to interpret because of the huge quantity of concepts: the topics per se, factual based research, maturity models, resources rather than costs and so on. Interviewees were happier to speak than to answer the survey. We failed in collecting data directly from formal written sources. We had to support the filling activity of the surveys by creating questions supported by Likert scales because of some arguments related to the costs to sustain for answering. We did not get access to employees. Despite all of the above, we consider the research as a good starting point for further research in the field of outsourcing in general. In terms of experience and net of relationships, we consider the research a success.

5.6.3 *Recommendations*

Hoping to have created a small breach to justify additional investigation in the same or similar directions, we want to underline as the topic (in our opinion) could be extended outside of the ICT boundaries. In the light of the dualisms “quantity/ quality, standard/customized, global/local, complexity/globalization”, the results could nourish and give rise to further social research aimed to investigate topics like: global models versus customized ones, scale economies versus precise actions, flexibility of the labor market versus the need for intellectual property, customization, skills and loyalty and many others.

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Appendix

Questionnaires

Extended version – 34 questions

Scope of the questionnaire is to collect information related to a ICT SW project related to BPR (i.e. business process reengineering) and developed with the support of outsourced resources

Assumptions:

- ⇒ The project which information will be provided is related to a business process reengineering
- ⇒ Depending on the context of the question, for the purpose of this questionnaire, “resources” mean “measurable items” like: budget, time, rewards, number of meetings, number of situations where to improve, empower, modify something.
- ⇒ Staff will answer only to questions that can impact them in terms of attitude.

Project name

Q.1 Name of the project

- ⇒ Type: text
- ⇒ Meaning: ID for employees

General meaning

Q.2 Among below options, chose the one that better describes the industrial classification of the customer.

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: Consumer Discretionary, Consumer Staples, Energy, Financials, Health Care, Industrials, Information Technology, Materials, Telecommunication Services, Utilities (Standard & Poor’s, 2006)

Q.3 To whom does the CIO report to?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: CEO, CFO, Other
- ⇒ Meaning: check question to validate theoretical implications

Q.4 Which one among the next options better describes your role in the customer’s organization?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: exec, senior, middle, junior, technician/analyst, other (Management Study Guide, n.d)
- ⇒ Meaning: check question to verify impact of outsourcing

⇒ Question for staff only

Outsourcing paragraph

Outsourcing is the strategic use of external resources to fulfil activities usually handled by internal staff. It means that outsourcing is often a matter of change and change management is a matter of transition of individuals.

Q.5 In the project you are considering to fill in the current survey, did the customer allocate enough resources to manage the change?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Q.6 In the project you are considering to fill in the current survey, did the customer consider resistance to change?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Why paragraph

Companies, while deciding how to perform their strategies, consider competitive advantage as key driver. Characteristics of competitive advantage are differentiation (qualitative characteristics) and costs (quantitative characteristics).

Q.7 Which one of the following characteristics of competitive advantage was considered during the decisional process?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Multiple choices / Check boxes
- ⇒ Options: differentiation / costs / a combination of them / other
- ⇒ In case of "Other" text box for next interview with closed questions
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 2 / true to false per each choice
- ⇒ Base value: 2 per each choice

Outsourcing is usually applied to repeatable processes, it impacts on employees' morale, it is harbinger of hidden costs and lock-in and it claims for proper processes.

Q.8 Did the customer plan to clearly define outsourcing boundaries around repeatable (sub)processes?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1

Q.9 Did the customer allocate enough resources to properly motivate internal employees?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Q.10 Did the customer allocate enough resources to review internal processes in order to support the outsourcing?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1

Q.11 Did the customer consider the risk of lock-in?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1

Q.12 Did the customer allocate enough resources to manage potential hidden costs?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1

What paragraph

Usually the core a business process the higher the need for customization, level of management and core skills.

Q.13 Did the customer outsource a core process?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1

Q.14 Did the customer perceive a loss in terms of process or process support control?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

How paragraph

Outsourcing can be classified as

1. Full: all the functionalities are outsourced
2. Selective: some functionalities of a service are delivered internally and some other outsourced
3. Transitional: obsolete and un-maintainable solutions require unavailable resources to be updated

4. Transformational: the service provider acts as a tutor that enables the customer to move along a more valuable service and different typologies have different impact on internal staff.

Q.15 Which one of above definition better describe the project under investigation?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 4 / from 0 full to 3 transformational
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Who paragraph

Q.16 Did the customer allocate proper budget for the transformation of internal staff

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Q.17 Did the customer clearly clarified the scope with internal staff

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Agile

Agile project management differs from the traditional one in terms of iterations and adaptation. It is aimed to cope with uncertainty and owns a proper declination which main points are the source of next questions. Agile PM needs ad hoc processes, roles, decisional autonomy, co-located teams, flexible schedule and budget, lean communications and documentation, motivated and skilled staff, high level of trust and a proper project team where also the sponsor and the customer can be easily engaged.

Q.18 Did the customer allocate proper resources to review internal processes and roles at the light of the needed flexibility

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Q.19 Did the customer provide decisional autonomy to the project team by creating suitable communications' channels with sponsor and functional customer?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Q.20 Did the customer allocate enough resources for co-located teams

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Q.21 Did the customer allocate contingency reserve to cope with flexible schedule, budget and risks? (KA - knowledge area - 1 and 8)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1

Q.22 Did the customer empower communications? (KA 7)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Q.23 Was an ad-hoc documentation (related just to un-changeable assets) maintained?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1

Q.24 Did the customer allocate proper resources to motivate internal staff

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Q.25 Did the customer allocate enough resources to empower trust

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1
- ⇒ Question for staff as well

Knowledge areas (previously not considered)

Q.26 Did the customer have a talent management process? (KA 6)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choices
- ⇒ Possible values: from 0 to 1 / true-false / yes/no
- ⇒ Base value: 0 (true)

To different levels of uncertainty correspond different typologies of contracts and need for trust between the customer and the service supplier. Where the level of uncertainty is low a fixed price is suggested but moving against higher uncertainty time and material if not cost-plus (i.e. the profit for the supplier grows while the cost decreases) contracts are more suitable.

Q.27 Did the customer ask for cost-plus contracts? (KA 9)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1

Q.28 Did the customer plan for long time collaborations, partnership or joint-venture with the service supplier in order to empower trust? (KA 9)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1

Where the situation is very complex and services are in scope, qualitative metrics better support a contract than thousands of quantitative ones.

Q.29 Were qualitative metrics considered in the contract?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree
- ⇒ Base value: 1

Success

Project Management Institute (2008) states that "Success is measured by product and project quality, timeliness, budget compliance, and degree of customer satisfaction. "
Based on that (KA 2, 3, 4, 5):

Q.30 In terms of percentage, what was the variation between expected and actual budget?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choices
- ⇒ Possible values: from 0 to 25 / from 26 to 50 / from 51 to 75 / from 71 to 100 / more than 100
- ⇒ Base value: the first option

Q.31 In terms of percentage, what was the variation between expected and actual duration?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choices
- ⇒ Possible values: from 0 to 25 / from 26 to 50 / from 51 to 75 / from 71 to 100 / more than 100
- ⇒ Base value: the first option

Q.32 In terms of percentage, what was the variation between expected and actual scope?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choices
- ⇒ Possible values: from 0 to 25 / from 26 to 50 / from 51 to 75 / from 71 to 100 / more than 100
- ⇒ Base value: the first option

Q.33 Were any maintenance projects executed during the execution of the project in scope itself or during the first year after its conclusion?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choices
- ⇒ Possible values: from 0 to 1 / true-false / yes/no
- ⇒ Base value: 0 (true)
- ⇒ Meaning: check question to verify if the customer is allocating resources in different ways than changes

Q.34 Was the previous solution completely replaced from the new one?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choices
- ⇒ Possible values: from 0 to 1 / true-false / yes/no
- ⇒ Base value: 0 (true)
- ⇒ Meaning: check question to validate success

Reduced version – 30 Questions - For service suppliers/customers

This survey is part of a research aimed to analyze the factors that impacts the result of ICT projects related to SW Solutions in a scenario of business process reengineering and with access to outsourcing practice. Main purpose is to verify if quantitative factors can explain results better, worse or in the same way as mixed ones (i.e. quantitative and qualitative).

Questions will be mainly focused on

- *uncertainty and its impact on the outsourcing practice and project management methodology*
- *change management and its impact on internal staff*

The latter point (impact on internal staff and resistance to change) has been the “unmoved mover” (from Aristotle’s Metaphysics “πρῶτον κινούν ἀκίνητον” – latin primum movens -) of the research:

Structure of many answers underlines the desire to measure the maturity level that a customer has in strategically allocating resources. This is a consequence of its level of awareness on the subject and all the facets that the questions consider.

We want to thank you very much in advance for your contribution.

Scope of the questionnaire is to collect information related to an ICT SW project related to BPR (i.e. business process reengineering) and developed with the support of outsourced resources.

Assumptions:

- ⇒ The information provided is related to a business process reengineering project
- ⇒ In the hypothesis of data collection, the information should be provided by someone with thorough knowledge and understanding of the contract, additional formal documents and actual results
- ⇒ We expect to find evidence of the answers to questions below within the contract or additional formal document, being these sources facts
- ⇒ Depending on the context of the question, for the purpose of this questionnaire, “resources” means “measurable items” like: budget, time, rewards, number of meetings, number of situations arranged to create, improve, empower, modify the project execution and these cause additional costs.
- ⇒ GC: In the text, references to GC (i.e. generic question) refer to the next statement:
 - In the signed contract (or additional formal document), references to the topics mentioned above: “do not exist”, “are chaotic”, “are clear”, “are clear and in combination with a set of processes to manage them”, “are clear and in combination with a set of adaptive processes to manage them”
- ⇒ KA: it means “Knowledge Area”

General purpose

Q.1 Name of the project

- ⇒ Type: text
- ⇒ Meaning: ID for employees

Q.2 Among the below options, choose the one that better describes the industrial classification of the customer.

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: Consumer Discretionary, Consumer Staples, Energy, Financials, Health Care, Industrials, Information Technology, Materials, Telecommunication Services, Utilities (Standard & Poor's, 2006)

Q.3 To whom does the CIO report to?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: CEO, CFO, Other

Outsourcing paragraph

Outsourcing is the strategic use of external resources to fulfil activities usually handled by internal staff. We think that it means that outsourcing is often a matter of change management and change management is a matter of transition of individuals.

Q.4 Did the customer allocate resources and manage the change so to cope with potential resistance from the internal staff? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Why paragraph

Companies, while deciding how to perform their strategies, consider competitive advantage as key driver. Characteristics of competitive advantage are differentiation (qualitative characteristics) and costs (quantitative characteristics).

Outsourcing is usually applied to repeatable processes, it impacts on morale of employees, it is harbinger of hidden costs and lock-in and it claims for proper processes.

Q.5 During the evaluation phase of the decision-making process related to the adoption of outsourcing, which one of the following characteristics of competitive advantage was considered as crucial for the customer in order to decide?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choice
- ⇒ Options: costs (1) / a combination of them (2) / differentiation (3) / other (4)
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 4

Q.6 Did the customer clearly define the boundaries of outsourcing around repeatable processes/functions/activities? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.7 Did the customer allocate resources to manage the risk of lock-in that could rise from outsourcing? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.8 Did the customer allocate resources and manage the risk of hidden costs that could rise from outsourcing? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

What paragraph

Usually the more a business process is core the higher the need for customization, level of management, core skills and need for internal control.

Q.9 Which one of the typologies of outsourcing better describe the one applied for the project under investigation?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 4
- ⇒ Base value: 1

Q.10 Did the customer allocate resources and manage the project so to avoid an implicit handover to the service supplier and not to face the loss of control of the business process itself? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

How paragraph

Outsourcing can be classified as

- 5. Full: all the functionalities are outsourced*
- 6. Selective: some functionalities of a service are delivered internally and some others outsourced*
- 7. Transitional: obsolete and un-maintainable solutions require unavailable resources to be updated*
- 8. Transformational: the service provider acts as a tutor that enables the customer to move along a more valuable service*

and different typologies have a different impact on internal staff.

Who paragraph

Q.11 Did the customer allocate resources and manage the transformation of internal staff? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.12 Did the customer clarify the scope of the project with internal staff? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Agile

Agile project management differs from the traditional one in terms of iterations and adaptation. It is aimed to cope with uncertainty and it owns a proper declination: ad-hoc processes, proper roles and responsibilities, decisional autonomy, co-located teams, flexible schedule and budget, lean communications and documentation, motivated and skilled staff, high level of trust and a proper project team (where also the sponsor and the customer can be easily engaged).

Q.13 Did the customer allocate resources and manage the project to provide decisional autonomy to the project team? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.14 Co-location supports trust, communications, understanding and commonality of views and reduces uncertainty. Did the customer allocate resources and manage the project fostering co-located teams? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.15 The high level of uncertainty undermines the chances of properly forecasting or considering the schedule, the budget and the risks. Did the customer allocate resources and manage contingency reserves to cope with flexible schedule, budget and risks? (Continue with GC; KA 1 and 8)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.16 With respect to documentation, Agile PM means ad-hoc and mainly related to un-changeable assets documentation; that fact could impact next operational support. Did the customer allocate resources and manage the project so to cope with that characteristic? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.17 Did the customer allocate resources and manage the project to empower trust? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice

- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5
- ⇒ Base value: 3

Q.18 Did the customer have a talent management process for retrieving information to map tasks to internal staff?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choices
- ⇒ Possible values: from 0 to 1 / true-false / yes/no

Outsourcing and Uncertainty (Agile PM)

Outsourcing is usually applied to repeatable processes, it impacts on morale of employees, it is harbinger of hidden costs and lock-in and it claims for proper processes.

Agile project management differs from the traditional one in terms of iterations and adaptation. It is aimed to cope with uncertainty and it owns a proper declination whose main points are the source of the next questions. Agile PM needs ad-hoc processes, roles, decisional autonomy, co-located teams, flexible schedule and budget, lean communications and documentation, motivated and skilled staff, high level of trust and a proper project team where also the sponsor and the customer can be easily engaged.

Q.19 Being informed about the attitude of the customer's employees could be relevant for the supplier in order to evaluate trust, collaboration level and the related needed resources to properly manage the project. Did the customer allocate resources and manage the project so to motivate internal staff considering constraints rising (in that sense) from both the outsourcing and the agile PM? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.20 Did the customer allocate resources and manage the review of internal processes, roles and responsibilities in the light of constraints rising from both the outsourcing and the agile PM? (Continue with GC)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.21 Did the customer allocate resources and manage the project so to create agile channels of communications among sponsor, functional customer, project team and service supplier in the light of constraints rising from both the outsourcing and the agile PM? (Continue with GC; KA 7)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Knowledge areas (previously not considered)

Different levels of uncertainty correspond to different typologies of contracts and need for trust between the customer and the service supplier. When the level of uncertainty is low a fixed price contract could be acceptable but while uncertainty grows then time and material contracts if not cost-plus ones (i.e. the profit for the supplier grows while the cost

decreases) are more suitable. In order to ease the achievement of the wanted result, trust should grow accordingly to the growth of the uncertainty. In addition, where the situation is very complex, qualitative metrics better define the expectations of the customer than thousands of quantitative ones.

Q.22 In order to empower trust between the customer and the supplier, did the customer allocate resources and plan for long time collaboration, partnership or joint-venture with the service supplier? (Continue with GC; KA 9)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.23 In order to cope with high levels of uncertainty, did the customer consider qualitative metrics to evaluate both the deliverables and the service level? (Continue with GC; KA 5)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5 / from completely agree to completely disagree

Initial decisional drivers

We contend that, in order to be consistent, every single thing that can be source of cost or profits (and considered in the evaluation phase of the decision-making process) should be specified in the contract (and/or additional formal document agreed between the customer and the service supplier). This is due in order to be consistent, causal and to improve efficiency and effectiveness in situations of high uncertainty as the one under investigation.

In the previous sections we have shown how, in our hypothesis, uncertainty, project management approach, outsourcing characteristics, change management and human resources could be matched to the success (budget, duration and scope) since each one of them is a potential source of cost and constraint for the project plan. The list of attributes was so thorough also to test the level of analysis performed from the customer and related to the project under investigation

However each customer can decide to consider different things during its decision-making process but then (as per above considerations) these things should be reported into the mentioned formal documents.

Q.24 Under the above umbrella and with the exception of strategic cost factors analyzed in previous sections, did the customer consider any other strategic factors, allocate strategic resources and include them in any formal document? (i.e. strategic means that the reason for which the factors and related resources have been considered and allocated is mapped and stated).

For instance: Costs for infrastructures, 3; SW licenses, 4; ...

These factors should correspond to the ones considered in the cost-benefit-ROI analysis.

Please specify the factor/s and its/their strenght/s in a scale from 1 to 4 by modifying/integrating/removing prefilled values (the ones indicated below are examples). The meaning of the strenght is:

- chaotic
- clear

- clear and in combination to a process to manage it
- clear and in combination to an adaptive process to manage it

- ⇒ Type: Free text / Five boxes
- ⇒ Already filled in text: infrastructure, software licenses, internal staff, training, outsourcing service provider
- ⇒ Already filled in values: none

Q.25 Text box for other factors and comments (If above 5 boxes are not enough):

- ⇒ Type: Free text / Text box

Q.26 Which one of the below typologies of contract better adapts to the one chosen by the customer? (KA 9)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: fixed price (3) / time & material (2) / cost-plus (1)

Success

*Project Management Institute (2008) states that “Success is measured by product and project quality, timeliness, budget compliance, and degree of customer satisfaction. “
Based on that (KA 2, 3, 4):*

Q.27 In terms of percentage, what was the variation between expected and actual budget of the project?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choices
- ⇒ Possible values: 0 (1) / from 1 to 10 (2) / from 11 to 25 (3) / from 26 to 50 (4) / more than 50 (5)

Q.28 In terms of percentage, what was the variation between expected and actual duration of the project?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choices
- ⇒ Possible values: 0 (1) / from 1 to 10 (2) / from 11 to 25 (3) / from 26 to 50 (4) / more than 50 (5)

Q.29 In terms of percentage, what was the variation between expected and actual scope/features of the project? (this is considered to be a technical – related to the project not to the ICT - quality check)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choices
- ⇒ Possible values: 0 (1) / from 1 to 10 (2) / from 11 to 25 (3) / from 26 to 50 (4) / more than 50 (5)

Q.30 Did end users ask to review the deliverables and was this request the reason for any maintenance projects executed during the execution of the primary project itself or during the first year after its conclusion? (this question is considered to be a functional quality check)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / Single choices
- ⇒ Possible values: “No, end users didn't claim for changes”, “We ran some analyses due to some defects”, “Yes, one maintenance project was run”, “Yes, more than one maintenance project was run”, “Yes we had to thoroughly review the project deliverables”

Reduced version – 10 Questions - For employees

This survey is part of a research aimed to analyze the factors that impacts the result of ICT projects related to SW Solutions in a scenario of business process reengineering and with access to outsourcing practice. Main purpose is to verify if quantitative factors can explain results better, worse or in the same way as mixed ones (i.e. quantitative and qualitative).

Questions will be mainly focused on

- *uncertainty and its impact on the outsourcing practice and project management methodology*
- *change management and its impact on internal staff*

The latter point (impact on internal staff and resistance to change) has been the “unmoved mover” (from Aristotle’s Metaphysics “πρῶτον κινουῦν ἀκίνητον” – latin primum movens -) of the research:

Structure of many answers underlines the desire to measure the maturity level that a customer has in strategically allocating resources. This is a consequence of its level of awareness on the subject and all the facets that the questions consider.

We want to thank you very much in advance for your contribution.

Scope of the questionnaire is to collect information related to an ICT SW project related to BPR (i.e. business process reengineering) and developed with the support of outsourced resources

Assumptions:

- ⇒ The information provided is related to a business process reengineering project
- ⇒ We expect to find evidence of the answers to questions below within the contract or additional formal document, being these sources comparable to facts
- ⇒ Depending on the context of the question, for the purpose of this questionnaire, “resources” means “measurable items” like: budget, time, rewards, number of meetings, number of situations arranged to create, improve, empower, modify the project execution and these cause additional costs

General purpose

Q.1 Name of the project

- ⇒ Type: text
- ⇒ Meaning: ID for employees

Q.2 Which one among the next options better describes your role in the customer’s organization?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: exec, senior, middle, junior, technician/analyst, other (Management Study Guide, n.d)
- ⇒ Meaning: check question to verify impact of outsourcing

Outsourcing paragraph

Outsourcing is the strategic use of external resources to fulfil activities usually handled by internal staff. We think that it means that outsourcing is often a matter of change management and change management is a matter of transition of individuals.

Why paragraph

Companies, while deciding how to perform their strategies, consider competitive advantage as key driver. Characteristics of competitive advantage are differentiation (qualitative characteristics) and costs (quantitative characteristics).

Outsourcing is usually applied to repeatable processes, it impacts on morale of employees, it is harbinger of hidden costs and lock-in and it claims for proper processes.

How paragraph

Outsourcing can be classified as:

9. Full: all the functionalities are outsourced

10. Selective: some functionalities of a service are delivered internally and some others outsourced

11. Transitional: obsolete and un-maintainable solutions require unavailable resources to be updated

12. Transformational: the service provider acts as a tutor that enables the customer to move along a more valuable service

and different typologies have different impacts on internal staff.

Q.3 Which one of the next typologies of outsourcing better describes the project under investigation?

⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice

⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 4

What paragraph

Usually the corer a business process the higher the need for customization, level of management and core skills.

Q.4 How did the employer consider, allocate proper resources and manage the project to avoid an implicit handover to the service supplier and not to face the loss of control of the business process itself?

⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice

⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Who paragraph

Q.5 How did the employer allocate resources and manage the transformation of internal staff?

⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice

⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.6 How did the employer clarify the scope of the project with internal staff?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Agile

Agile project management differs from the traditional one in terms of iterations and adaptation. It is aimed to cope with uncertainty and owns a proper declination: ad-hoc processes, proper roles, responsibilities, decisional autonomy, co-located teams, flexible schedule and budget, lean communications and documentation, motivated and skilled staff, high level of trust and a proper project team (where also the sponsor and the customer can be easily engaged).

Q.7 How did the employer allocate resources and manage the project to provide decisional autonomy to the project team?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.8 How did the employer allocate resources and manage the project so to foster co-located teams?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.9 How did the employer allocate resources, and manage the project to empower trust?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Outsourcing and Uncertainty (Agile PM)

Outsourcing is usually applied to repeatable processes, it impacts on morale of employees, it is harbinger of hidden costs and lock-in and it claims for proper processes.

Agile project management differs from the traditional one in terms of iterations and adaptation. It is aimed to cope with uncertainty and owns a proper declination whose main points are the source of following questions. Agile PM needs ad-hoc processes, roles, decisional autonomy, co-located teams, flexible schedule and budget, lean communications and documentation, motivated and skilled staff, high level of trust and a proper project team where also the sponsor and the customer can be easily engaged.

Q.10 How did the employer allocate resources and manage the project to properly motivate internal staff considering constraints rising from both the outsourcing and the agile PM?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.11 How did the employer allocate resources and manage the project to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities in the light of constraints rising from both the outsourcing and the agile PM?

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5

Q.12 How did the employer allocate resources and manage the project to create agile channels of communications among sponsor, functional customer, project team and service supplier in the light of constraints rising from both the outsourcing and the agile PM? (KN 7)

- ⇒ Type: Multiple options / single choice
- ⇒ Possible values: from 1 to 5
- ⇒ Base value: 3

Knowledge areas (previously not considered)

Different levels of uncertainty correspond to different typologies of contracts and need for trust between the customer and the service supplier. When the level of uncertainty is low a fixed price contract could be acceptable but while uncertainty grows then time and material contracts if not cost-plus ones (i.e. the profit for the supplier grows while the cost decreases) are more suitable. In order to ease the achievement of the wanted result, trust should grow accordingly to the growth of the uncertainty. In addition, where the situation is very complex, qualitative metrics better define the expectations of the customer than thousands of quantitative ones.

Success

Project Management Institute (2008) states that “Success is measured by product and project quality, timeliness, budget compliance, and degree of customer satisfaction. “

Coded questions: Extended questionnaire

Acronym	Question	Description
G_PJN	Q_1	Project name to map suppliers and customer staff answers
G_IND	Q_2	Industrial classification of the customer
G_CIO	Q_3	Report chain of the CIO
O_RES	Q_4	Resistance to change from customer staff
O_CAC	Q_5	Reason related to competitive advantage that pushed the choice
O_BND	Q_6	Clear definition of the scope/boundaries to/of outsource
O_LKN	Q_7	Lock-in considered and managed
O_HDC	Q_8	Hidden costs considered and managed
O_TYP	Q_9	Typology of outsourcing
O_IHV	Q_10	Implicit handover considered and managed
O_STR	Q_11	Transformation of internal staff considered and managed
O_SCP	Q_12	Clarification of the scope considered and managed
A_AUT	Q_13	Autonomy to agile team considered and managed
A_CLT	Q_14	Co-location of agile considered and managed
A_CTR	Q_15	Contingency reserve to deal with flexible schedule, budget and risk considered and managed
A_AHD	Q_16	Ad-hoc documentation for agile team considered and managed
A_TST	Q_17	Trust for agile team considered and managed
A_TMP	Q_18	Existence of a talent management process
C_MTV	Q_19	Motivation of agile team considered and managed
C_PRC	Q_20	Review of internal processes to foster agile team considered and managed
C_CMM	Q_21	Agile communications to foster agile team considered and managed
C_LTC	Q_22	Long term collaboration between the customer and the supplier considered and managed
C_QTY	Q_23	Qualitative metrics to cope with uncertainty considered and managed
C_OTH	Q_24	Other factors of cost
C_TXT	Q_25	Other factors of cost free text
C_CTR	Q_26	Typology of the contract
S_BDG	Q_27	Degree of success in terms of budget
S_DRT	Q_28	Degree of success in terms of duration
S_SC1	Q_29	Degree of success in terms of scope technical check
S_SC2	Q_30	Degree of success in terms of scope functional check

Coded questions: Reduced questionnaire

Acronym	Question	Description	Cross ref.
G_PJN	Q_1	Project name to map suppliers and customer's staff answers	Q_1
G_ROL	Q_2	Employee's role	N/A
O_TYP	Q_3	Typology of outsourcing	Q_9
O_IHV	Q_4	Implicit handover considered and managed	Q_10
O_STR	Q_5	Transformation of internal staff considered and managed	Q_11
O_SCP	Q_6	Clarification of the scope considered and managed	Q_12
A_AUT	Q_7	Autonomy to agile team considered and managed	Q_13
A_CLT	Q_8	Co-location of agile considered and managed	Q_14
A_TST	Q_9	Trust for agile team considered and managed	Q_17
C_MTV	Q_10	Motivation of agile team considered and managed	Q_19
C_PRC	Q_11	Review of internal processes to foster agile team considered and managed	Q_20
C_CMM	Q_12	Agile communications to foster agile team considered and managed	Q_21

Interpreted interviews

1st Transcript

- We work in the public sector / government
- When we outsource usually support infrastructure not SW Solutions
- We act on behalf of the employees
- Employees are not motivated enough to learn, improve and work
- Employees are never made redundant
- Costs are relevant and the control in the outsourcer's hands
- The outsourcer delivers details not only a backbone or a rough platform where internal employees can start with customization

2nd Transcript

- From a strategic standpoint it does not make sense to outsource services that differentiate
- Nevertheless there are some exceptions
- Studies show how there are exceptions:
 - Application development, maintenance and testing
 - Data centre / application hosting
 - Network and telecommunications
 - End-user services (workplace, helpdesk...)
- Outsourcing makes sense per independent autonomous services
- In case of interdependence we have to carefully evaluate interdependencies

3rd Transcript

- Outsourcing of SW Solutions with BPR is difficult to understand
- Often it is approached for differentiation
- Change is usually not properly managed and a serious issue
- Benefits are not clear either in terms of differentiation or cost
- Often the scope seems to be not clear or the path against the scope not properly planned

4th Transcript

- Outsourcing is used to achieve competitive advantage but rarely we see how it happens either for costs or differentiation
- Perhaps there are other drivers that allow to get more credibility in the financial market or to retrieve funds for other purposes. Financial market could be a reason but we do not see the pattern / logic
- Customer and/or vendor lock-in is a common practice in Italy
- US and Japanese customers are better than Italian ones in maintaining the control
- Many indicators show how the focus seems to be different from the one stated
- Issue for employees are unpredictable and not only related to the ICT dept

5th/6th Transcripts

- Customers are in general not experts in Outsourcing
- In given Countries (Italy, Spain,.. Mediterranean region), customers approach outsourcing contracts with a long list of assumptions rather than with a service definition and related quality criteria
- This is good for the outsourcer since, due to the complexity of ICT SW projects, there will be many exceptions to the contract.
- Cost-plus contracts (used in situations of high uncertainty) are often used in Outsourcing projects but not in Mediterranean region.
- Customer rarely measures results and outsourcing is often a trend
- Outsourcing is often the chance for business process reengineering

7th Transcript

- Most times, there is no proper decisional model.
- Most managers “assume” there will be a cost reduction because they only look at the salaries/cost of personnel of the outsourced people, not the overall project cost.

8th Transcript

- We outsource everything from repeatable processes to standard ones
- Independently of the results, once the project is closed we rarely measure benefits. It is archived full stop
- The efficacy and efficiency of a project in supporting strategies is not considered

9th/10th Transcripts

- Lack of experience related to BPR outsourcing
- Outsourcing is usually applied to stable assets like infrastructure
- This is common in infrastructures because we just set up the firewall but do not do that
- Relevant is the control of the subject: maintaining it
- Nevertheless, sometimes there is the risk of lock-in and for that reason the control is relevant and only “stable assets should be outsourced”

11th Transcripts

- Impact on internal resources depends also on the size of the ICTdept. Sometimes it is so small that it is impossible to make employees redundant something
- In some cases the department is so small that support or development of business processes must be outsourced

12th Transcripts

- There are two types of outsourcing:
 - Functional / hierarchical
 - Per process
- Dealing with ICT outsourcing is, in some cases, a serious limit because it impacts the whole company. It means excluding the business side.

- In general the outsourcer is specialized in the delivery of a particular service so to offer the same service to multiple customers and in that way exploiting scale economies. All of it could move against standard processes in the customer side, poor adaptation to the surrounding environment and next lack of competitive advantage.
- To reduce costs the outsourcer often has recourse to offshoring practices.
- With respect to the contract, who drives the drafting is usually the outsourcer. KPIs are relevant elements to consider but rarely properly considered (KPIs measure SLAs).

13th Transcripts

- Outsourcing is often used to achieve per competitive advantage in both its declinations
- It is not clear how to differentiate since outsourcers try to deliver a standard service many times
- Lack of scope is a possible indicator of concealed purposes: we state something but are looking for something different
- IBM differentiated sectors closing the collaboration among them in the 80's. It was a failure because of lack of cooperation and opportunity.
- Above point means that differentiation is a plus just if there is the opportunity not per itself.

Data analysis (full version)

Quantitative model

*Cost of the HW - C. OTH HW * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S. BDG*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.084 ^a	9	.430	.403 ^b	.391	.416			
Likelihood Ratio	10.453	9	.315	.351 ^b	.339	.363			
Fisher's Exact Test	10.402			.342 ^b	.330	.354			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.410 ^c	1	.522	.568 ^b	.555	.580	.316 ^b	.304 .328	
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 16 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2000000.

c. The standardized statistic is -.641.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.148	.272	-.535	.593	.600 ^c	.587	.613
N of Valid Cases	23							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2000000.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	7.467 ^a	12	.825	.926 ^b	.919	.933			
Likelihood Ratio	8.141	12	.774	.945 ^b	.940	.951			
Fisher's Exact Test	8.442			.970 ^b	.965	.974			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.070 ^c	1	.791	.858 ^b	.849	.867	.438 ^b	.425 .451	
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2000000.

c. The standardized statistic is -.265.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.099	.238	-.420	.675	.704 ^c	.693	.716
N of Valid Cases		23						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2000000.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	3.450 ^a	6	.751	.730 ^b	.719	.741			
Likelihood Ratio	4.514	6	.607	.698 ^b	.686	.710			
Fisher's Exact Test	5.152			.818 ^b	.808	.828			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.166 ^c	1	.684	.791 ^b	.781	.802	.451 ^b	.438 .464	
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 10 cells (83.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2000000.

c. The standardized statistic is -.407.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.212	.309	-.659	.510	.634 ^c	.621	.646
N of Valid Cases		23						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2000000.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	13.485 ^a	12	.335	.372 ^b	.360	.385			
Likelihood Ratio	15.859	12	.198	.264 ^b	.253	.275			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.261			.305 ^b	.293	.317			
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.552 ^c	1	.033	.039 ^b	.034	.044	.021 ^b	.017 .025	
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2000000.

c. The standardized statistic is 2.134.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.564	.197	2.620	.009	.023 ^c	.019	.027
N of Valid Cases	23							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2000000.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	7.613 ^a	9	.574	.562 ^b	.549	.575			
Likelihood Ratio	9.964	9	.353	.386 ^b	.373	.398			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.966			.415 ^b	.402	.427			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.785 ^c	1	.376	.460 ^b	.447	.472	.230 ^b	.219 .241	
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 16 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 79654295.

c. The standardized statistic is .886.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.305	.279	1.083	.279	.271 ^c	.259	.282
N of Valid Cases		23						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 79654295.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.491 ^a	12	.573	.664 ^b	.652	.676			
Likelihood Ratio	11.784	12	.463	.639 ^b	.626	.651			
Fisher's Exact Test	10.589			.707 ^b	.696	.719			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.298 ^c	1	.585	.630 ^b	.617	.642	.332 ^b	.320 .344	
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 79654295.

c. The standardized statistic is -.546.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.108	.258	-.415	.678	.675 ^c	.663	.687
N of Valid Cases	23							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 79654295.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	7.016 ^a	6	.319	.307 ^b	.295	.319			
Likelihood Ratio	7.165	6	.306	.260 ^b	.248	.271			
Fisher's Exact Test	7.442			.362 ^b	.350	.375			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.877 ^c	1	.090	.110 ^b	.102	.118	.080 ^b	.073 .087	
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 10 cells (83.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 79654295.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.696.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.652	.242	2.037	.042	.073 ^c	.066	.080
N of Valid Cases	23							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 79654295.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	13.309 ^a	12	.347	.380 ^b	.367	.392			
Likelihood Ratio	14.324	12	.280	.344 ^b	.331	.356			
Fisher's Exact Test	12.061			.443 ^b	.430	.455			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.358 ^c	1	.244	.290 ^b	.278	.301	.147 ^b	.137 .156	
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 79654295.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.165.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.328	.254	1.237	.216	.205 ^c	.194	.215
N of Valid Cases		23						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 79654295.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	11.707 ^a	9	.230	.239 ^b	.228	.250			
Likelihood Ratio	10.171	9	.337	.530 ^b	.517	.543			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.127			.461 ^b	.448	.474			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.028 ^c	1	.868	.904 ^b	.897	.912	.484 ^b	.471 .497	
N of Valid Cases	22								

a. 16 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1507486128.

c. The standardized statistic is -.166.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.055	.305	.181	.856	.834 ^c	.825	.844
N of Valid Cases		22						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1507486128.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	12.756 ^a	12	.387	.438 ^b	.426	.451			
Likelihood Ratio	12.979	12	.371	.614 ^b	.601	.627			
Fisher's Exact Test	10.852			.613 ^b	.600	.626			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.019 ^c	1	.890	.935 ^b	.929	.942	.483 ^b	.470 .496	
N of Valid Cases	22								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1507486128.

c. The standardized statistic is -.138.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.036	.248	.145	.884	.890 ^c	.882	.898
N of Valid Cases		22						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1507486128.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	4.574 ^a	6	.599	.709 ^b	.697	.720			
Likelihood Ratio	5.050	6	.537	.763 ^b	.752	.774			
Fisher's Exact Test	4.621			.813 ^b	.803	.823			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.054 ^c	1	.152	.198 ^b	.188	.208	.122 ^b	.113 .130	
N of Valid Cases	22								

a. 11 cells (91.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1507486128.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.433.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.514	.239	-1.765	.078	.146 ^c	.136	.155
N of Valid Cases	22							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1507486128.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	14.961 ^a	12	.244	.255 ^b	.244	.266			
Likelihood Ratio	16.395	12	.174	.415 ^b	.403	.428			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.591			.464 ^b	.452	.477			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.628 ^c	1	.105	.117 ^b	.109	.125	.060 ^b	.054 .066	
N of Valid Cases	22								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .27.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1507486128.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.621.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.400	.178	2.190	.029	.084 ^c	.077	.091
N of Valid Cases	22							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1507486128.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	7.818 ^a	9	.553	.665 ^b	.653	.677			
Likelihood Ratio	10.032	9	.348	.583 ^b	.571	.596			
Fisher's Exact Test	8.305			.621 ^b	.609	.634			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.328 ^c	1	.567	.640 ^b	.627	.652	.332 ^b	.320 .344	
N of Valid Cases	22								

a. 16 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 205597102.

c. The standardized statistic is -.573.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.167	.279	-.595	.552	.531 ^c	.518	.544
N of Valid Cases		22						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 205597102.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	11.079 ^a	12	.522	.628 ^b	.615	.640			
Likelihood Ratio	14.392	12	.276	.476 ^b	.463	.489			
Fisher's Exact Test	12.216			.359 ^b	.346	.371			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.157 ^c	1	.692	.742 ^b	.730	.753	.379 ^b	.366 .391	
N of Valid Cases	22								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 205597102.

c. The standardized statistic is .396.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.118	.224	.528	.597	.635 ^c	.623	.648
N of Valid Cases		22						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 205597102.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	4.166 ^a	6	.654	.799 ^b	.789	.809			
Likelihood Ratio	5.108	6	.530	.739 ^b	.728	.751			
Fisher's Exact Test	4.801			.856 ^b	.847	.865			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.400 ^c	1	.527	.674 ^b	.662	.686	.347 ^b	.334 .359	
N of Valid Cases	22								

a. 11 cells (91.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 205597102.

c. The standardized statistic is .632.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.296	.358	.800	.424	.394 ^c	.382	.407
N of Valid Cases		22						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 205597102.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	16.317 ^a	12	.177	.176 ^b	.166	.186			
Likelihood Ratio	20.215	12	.063	.114 ^b	.105	.122			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.105			.116 ^b	.107	.124			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.258 ^c	1	.133	.147 ^b	.138	.156	.085 ^b	.077 .092	
N of Valid Cases	22								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 205597102.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.503.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.348	.229	1.468	.142	.153 ^c	.144	.162
N of Valid Cases		22						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 205597102.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	13.050 ^a	12	.365	.267 ^b	.256	.279			
Likelihood Ratio	13.161	12	.357	.332 ^b	.319	.344			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.527			.269 ^b	.257	.280			
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.157 ^c	1	.076	.085 ^b	.078	.092	.049 ^b	.044 .055	
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 846668601.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.777.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.493	.246	1.927	.054	.044 ^c	.039	.049
N of Valid Cases		23						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 846668601.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	13.800 ^a	16	.614	.718 ^b	.706	.730			
Likelihood Ratio	14.302	16	.576	.749 ^b	.738	.760			
Fisher's Exact Test	15.171			.708 ^b	.696	.720			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.409 ^c	1	.121	.129 ^b	.120	.137	.072 ^b	.066 .079	
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 846668601.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.552.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.391	.203	1.896	.058	.086 ^c	.079	.093
N of Valid Cases		23						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 846668601.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	5.615 ^a	8	.690	.684 ^b	.672	.696			
Likelihood Ratio	7.223	8	.513	.539 ^b	.526	.551			
Fisher's Exact Test	8.581			.656 ^b	.644	.668			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.440 ^c	1	.507	.669 ^b	.657	.682	.339 ^b	.326 .351	
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 13 cells (86.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 846668601.

c. The standardized statistic is .663.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.289	.316	.898	.369	.394 ^c	.382	.407
N of Valid Cases		23						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 846668601.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	16.264 ^a	16	.435	.501 ^b	.489	.514			
Likelihood Ratio	17.522	16	.353	.427 ^b	.414	.439			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.582			.486 ^b	.473	.499			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.742 ^c	1	.187	.201 ^b	.191	.212	.107 ^b .099 .115		
N of Valid Cases	23								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 846668601.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.320.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.		
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.365	.237	1.578	.115	.119 ^c .110 .127	
N of Valid Cases	23						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 846668601.

Qualitative model: the Outsourcing subset

Allocation of resources to cope with resistance to change from the internal staff - O_RES * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S_BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	14.536 ^a	16	.559	.548 ^b	.535	.561			
Likelihood Ratio	16.493	16	.419	.434 ^b	.421	.447			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.140			.536 ^b	.523	.549			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.690 ^c	1	.406	.449 ^b	.436	.462	.231 ^b	.220 .241	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 969556011.

c. The standardized statistic is -.831.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.109	.235	-.456	.648	.634 ^c	.622	.647
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 969556011.

Allocation of resources to cope with resistance to change from the internal staff - O RES * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	16.916 ^a	16	.391	.440 ^b	.427	.452			
Likelihood Ratio	18.796	16	.279	.541 ^b	.528	.554			
Fisher's Exact Test	15.208			.550 ^b	.537	.562			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.042 ^c	1	.837	.863 ^b	.854	.872	.442 ^b	.429 .455	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 969556011.

c. The standardized statistic is .206.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.082	.217	.381	.703	.702 ^c	.690	.713
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 969556011.

*Allocation of resources to cope with resistance to change from the internal staff - O RES * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	16.660 ^a	16	.408	.290 ^b	.278	.301			
Likelihood Ratio	16.582	16	.413	.245 ^b	.234	.256			
Fisher's Exact Test	19.255			.306 ^b	.294	.317			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.253 ^c	1	.615	.669 ^b	.657	.681	.354 ^b	.342 .367	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 969556011.

c. The standardized statistic is -.503.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.131	.283	.469	.639	.651 ^c	.639	.663
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 969556011.

Allocation of resources to cope with resistance to change from the internal staff - O RES * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	19.150 ^a	16	.261	.280 ^b	.268	.291			
Likelihood Ratio	21.649	16	.155	.282 ^b	.271	.294			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.194			.286 ^b	.274	.298			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.242 ^c	1	.622	.639 ^b	.627	.652	.335 ^b	.323 .347	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 969556011.

c. The standardized statistic is .492.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.150	.215	.697	.486	.481 ^c	.468	.494
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 969556011.

Clear definition of the boundaries of outsourcing (repeatable processes/functions/...) - O BND * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.766 ^a	16	.281	.296 ^b	.285	.308			
Likelihood Ratio	21.867	16	.148	.137 ^b	.128	.146			
Fisher's Exact Test	19.451			.144 ^b	.135	.153			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.004 ^c	1	.949	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000	.500 ^b	.487 .513	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 306940390.

c. The standardized statistic is .063.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.115	.258	.448	.654	.610 ^c	.598	.623
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 306940390.

Clear definition of the boundaries of outsourcing (repeatable processes/functions/...) - O BND * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	20.096 ^a	16	.216	.218 ^b	.208	.229			
Likelihood Ratio	24.676	16	.076	.165 ^b	.155	.174			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.965			.128 ^b	.119	.136			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.259 ^c	1	.262	.284 ^b	.272	.296	.141 ^b	.132 .150	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 306940390.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.122.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.261	.221	1.187	.235	.200 ^c	.190	.211
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 306940390.

Clear definition of the boundaries of outsourcing (repeatable processes/functions/...) - O BND * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	21.793 ^a	16	.150	.171 ^b	.161	.181			
Likelihood Ratio	16.009	16	.452	.313 ^b	.301	.325			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.618			.323 ^b	.311	.335			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.943 ^c	1	.163	.196 ^b	.186	.206	.103 ^b	.095 .111	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 306940390.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.394.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.280	.259	-1.014	.311	.317 ^c	.305	.329
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 306940390.

Clear definition of the boundaries of outsourcing (repeatable processes/functions/...) - O BND * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	23.226 ^a	16	.108	.097 ^b	.089	.104			
Likelihood Ratio	26.711	16	.045	.099 ^b	.091	.106			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.354			.124 ^b	.115	.132			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.112 ^c	1	.737	.775 ^b	.764	.786	.393 ^b	.380 .405	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 306940390.

c. The standardized statistic is .335.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.010	.202	.050	.960	.970 ^c	.965	.974
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 306940390.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	13.003 ^a	16	.673	.729 ^b	.717	.740			
Likelihood Ratio	15.955	16	.456	.531 ^b	.519	.544			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.345			.524 ^b	.511	.536			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.000 ^c	1	.986	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000	.509 ^b	.496 .521	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 172720898.

c. The standardized statistic is .017.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.		
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.098	.245	.402	.688	.663 ^c	.650 .675
N of Valid Cases	25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 172720898.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	21.344 ^a	16	.166	.156 ^b	.147	.165			
Likelihood Ratio	26.402	16	.049	.084 ^b	.077	.091			
Fisher's Exact Test	19.254			.057 ^b	.051	.062			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.008 ^c	1	.928	.956 ^b	.951	.962	.480 ^b	.467 .493	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 172720898.

c. The standardized statistic is .090.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.066	.235	.281	.779	.754 ^c	.743	.765
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 172720898.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	17.346 ^a	16	.364	.398 ^b	.385	.410			
Likelihood Ratio	13.778	16	.615	.549 ^b	.536	.562			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.710			.597 ^b	.585	.610			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.063 ^c	1	.802	.870 ^b	.861	.878	.449 ^b	.436 .461	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 172720898.

c. The standardized statistic is -.250.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.136	.297	.459	.646	.635 ^c	.623	.648
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 172720898.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.703 ^a	16	.882	.959 ^b	.954	.964			
Likelihood Ratio	13.160	16	.661	.951 ^b	.945	.956			
Fisher's Exact Test	10.854			.959 ^b	.954	.964			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.573 ^c	1	.449	.489 ^b	.476	.502	.249 ^b	.238 .260	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 172720898.

c. The standardized statistic is -.757.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.174	.195	-.887	.375	.419 ^c	.406	.431
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 172720898.

Allocation of resources to cope with the risk of hidden costs - O HDC * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.809 ^a	16	.876	.901 ^b	.893	.909			
Likelihood Ratio	11.408	16	.784	.868 ^b	.859	.877			
Fisher's Exact Test	15.421			.860 ^b	.851	.869			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.953 ^c	1	.162	.166 ^b	.157	.176	.089 ^b	.082 .096	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 15053862.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.397.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.288	.244	-1.158	.247	.219 ^c	.208	.229
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 15053862.

Allocation of resources to cope with the risk of hidden costs - O HDC * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.796 ^a	16	.467	.535 ^b	.522	.548			
Likelihood Ratio	17.530	16	.352	.557 ^b	.544	.570			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.875			.581 ^b	.568	.593			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.654 ^c	1	.419	.435 ^b	.422	.448	.227 ^b	.216 .238	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 15053862.

c. The standardized statistic is -.809.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.154	.218	-.697	.486	.480 ^c	.467	.493
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 15053862.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	11.143 ^a	16	.801	.697 ^b	.685	.708			
Likelihood Ratio	11.327	16	.789	.733 ^b	.721	.744			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.609			.752 ^b	.740	.763			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.406 ^c	1	.236	.256 ^b	.244	.267	.139 ^b	.130 .148	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 15053862.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.186.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.214	.265	-.797	.426	.474 ^c	.461	.486
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 15053862.

Allocation of resources to cope with the risk of hidden costs - O HDC * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S_SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.891 ^a	16	.816	.918 ^b	.911	.925			
Likelihood Ratio	12.065	16	.739	.947 ^b	.941	.953			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.891			.957 ^b	.951	.962			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.118 ^c	1	.732	.758 ^b	.747	.769	.386 ^b	.373 .398	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 15053862.

c. The standardized statistic is -.343.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.068	.210	-.326	.744	.749 ^c	.738	.760
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 15053862.

Allocation of resources so to avoid an loss of control via an implicit handover to the Service Provider - O IHV * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	19.550 ^a	16	.241	.232 ^b	.221	.243			
Likelihood Ratio	14.882	16	.533	.677 ^b	.665	.689			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.830			.690 ^b	.678	.702			
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.362 ^c	1	.067	.069 ^b	.063	.076	.038 ^b	.033 .043	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1988899140.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.834.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.307	.224	-1.298	.194	.160 ^c	.151	.170
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1988899140.

Allocation of resources so to avoid an loss of control via an implicit handover to the Service Provider - O IHV * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	17.373 ^a	16	.362	.393 ^b	.380	.406			
Likelihood Ratio	18.912	16	.273	.659 ^b	.647	.671			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.474			.679 ^b	.667	.691			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.644 ^c	1	.200	.223 ^b	.212	.234	.112 ^b	.104 .120	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1988899140.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.282.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.202	.199	-.993	.321	.325 ^c	.313	.337
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1988899140.

Allocation of resources so to avoid an loss of control via an implicit handover to the Service Provider - O IHV * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	17.735 ^a	16	.340	.361 ^b	.348	.373			
Likelihood Ratio	12.879	16	.682	.786 ^b	.775	.796			
Fisher's Exact Test	15.324			.752 ^b	.741	.763			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.678 ^c	1	.102	.106 ^b	.098	.114	.060 ^b	.054 .066	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1988899140.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.637.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.258	.260	-.935	.350	.355 ^c	.343	.368
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1988899140.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	7.131 ^a	16	.971	.994 ^b	.992	.996			
Likelihood Ratio	10.674	16	.829	.993 ^b	.991	.995			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.104			.994 ^b	.992	.996			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.001 ^c	1	.982	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000	.519 ^b	.506 .531	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1988899140.

c. The standardized statistic is .023.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.005	.200	.026	.979	.975 ^c	.971	.979
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1988899140.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.970 ^a	12	.619	.741 ^b	.730	.752			
Likelihood Ratio	8.832	12	.717	.859 ^b	.850	.868			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.549			.836 ^b	.826	.845			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.458 ^c	1	.117	.122 ^b	.114	.131	.071 ^b	.065 .078	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .16.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1803017504.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.568.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.341	.222	-1.476	.140	.142 ^c	.133	.150
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1803017504.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.722 ^a	12	.640	.717 ^b	.705	.728			
Likelihood Ratio	12.861	12	.379	.716 ^b	.704	.727			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.960			.692 ^b	.680	.704			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.489 ^c	1	.484	.516 ^b	.503	.529	.267 ^b	.256 .279	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .48.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1803017504.

c. The standardized statistic is -.699.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.137	.207	-.656	.512	.524 ^c	.511	.537
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1803017504.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	20.971 ^a	12	.051	.012 ^b	.009	.014			
Likelihood Ratio	18.791	12	.094	.024 ^b	.020	.028			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.688			.015 ^b	.012	.018			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.121 ^c	1	.728	.742 ^b	.731	.753	.409 ^b	.396 .421	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 19 cells (95.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .16.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1803017504.

c. The standardized statistic is -.347.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.141	.353	.396	.692	.622 ^c	.610	.634
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1803017504.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	6.849 ^a	12	.867	.927 ^b	.921	.934			
Likelihood Ratio	9.489	12	.661	.926 ^b	.919	.933			
Fisher's Exact Test	7.613			.938 ^b	.931	.944			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.094 ^c	1	.759	.770 ^b	.759	.781	.412 ^b	.400 .425	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .48.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1803017504.

c. The standardized statistic is -.307.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.062	.165	-.377	.706	.769 ^c	.758	.780
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1803017504.

Clarification of the scope of the project with internal staff - O SCP * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.693 ^a	12	.643	.683 ^b	.671	.695			
Likelihood Ratio	11.019	12	.527	.665 ^b	.653	.677			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.449			.685 ^b	.673	.697			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.005 ^c	1	.942	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000	.514 ^b	.501 .527	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1559012828.

c. The standardized statistic is -.073.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.		
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.007	.245	.028	.978	.988 ^c	.985 .991
N of Valid Cases	25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1559012828.

Clarification of the scope of the project with internal staff - O SCP * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.532 ^a	12	.742	.837 ^b	.828	.847			
Likelihood Ratio	10.550	12	.568	.840 ^b	.830	.849			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.088			.783 ^b	.773	.794			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.458 ^c	1	.498	.550 ^b	.537	.563	.275 ^b	.263 .286	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1559012828.

c. The standardized statistic is .677.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.178	.250	.716	.474	.447 ^c	.434	.460
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1559012828.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	11.263 ^a	12	.507	.513 ^b	.500	.525			
Likelihood Ratio	10.291	12	.590	.559 ^b	.547	.572			
Fisher's Exact Test	12.575			.564 ^b	.551	.577			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.340 ^c	1	.560	.655 ^b	.643	.667	.324 ^b	.312 .336	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 19 cells (95.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1559012828.

c. The standardized statistic is .583.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.373	.287	1.223	.221	.236 ^c	.225	.247
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1559012828.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.861 ^a	12	.715	.805 ^b	.795	.815			
Likelihood Ratio	12.218	12	.428	.692 ^b	.680	.704			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.878			.671 ^b	.659	.683			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.656 ^c	1	.418	.445 ^b	.432	.458	.232 ^b	.221 .242	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1559012828.

c. The standardized statistic is -.810.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.188	.182	-1.029	.303	.428 ^c	.415	.441
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1559012828.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.429 ^a	16	.843	.842 ^b	.832	.851			
Likelihood Ratio	10.835	16	.820	.853 ^b	.844	.862			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.540			.849 ^b	.839	.858			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.130 ^c	1	.718	.769 ^b	.758	.780	.395 ^b	.382 .407	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 110811807.

c. The standardized statistic is -.361.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.013	.267	.048	.962	.954 ^c	.949	.959
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 110811807.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	12.484 ^a	16	.710	.852 ^b	.842	.861			
Likelihood Ratio	13.679	16	.623	.785 ^b	.774	.795			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.162			.785 ^b	.774	.796			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.342 ^c	1	.559	.578 ^b	.566	.591	.297 ^b	.285 .308	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 110811807.

c. The standardized statistic is .585.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.191	.228	.825	.410	.403 ^c	.390	.415
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 110811807.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.699 ^a	16	.925	.821 ^b	.811	.831			
Likelihood Ratio	10.616	16	.833	.695 ^b	.683	.707			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.518			.818 ^b	.808	.828			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.062 ^c	1	.803	.867 ^b	.858	.876	.449 ^b	.436 .462	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 23 cells (92.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 110811807.

c. The standardized statistic is -.249.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.058	.240	.241	.809	.856 ^c	.847	.865
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 110811807.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.931 ^a	16	.272	.289 ^b	.277	.300			
Likelihood Ratio	16.899	16	.392	.475 ^b	.462	.488			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.384			.462 ^b	.449	.475			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.386 ^c	1	.535	.574 ^b	.561	.586	.290 ^b	.279 .302	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 110811807.

c. The standardized statistic is .621.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.163	.215	.743	.458	.481 ^c	.468	.493
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 110811807.

*Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	25.170 ^a	16	.067	.091 ^b	.084	.099			
Likelihood Ratio	25.799	16	.057	.021 ^b	.017	.024			
Fisher's Exact Test	24.168			.019 ^b	.015	.022			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.803 ^c	1	.370	.410 ^b	.397	.423	.210 ^b	.200 .221	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 921622515.

c. The standardized statistic is .896.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.242	.244	1.001	.317	.281 ^c	.269	.292
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 921622515.

Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	25.941 ^a	16	.055	.029 ^b	.024	.033			
Likelihood Ratio	29.689	16	.020	.023 ^b	.019	.026			
Fisher's Exact Test	22.811			.013 ^b	.010	.016			
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.058 ^c	1	.080	.090 ^b	.083	.098	.047 ^b	.042 .053	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 921622515.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.749.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.356	.212	1.680	.093	.090 ^c	.082	.097
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 921622515.

Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.994 ^a	16	.453	.362 ^b	.349	.374			
Likelihood Ratio	14.431	16	.567	.453 ^b	.440	.465			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.881			.428 ^b	.415	.440			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.091 ^c	1	.763	.796 ^b	.785	.806	.408 ^b	.396 .421	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 921622515.

c. The standardized statistic is -.301.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.207	.274	.766	.444	.468 ^c	.455	.481
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 921622515.

Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	17.710 ^a	16	.341	.375 ^b	.363	.388			
Likelihood Ratio	17.633	16	.346	.576 ^b	.563	.589			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.412			.641 ^b	.629	.653			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.144 ^c	1	.704	.728 ^b	.716	.739	.377 ^b	.364 .389	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 921622515.

c. The standardized statistic is .380.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.102	.234	.433	.665	.634 ^c	.622	.647
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 921622515.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.192 ^a	16	.313	.336 ^b	.324	.349			
Likelihood Ratio	18.473	16	.297	.334 ^b	.322	.346			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.685			.322 ^b	.310	.334			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.384 ^c	1	.536	.579 ^b	.566	.592	.306 ^b	.294 .318	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1951498964.

c. The standardized statistic is -.619.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.089	.241	-.368	.713	.693 ^c	.681	.705
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1951498964.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	27.103 ^a	16	.040	.032 ^b	.028	.037			
Likelihood Ratio	30.507	16	.016	.032 ^b	.027	.037			
Fisher's Exact Test	20.958			.028 ^b	.024	.032			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.101 ^c	1	.751	.764 ^b	.753	.775	.405 ^b	.393 .418	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1951498964.

c. The standardized statistic is -.317.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.054	.239	-.225	.822	.798 ^c	.787	.808
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1951498964.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S_SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	20.975 ^a	16	.179	.208 ^b	.198	.219			
Likelihood Ratio	14.203	16	.584	.522 ^b	.509	.535			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.216			.623 ^b	.611	.636			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.292 ^c	1	.589	.644 ^b	.631	.656	.338 ^b	.326 .351	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1951498964.

c. The standardized statistic is -.540.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.008	.283	.029	.977	.979 ^c	.976	.983
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1951498964.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.762 ^a	16	.470	.539 ^b	.526	.552			
Likelihood Ratio	18.451	16	.298	.636 ^b	.624	.649			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.580			.675 ^b	.662	.687			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.598 ^c	1	.439	.465 ^b	.452	.477	.246 ^b	.235 .257	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1951498964.

c. The standardized statistic is -.773.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.146	.204	-.715	.474	.491 ^c	.478	.504
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1951498964.

*Main reason to outsource - O CAC * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	7.605 ^a	12	.815	.844 ^b	.834	.853			
Likelihood Ratio	8.510	12	.744	.863 ^b	.854	.872			
Fisher's Exact Test	10.194			.845 ^b	.836	.854			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.073 ^c	1	.787	.826 ^b	.816	.836	.436 ^b	.423 .448	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1676440099.

c. The standardized statistic is -.271.

*Main reason to outsource - O CAC * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	17.251 ^a	12	.140	.137 ^b	.129	.146			
Likelihood Ratio	18.992	12	.089	.175 ^b	.165	.185			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.167			.232 ^b	.221	.242			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.003 ^c	1	.958	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000	.505 ^b	.492 .518	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1676440099.

c. The standardized statistic is .052.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	20.252 ^a	12	.062	.093 ^b	.086	.101			
Likelihood Ratio	20.965	12	.051	.008 ^b	.006	.010			
Fisher's Exact Test	19.508			.014 ^b	.011	.017			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.696 ^c	1	.193	.213 ^b	.203	.224	.126 ^b	.117 .134	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 19 cells (95.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1676440099.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.302.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.994 ^a	12	.616	.702 ^b	.690	.714			
Likelihood Ratio	11.801	12	.462	.752 ^b	.741	.763			
Fisher's Exact Test	8.622			.863 ^b	.854	.872			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.020 ^c	1	.888	.939 ^b	.933	.945	.479 ^b	.466 .492	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1676440099.

c. The standardized statistic is .140.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.206 ^a	12	.598	.689 ^b	.677	.701			
Likelihood Ratio	10.895	12	.538	.687 ^b	.675	.699			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.117			.652 ^b	.639	.664			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.370 ^c	1	.543	.607 ^b	.595	.620	.317 ^b	.305 .329	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1465507556.

c. The standardized statistic is .609.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	11.279 ^a	12	.505	.566 ^b	.553	.579			
Likelihood Ratio	12.693	12	.392	.711 ^b	.699	.722			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.696			.715 ^b	.703	.726			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.034 ^c	1	.854	.885 ^b	.876	.893	.470 ^b	.457 .483	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1465507556.

c. The standardized statistic is .183.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.109 ^a	12	.606	.687 ^b	.675	.699			
Likelihood Ratio	9.800	12	.634	.750 ^b	.739	.761			
Fisher's Exact Test	10.759			.791 ^b	.780	.801			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.137 ^c	1	.711	.809 ^b	.798	.819	.414 ^b	.401 .426	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 19 cells (95.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1465507556.

c. The standardized statistic is .370.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.785 ^a	12	.635	.713 ^b	.702	.725			
Likelihood Ratio	13.140	12	.359	.671 ^b	.659	.683			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.546			.746 ^b	.734	.757			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.252 ^c	1	.263	.292 ^b	.281	.304	.151 ^b	.141 .160	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1465507556.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.119.

Qualitative model: the Agile subset

Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	22.009 ^a	16	.143	.146 ^b	.137	.155			
Likelihood Ratio	19.243	16	.256	.296 ^b	.284	.308			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.860			.204 ^b	.194	.214			
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.007 ^c	1	.025	.028 ^b	.024	.032	.014 ^b	.011 .017	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1810951851.

c. The standardized statistic is -2.238.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.503	.210	-2.220	.026	.025 ^c	.021	.029
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1810951851.

Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	21.595 ^a	16	.157	.152 ^b	.143	.161			
Likelihood Ratio	25.365	16	.064	.139 ^b	.130	.148			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.293			.177 ^b	.167	.186			
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.029 ^c	1	.045	.047 ^b	.042	.052	.024 ^b	.020 .028	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1810951851.

c. The standardized statistic is -2.007.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.427	.200	-2.056	.040	.040 ^c	.035	.045
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1810951851.

Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.059 ^a	16	.320	.348 ^b	.335	.360			
Likelihood Ratio	15.146	16	.514	.380 ^b	.367	.393			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.829			.366 ^b	.353	.378			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.758 ^c	1	.097	.094 ^b	.086	.101	.063 ^b	.057 .069	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1810951851.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.661.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.262	.225	-1.080	.280	.360 ^c	.348	.373
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1810951851.

Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.595 ^a	16	.929	.982 ^b	.979	.986			
Likelihood Ratio	11.582	16	.772	.982 ^b	.979	.985			
Fisher's Exact Test	10.150			.981 ^b	.978	.985			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.451 ^c	1	.502	.524 ^b	.511	.537	.280 ^b	.269 .292	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1810951851.

c. The standardized statistic is .672.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.180	.209	.858	.391	.395 ^c	.383	.408
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1810951851.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	21.001 ^a	16	.178	.196 ^b	.185	.206			
Likelihood Ratio	14.946	16	.529	.539 ^b	.526	.552			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.525			.543 ^b	.530	.556			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.863 ^c	1	.172	.182 ^b	.172	.191	.104 ^b	.096 .112	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2096426169.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.365.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.309	.234	-1.271	.204	.195 ^c	.185	.205
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2096426169.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	17.494 ^a	16	.354	.375 ^b	.363	.388			
Likelihood Ratio	19.342	16	.251	.387 ^b	.374	.399			
Fisher's Exact Test	15.593			.458 ^b	.445	.471			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.084 ^c	1	.772	.802 ^b	.791	.812	.409 ^b	.396 .422	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2096426169.

c. The standardized statistic is -.290.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.050	.256	-.196	.844	.819 ^c	.809	.829
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2096426169.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	11.861 ^a	16	.753	.637 ^b	.625	.650			
Likelihood Ratio	13.310	16	.650	.494 ^b	.481	.507			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.465			.569 ^b	.556	.582			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.137 ^c	1	.712	.775 ^b	.764	.786	.381 ^b	.368 .393	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2096426169.

c. The standardized statistic is -.370.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.156	.290	.541	.589	.599 ^c	.586	.612
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2096426169.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	16.534 ^a	16	.416	.464 ^b	.451	.477			
Likelihood Ratio	16.650	16	.409	.619 ^b	.606	.631			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.995			.727 ^b	.716	.739			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.031 ^c	1	.860	.901 ^b	.893	.908	.456 ^b	.443 .469	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2096426169.

c. The standardized statistic is -.177.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.011	.234	-.049	.961	.957 ^c	.952	.962
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2096426169.

*Allocation of contingency reserves to cope with flexible schedule, budget and risks - A CTR * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.699 ^a	16	.828	.834 ^b	.824	.843			
Likelihood Ratio	10.294	16	.851	.892 ^b	.884	.900			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.001			.892 ^b	.884	.900			
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.117 ^c	1	.077	.080 ^b	.073	.087	.045 ^b	.040 .050	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 762367465.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.765.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.395	.233	-1.584	.113	.100 ^c	.093	.108
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 762367465.

*Allocation of contingency reserves to cope with flexible schedule, budget and risks - A CTR * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	14.421 ^a	16	.567	.697 ^b	.685	.709			
Likelihood Ratio	14.184	16	.585	.770 ^b	.759	.781			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.434			.751 ^b	.740	.763			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.983 ^c	1	.159	.176 ^b	.166	.186	.091 ^b	.083 .098	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 762367465.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.408.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.282	.219	-1.243	.214	.213 ^c	.202	.223
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 762367465.

*Allocation of contingency reserves to cope with flexible schedule, budget and risks - A CTR * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.755 ^a	16	.923	.849 ^b	.840	.858			
Likelihood Ratio	8.970	16	.915	.842 ^b	.833	.852			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.189			.827 ^b	.817	.836			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.343 ^c	1	.558	.626 ^b	.614	.638	.303 ^b	.291 .315	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 762367465.

c. The standardized statistic is -.585.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.019	.331	.058	.954	.954 ^c	.949	.960
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 762367465.

Allocation of contingency reserves to cope with flexible schedule, budget and risks - A CTR * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	13.976 ^a	16	.600	.708 ^b	.696	.719			
Likelihood Ratio	16.358	16	.428	.528 ^b	.515	.541			
Fisher's Exact Test	15.845			.520 ^b	.508	.533			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.353 ^c	1	.553	.558 ^b	.545	.571	.296 ^b	.284 .308	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 762367465.

c. The standardized statistic is -.594.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.060	.171	-.348	.728	.804 ^c	.794	.814
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 762367465.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	22.421 ^a	12	.033	.017 ^b	.014	.020			
Likelihood Ratio	21.330	12	.046	.031 ^b	.027	.035			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.861			.051 ^b	.046	.057			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.106 ^c	1	.745	.805 ^b	.794	.815	.401 ^b	.389 .414	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1540442866.

c. The standardized statistic is -.326.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.042	.210	-.198	.843	.858 ^c	.849	.867
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1540442866.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	11.680 ^a	12	.472	.533 ^b	.520	.546			
Likelihood Ratio	16.362	12	.175	.393 ^b	.381	.406			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.727			.413 ^b	.400	.425			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.096 ^c	1	.757	.802 ^b	.792	.812	.398 ^b	.385 .411	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1540442866.

c. The standardized statistic is -.310.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.033	.217	-.153	.878	.887 ^c	.879	.895
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1540442866.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.480 ^a	12	.747	.838 ^b	.829	.848			
Likelihood Ratio	9.846	12	.629	.748 ^b	.737	.759			
Fisher's Exact Test	10.691			.791 ^b	.780	.801			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.751 ^c	1	.386	.445 ^b	.432	.458	.229 ^b	.218 .240	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 18 cells (90.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1540442866.

c. The standardized statistic is -.867.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.248	.262	-.908	.364	.403 ^c	.391	.416
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1540442866.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.423 ^a	12	.219	.228 ^b	.217	.239			
Likelihood Ratio	19.582	12	.075	.167 ^b	.157	.177			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.774			.177 ^b	.167	.187			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.968 ^c	1	.085	.095 ^b	.087	.103	.050 ^b	.045 .056	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1540442866.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.723.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.385	.225	-1.704	.088	.085 ^c	.077	.092
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1540442866.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.383 ^a	16	.897	.932 ^b	.926	.939			
Likelihood Ratio	10.464	16	.841	.964 ^b	.960	.969			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.258			.963 ^b	.958	.968			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.331 ^c	1	.565	.584 ^b	.572	.597	.316 ^b	.304 .328	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 84799795.

c. The standardized statistic is -.575.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.082	.238	-.345	.730	.721 ^c	.709	.733
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 84799795.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	12.239 ^a	16	.727	.826 ^b	.816	.836			
Likelihood Ratio	17.266	16	.369	.689 ^b	.677	.701			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.287			.722 ^b	.710	.734			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.329 ^c	1	.566	.609 ^b	.597	.622	.306 ^b	.294 .318	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 84799795.

c. The standardized statistic is .574.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.147	.227	.655	.512	.485 ^c	.472	.497
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 84799795.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.396 ^a	16	.845	.854 ^b	.844	.863			
Likelihood Ratio	10.692	16	.828	.861 ^b	.852	.870			
Fisher's Exact Test	15.584			.821 ^b	.812	.831			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.243 ^c	1	.265	.309 ^b	.297	.321	.170 ^b	.160 .180	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 84799795.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.115.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.		
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.288	.234	-1.152	.249	.322 ^c	.310 .334
N of Valid Cases		25					

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 84799795.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.785 ^a	16	.823	.918 ^b	.911	.925			
Likelihood Ratio	12.848	16	.684	.947 ^b	.941	.952			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.115			.952 ^b	.946	.957			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.086 ^c	1	.769	.796 ^b	.786	.807	.412 ^b	.399 .425	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 84799795.

c. The standardized statistic is -.294.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.049	.201	-.242	.809	.823 ^c	.813	.833
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 84799795.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.429 ^a	16	.843	.834 ^b	.825	.844			
Likelihood Ratio	10.835	16	.820	.848 ^b	.839	.857			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.540			.842 ^b	.832	.851			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.130 ^c	1	.718	.773 ^b	.762	.784	.400 ^b	.387 .412	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 297761863.

c. The standardized statistic is -.361.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.013	.267	.048	.962	.956 ^c	.950	.961
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 297761863.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	12.484 ^a	16	.710	.836 ^b	.826	.845			
Likelihood Ratio	13.679	16	.623	.762 ^b	.751	.773			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.162			.763 ^b	.752	.774			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.342 ^c	1	.559	.579 ^b	.566	.591	.303 ^b	.291 .315	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 297761863.

c. The standardized statistic is .585.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.191	.228	.825	.410	.398 ^c	.385	.410
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 297761863.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.699 ^a	16	.925	.818 ^b	.808	.828			
Likelihood Ratio	10.616	16	.833	.686 ^b	.674	.698			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.518			.809 ^b	.799	.819			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.062 ^c	1	.803	.863 ^b	.854	.871	.446 ^b	.433 .458	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 23 cells (92.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 297761863.

c. The standardized statistic is -.249.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.058	.240	.241	.809	.857 ^c	.848	.866
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 297761863.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.931 ^a	16	.272	.277 ^b	.265	.288			
Likelihood Ratio	16.899	16	.392	.461 ^b	.448	.474			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.384			.450 ^b	.437	.463			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.386 ^c	1	.535	.566 ^b	.553	.579	.285 ^b	.273 .297	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 297761863.

c. The standardized statistic is .621.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.163	.215	.743	.458	.475 ^c	.462	.488
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 297761863.

*Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	25.170 ^a	16	.067	.096 ^b	.089	.104			
Likelihood Ratio	25.799	16	.057	.023 ^b	.019	.026			
Fisher's Exact Test	24.168			.021 ^b	.017	.025			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.803 ^c	1	.370	.409 ^b	.397	.422	.206 ^b	.195 .216	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1515591596.

c. The standardized statistic is .896.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.242	.244	1.001	.317	.279 ^c	.267	.290
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1515591596.

Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	25.941 ^a	16	.055	.032 ^b	.027	.037			
Likelihood Ratio	29.689	16	.020	.022 ^b	.018	.026			
Fisher's Exact Test	22.811			.012 ^b	.009	.015			
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.058 ^c	1	.080	.090 ^b	.083	.098	.045 ^b	.040 .051	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1515591596.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.749.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.356	.212	1.680	.093	.089 ^c	.082	.097
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1515591596.

*Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.994 ^a	16	.453	.378 ^b	.365	.390			
Likelihood Ratio	14.431	16	.567	.468 ^b	.455	.481			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.881			.442 ^b	.429	.454			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.091 ^c	1	.763	.803 ^b	.793	.814	.422 ^b	.409 .435	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1515591596.

c. The standardized statistic is -.301.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.207	.274	.766	.444	.475 ^c	.462	.488
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1515591596.

Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	17.710 ^a	16	.341	.378 ^b	.365	.390			
Likelihood Ratio	17.633	16	.346	.568 ^b	.555	.581			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.412			.637 ^b	.624	.649			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.144 ^c	1	.704	.727 ^b	.716	.739	.376 ^b	.364 .388	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1515591596.

c. The standardized statistic is .380.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.102	.234	.433	.665	.631 ^c	.619	.644
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1515591596.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.192 ^a	16	.313	.345 ^b	.333	.358			
Likelihood Ratio	18.473	16	.297	.334 ^b	.322	.346			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.685			.320 ^b	.308	.332			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.384 ^c	1	.536	.569 ^b	.556	.582	.292 ^b	.280 .303	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1157648955.

c. The standardized statistic is -.619.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.089	.241	-.368	.713	.688 ^c	.676	.699
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1157648955.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	27.103 ^a	16	.040	.029 ^b	.024	.033			
Likelihood Ratio	30.507	16	.016	.027 ^b	.023	.031			
Fisher's Exact Test	20.958			.025 ^b	.021	.029			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.101 ^c	1	.751	.761 ^b	.750	.772	.398 ^b	.385 .410	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1157648955.

c. The standardized statistic is -.317.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.054	.239	-.225	.822	.796 ^c	.786	.806
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1157648955.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S_SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	20.975 ^a	16	.179	.213 ^b	.202	.223			
Likelihood Ratio	14.203	16	.584	.529 ^b	.516	.542			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.216			.627 ^b	.615	.640			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.292 ^c	1	.589	.648 ^b	.635	.660	.342 ^b	.330 .354	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1157648955.

c. The standardized statistic is -.540.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.008	.283	.029	.977	.979 ^c	.975	.983
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1157648955.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.762 ^a	16	.470	.543 ^b	.530	.556			
Likelihood Ratio	18.451	16	.298	.638 ^b	.626	.651			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.580			.681 ^b	.669	.693			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.598 ^c	1	.439	.461 ^b	.448	.474	.241 ^b	.230 .252	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1157648955.

c. The standardized statistic is -.773.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.146	.204	-.715	.474	.487 ^c	.474	.500
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1157648955.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	3.108 ^a	4	.540	.691 ^b	.679	.702			
Likelihood Ratio	3.887	4	.422	.691 ^b	.679	.702			
Fisher's Exact Test	3.031			.691 ^b	.679	.702			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.651 ^c	1	.420	.471 ^b	.458	.484	.280 ^b	.268 .291	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 10 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .48.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 310042136.

c. The standardized statistic is -.807.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	1.038 ^a	4	.904	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Likelihood Ratio	1.047	4	.903	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Fisher's Exact Test	1.351			1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.378 ^c	1	.539	.577 ^b	.564	.590	.318 ^b	.306	.330
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 10 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.44.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 310042136.

c. The standardized statistic is .615.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	3.224 ^a	4	.521	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Likelihood Ratio	4.379	4	.357	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Fisher's Exact Test	3.102			1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.288 ^c	1	.256	.294 ^b	.282	.305	.197 ^b	.187 .208	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 8 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .48.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 310042136.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.135.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	1.114 ^a	4	.892	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Likelihood Ratio	1.128	4	.890	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Fisher's Exact Test	1.428			1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.001 ^c	1	.981	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000	.556 ^b	.543	.569
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 10 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.44.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 310042136.

c. The standardized statistic is -.023.

Qualitative model: the Knowledge Areas subset

Allocation of contingency reserves to cope with flexible schedule, budget and risks - A CTR * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.699 ^a	16	.828	.837 ^b	.827	.846			
Likelihood Ratio	10.294	16	.851	.896 ^b	.888	.904			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.001			.896 ^b	.888	.904			
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.117 ^c	1	.077	.087 ^b	.080	.094	.049 ^b	.044 .055	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 128728968.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.765.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.395	.233	-1.584	.113	.101 ^c	.093	.108
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 128728968.

*Allocation of contingency reserves to cope with flexible schedule, budget and risks - A CTR * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	14.421 ^a	16	.567	.686 ^b	.674	.698			
Likelihood Ratio	14.184	16	.585	.758 ^b	.747	.769			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.434			.739 ^b	.728	.751			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.983 ^c	1	.159	.183 ^b	.173	.193	.093 ^b	.086 .101	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 128728968.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.408.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.282	.219	-1.243	.214	.215 ^c	.205	.226
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 128728968.

*Allocation of contingency reserves to cope with flexible schedule, budget and risks - A CTR * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.755 ^a	16	.923	.855 ^b	.846	.864			
Likelihood Ratio	8.970	16	.915	.850 ^b	.840	.859			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.189			.834 ^b	.824	.843			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.343 ^c	1	.558	.621 ^b	.609	.634	.307 ^b	.295 .319	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 128728968.

c. The standardized statistic is -.585.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.019	.331	.058	.954	.948 ^c	.942	.954
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 128728968.

Allocation of contingency reserves to cope with flexible schedule, budget and risks - A CTR * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	13.976 ^a	16	.600	.711 ^b	.699	.722			
Likelihood Ratio	16.358	16	.428	.543 ^b	.531	.556			
Fisher's Exact Test	15.845			.536 ^b	.523	.548			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.353 ^c	1	.553	.561 ^b	.548	.574	.301 ^b	.289 .313	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 128728968.

c. The standardized statistic is -.594.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.060	.171	-.348	.728	.798 ^c	.788	.809
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 128728968.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.192 ^a	16	.313	.332 ^b	.320	.344			
Likelihood Ratio	18.473	16	.297	.325 ^b	.312	.337			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.685			.311 ^b	.299	.323			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.384 ^c	1	.536	.580 ^b	.567	.593	.303 ^b	.291 .315	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 229055743.

c. The standardized statistic is -.619.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.089	.241	-.368	.713	.693 ^c	.681	.705
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 229055743.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	27.103 ^a	16	.040	.029 ^b	.024	.033			
Likelihood Ratio	30.507	16	.016	.030 ^b	.026	.034			
Fisher's Exact Test	20.958			.026 ^b	.022	.031			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.101 ^c	1	.751	.765 ^b	.754	.776	.404 ^b	.391 .416	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 229055743.

c. The standardized statistic is -.317.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.054	.239	-.225	.822	.794 ^c	.783	.804
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 229055743.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S_SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	20.975 ^a	16	.179	.195 ^b	.185	.205			
Likelihood Ratio	14.203	16	.584	.516 ^b	.503	.529			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.216			.618 ^b	.605	.630			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.292 ^c	1	.589	.648 ^b	.636	.660	.338 ^b	.326 .350	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 229055743.

c. The standardized statistic is -.540.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.008	.283	.029	.977	.979 ^c	.975	.982
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 229055743.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.762 ^a	16	.470	.530 ^b	.517	.543			
Likelihood Ratio	18.451	16	.298	.625 ^b	.612	.637			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.580			.668 ^b	.656	.680			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.598 ^c	1	.439	.472 ^b	.459	.485	.248 ^b	.237 .260	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 229055743.

c. The standardized statistic is -.773.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.146	.204	-.715	.474	.500 ^c	.487	.512
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 229055743.

Allocation of resources to plan a Inog time collaboration with the Service Provider - C LTC * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.310 ^a	12	.107	.112 ^b	.104	.121			
Likelihood Ratio	13.864	12	.309	.382 ^b	.369	.394			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.120			.375 ^b	.363	.388			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.798 ^c	1	.180	.204 ^b	.194	.215	.115 ^b	.106 .123	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2052202647.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.341.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.215	.257	-.812	.417	.385 ^c	.372	.398
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2052202647.

Allocation of resources to plan a Inog time collaboration with the Service Provider - C LTC * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.198 ^a	12	.599	.681 ^b	.669	.693			
Likelihood Ratio	13.256	12	.351	.655 ^b	.643	.667			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.737			.717 ^b	.705	.728			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.243 ^c	1	.622	.660 ^b	.648	.672	.341 ^b	.328 .353	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2052202647.

c. The standardized statistic is -.493.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.053	.271	-.194	.846	.818 ^c	.808	.828
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2052202647.

Allocation of resources to plan a Inog time collaboration with the Service Provider - C LTC * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	11.664 ^a	12	.473	.613 ^b	.600	.626			
Likelihood Ratio	9.343	12	.673	.799 ^b	.788	.809			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.992			.588 ^b	.576	.601			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.865 ^c	1	.352	.424 ^b	.411	.437	.217 ^b	.206 .228	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 18 cells (90.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2052202647.

c. The standardized statistic is -.930.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.009	.322	-.028	.977	.964 ^c	.959	.969
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2052202647.

Allocation of resources to plan a Inog time collaboration with the Service Provider - C LTC * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	12.709 ^a	12	.391	.418 ^b	.406	.431			
Likelihood Ratio	16.109	12	.186	.375 ^b	.363	.388			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.549			.427 ^b	.414	.440			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.031 ^c	1	.860	.877 ^b	.869	.886	.453 ^b	.440 .466	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2052202647.

c. The standardized statistic is .176.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.094	.201	.468	.640	.686 ^c	.674	.698
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2052202647.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	28.780 ^a	16	.025	.079 ^b	.072	.086			
Likelihood Ratio	30.163	16	.017	.002 ^b	.001	.004			
Fisher's Exact Test	27.380			.002 ^b	.001	.004			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.187 ^c	1	.139	.157 ^b	.148	.166	.083 ^b	.075 .090	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 269342361.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.479.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.311	.243	-1.248	.212	.179 ^c	.169	.189
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 269342361.

Use of qualitative metrics to evaluate the service levels - C QTY * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	14.524 ^a	16	.560	.659 ^b	.646	.671			
Likelihood Ratio	18.406	16	.301	.547 ^b	.534	.560			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.753			.601 ^b	.588	.613			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.689 ^c	1	.407	.423 ^b	.410	.436	.227 ^b	.216 .237	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 269342361.

c. The standardized statistic is -.830.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.168	.232	-.716	.474	.437 ^c	.424	.449
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 269342361.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	14.373 ^a	16	.571	.511 ^b	.499	.524			
Likelihood Ratio	11.524	16	.776	.748 ^b	.737	.759			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.912			.791 ^b	.780	.801			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.407 ^c	1	.121	.139 ^b	.130	.147	.083 ^b	.075 .090	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 269342361.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.551.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.368	.260	-1.281	.200	.201 ^c	.190	.211
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 269342361.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.302 ^a	16	.307	.331 ^b	.319	.343			
Likelihood Ratio	22.444	16	.129	.170 ^b	.160	.180			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.572			.130 ^b	.121	.139			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.054 ^c	1	.817	.849 ^b	.840	.858	.430 ^b	.418 .443	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 269342361.

c. The standardized statistic is .231.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.106	.213	.501	.616	.622 ^c	.610	.635
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 269342361.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	3.108 ^a	4	.540	.684 ^b	.672	.696			
Likelihood Ratio	3.887	4	.422	.684 ^b	.672	.696			
Fisher's Exact Test	3.031			.684 ^b	.672	.696			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.651 ^c	1	.420	.463 ^b	.450	.476	.279 ^b	.267	.290
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 10 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .48.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1781166669.

c. The standardized statistic is -.807.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	1.038 ^a	4	.904	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Likelihood Ratio	1.047	4	.903	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Fisher's Exact Test	1.351			1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.378 ^c	1	.539	.572 ^b	.559	.585	.317 ^b	.305	.329
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 10 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.44.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1781166669.

c. The standardized statistic is .615.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	3.224 ^a	4	.521	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Likelihood Ratio	4.379	4	.357	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Fisher's Exact Test	3.102			1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.288 ^c	1	.256	.291 ^b	.279	.303	.198 ^b	.188	.208
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 8 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .48.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1781166669.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.135.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	1.114 ^a	4	.892	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Likelihood Ratio	1.128	4	.890	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Fisher's Exact Test	1.428			1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.001 ^c	1	.981	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000	.542 ^b	.529	.555
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 10 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.44.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1781166669.

c. The standardized statistic is -.023.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.272 ^a	8	.054	.050 ^b	.045	.056			
Likelihood Ratio	13.102	8	.108	.113 ^b	.105	.121			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.812			.087 ^b	.080	.094			
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.494 ^c	1	.062	.073 ^b	.067	.080	.046 ^b	.041 .052	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 15 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 370656081.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.869.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	4.272 ^a	8	.832	.907 ^b	.899	.914			
Likelihood Ratio	5.165	8	.740	.931 ^b	.924	.937			
Fisher's Exact Test	4.919			.898 ^b	.890	.905			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.100 ^c	1	.294	.320 ^b	.308	.332	.179 ^b	.169 .188	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 15 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 370656081.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.049.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.826 ^a	8	.045	.054 ^b	.048	.060			
Likelihood Ratio	14.457	8	.071	.031 ^b	.026	.035			
Fisher's Exact Test	12.200			.063 ^b	.057	.069			
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.343 ^c	1	.037	.046 ^b	.040	.051	.037 ^b	.032 .042	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 14 cells (93.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 370656081.

c. The standardized statistic is -2.084.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	6.753 ^a	8	.564	.638 ^b	.625	.650			
Likelihood Ratio	8.559	8	.381	.627 ^b	.615	.639			
Fisher's Exact Test	6.111			.709 ^b	.698	.721			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.720 ^c	1	.396	.416 ^b	.403	.428	.237 ^b	.226 .248	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 15 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 370656081.

c. The standardized statistic is .848.

Qualitative model: the Change subset

Allocation of resources so to avoid an loss of control via an implicit handover to the Service Provider - O IHV * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	19.550 ^a	16	.241	.239 ^b	.228	.250			
Likelihood Ratio	14.882	16	.533	.684 ^b	.672	.696			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.830			.696 ^b	.684	.708			
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.362 ^c	1	.067	.072 ^b	.065	.078	.040 ^b	.035 .045	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 104854168.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.834.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.307	.224	-1.298	.194	.164 ^c	.155	.174
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 104854168.

Allocation of resources so to avoid an loss of control via an implicit handover to the Service Provider - O IHV * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	17.373 ^a	16	.362	.406 ^b	.393	.419			
Likelihood Ratio	18.912	16	.273	.666 ^b	.653	.678			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.474			.686 ^b	.674	.698			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.644 ^c	1	.200	.228 ^b	.217	.239	.113 ^b	.105 .121	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 104854168.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.282.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.202	.199	-.993	.321	.333 ^c	.321	.345
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 104854168.

Allocation of resources so to avoid an loss of control via an implicit handover to the Service Provider - O IHV * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	17.735 ^a	16	.340	.367 ^b	.354	.379			
Likelihood Ratio	12.879	16	.682	.787 ^b	.777	.798			
Fisher's Exact Test	15.324			.751 ^b	.740	.762			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.678 ^c	1	.102	.116 ^b	.108	.125	.066 ^b	.060 .073	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 104854168.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.637.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.258	.260	-.935	.350	.361 ^c	.348	.373
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 104854168.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	7.131 ^a	16	.971	.995 ^b	.994	.997			
Likelihood Ratio	10.674	16	.829	.994 ^b	.992	.996			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.104			.995 ^b	.993	.997			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.001 ^c	1	.982	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000	.520 ^b	.507 .533	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 104854168.

c. The standardized statistic is .023.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.		
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.005	.200	.026	.979	.974 ^c	.970 .978
N of Valid Cases	25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 104854168.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.970 ^a	12	.619	.730 ^b	.719	.742			
Likelihood Ratio	8.832	12	.717	.857 ^b	.848	.866			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.549			.832 ^b	.822	.842			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.458 ^c	1	.117	.122 ^b	.114	.131	.073 ^b	.066 .080	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .16.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 865180977.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.568.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.341	.222	-1.476	.140	.141 ^c	.132	.150
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 865180977.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.722 ^a	12	.640	.709 ^b	.697	.721			
Likelihood Ratio	12.861	12	.379	.713 ^b	.701	.724			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.960			.685 ^b	.673	.697			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.489 ^c	1	.484	.522 ^b	.509	.535	.271 ^b	.260 .283	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .48.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 865180977.

c. The standardized statistic is -.699.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.137	.207	-.656	.512	.531 ^c	.518	.544
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 865180977.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	20.971 ^a	12	.051	.011 ^b	.008	.013			
Likelihood Ratio	18.791	12	.094	.023 ^b	.019	.027			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.688			.016 ^b	.013	.019			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.121 ^c	1	.728	.752 ^b	.741	.763	.415 ^b	.402 .427	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 19 cells (95.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .16.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 865180977.

c. The standardized statistic is -.347.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.141	.353	.396	.692	.626 ^c	.613	.638
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 865180977.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	6.849 ^a	12	.867	.923 ^b	.916	.929			
Likelihood Ratio	9.489	12	.661	.921 ^b	.914	.928			
Fisher's Exact Test	7.613			.934 ^b	.928	.941			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.094 ^c	1	.759	.773 ^b	.762	.784	.410 ^b	.397 .422	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .48.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 865180977.

c. The standardized statistic is -.307.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.062	.165	-.377	.706	.780 ^c	.769	.791
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 865180977.

Clarification of the scope of the project with internal staff - O SCP * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.693 ^a	12	.643	.690 ^b	.678	.702			
Likelihood Ratio	11.019	12	.527	.670 ^b	.658	.682			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.449			.689 ^b	.677	.701			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.005 ^c	1	.942	1.000 ^b	1.000	1.000	.511 ^b	.498 .524	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 415409172.

c. The standardized statistic is -.073.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.007	.245	.028	.978	.988 ^c	.985	.991
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 415409172.

Clarification of the scope of the project with internal staff - O SCP * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.532 ^a	12	.742	.836 ^b	.827	.846			
Likelihood Ratio	10.550	12	.568	.837 ^b	.828	.847			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.088			.785 ^b	.774	.795			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.458 ^c	1	.498	.549 ^b	.536	.562	.276 ^b	.264 .287	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 415409172.

c. The standardized statistic is .677.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.178	.250	.716	.474	.447 ^c	.434	.460
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 415409172.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	11.263 ^a	12	.507	.531 ^b	.518	.543			
Likelihood Ratio	10.291	12	.590	.575 ^b	.562	.588			
Fisher's Exact Test	12.575			.580 ^b	.567	.593			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.340 ^c	1	.560	.658 ^b	.646	.670	.326 ^b	.314 .338	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 19 cells (95.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 415409172.

c. The standardized statistic is .583.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.373	.287	1.223	.221	.239 ^c	.228	.250
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 415409172.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.861 ^a	12	.715	.806 ^b	.796	.816			
Likelihood Ratio	12.218	12	.428	.699 ^b	.687	.711			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.878			.679 ^b	.667	.691			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.656 ^c	1	.418	.446 ^b	.433	.459	.235 ^b	.224 .246	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 415409172.

c. The standardized statistic is -.810.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.188	.182	-1.029	.303	.431 ^c	.418	.444
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 415409172.

Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	22.009 ^a	16	.143	.151 ^b	.142	.160			
Likelihood Ratio	19.243	16	.256	.304 ^b	.293	.316			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.860			.212 ^b	.202	.223			
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.007 ^c	1	.025	.025 ^b	.021	.029	.013 ^b	.010 .015	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1569707924.

c. The standardized statistic is -2.238.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.503	.210	-2.220	.026	.022 ^c	.018	.026
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1569707924.

*Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	21.595 ^a	16	.157	.147 ^b	.138	.157			
Likelihood Ratio	25.365	16	.064	.139 ^b	.130	.148			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.293			.181 ^b	.171	.190			
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.029 ^c	1	.045	.046 ^b	.040	.051	.024 ^b	.020 .028	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1569707924.

c. The standardized statistic is -2.007.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.427	.200	-2.056	.040	.038 ^c	.033	.043
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1569707924.

Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.059 ^a	16	.320	.353 ^b	.341	.365			
Likelihood Ratio	15.146	16	.514	.392 ^b	.379	.404			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.829			.372 ^b	.360	.385			
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.758 ^c	1	.097	.098 ^b	.090	.105	.065 ^b	.058 .071	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1569707924.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.661.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.262	.225	-1.080	.280	.354 ^c	.342	.366
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1569707924.

Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A AUT * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.595 ^a	16	.929	.980 ^b	.977	.984			
Likelihood Ratio	11.582	16	.772	.980 ^b	.977	.984			
Fisher's Exact Test	10.150			.981 ^b	.977	.984			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.451 ^c	1	.502	.516 ^b	.503	.529	.272 ^b	.261 .284	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1569707924.

c. The standardized statistic is .672.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.180	.209	.858	.391	.393 ^c	.380	.405
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1569707924.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	21.001 ^a	16	.178	.196 ^b	.186	.207			
Likelihood Ratio	14.946	16	.529	.547 ^b	.534	.560			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.525			.547 ^b	.534	.560			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.863 ^c	1	.172	.182 ^b	.172	.192	.108 ^b	.100 .116	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1518639446.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.365.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.309	.234	-1.271	.204	.194 ^c	.184	.204
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1518639446.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	17.494 ^a	16	.354	.384 ^b	.371	.396			
Likelihood Ratio	19.342	16	.251	.397 ^b	.384	.410			
Fisher's Exact Test	15.593			.471 ^b	.458	.484			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.084 ^c	1	.772	.806 ^b	.796	.816	.410 ^b	.397 .423	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1518639446.

c. The standardized statistic is -.290.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.050	.256	-.196	.844	.824 ^c	.814	.834
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1518639446.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	11.861 ^a	16	.753	.653 ^b	.641	.665			
Likelihood Ratio	13.310	16	.650	.504 ^b	.491	.517			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.465			.583 ^b	.570	.595			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.137 ^c	1	.712	.778 ^b	.767	.788	.389 ^b	.376 .401	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1518639446.

c. The standardized statistic is -.370.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.156	.290	.541	.589	.602 ^c	.589	.615
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1518639446.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	16.534 ^a	16	.416	.464 ^b	.451	.477			
Likelihood Ratio	16.650	16	.409	.623 ^b	.611	.635			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.995			.726 ^b	.715	.738			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.031 ^c	1	.860	.899 ^b	.892	.907	.457 ^b	.444 .470	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1518639446.

c. The standardized statistic is -.177.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.011	.234	-.049	.961	.955 ^c	.950	.960
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1518639446.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.383 ^a	16	.897	.936 ^b	.930	.942			
Likelihood Ratio	10.464	16	.841	.967 ^b	.962	.971			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.258			.965 ^b	.961	.970			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.331 ^c	1	.565	.588 ^b	.575	.600	.315 ^b	.303 .327	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1029659588.

c. The standardized statistic is -.575.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.082	.238	-.345	.730	.712 ^c	.700	.723
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1029659588.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	12.239 ^a	16	.727	.825 ^b	.815	.835			
Likelihood Ratio	17.266	16	.369	.691 ^b	.679	.702			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.287			.723 ^b	.712	.735			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.329 ^c	1	.566	.605 ^b	.592	.617	.309 ^b	.297 .320	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1029659588.

c. The standardized statistic is .574.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.147	.227	.655	.512	.492 ^c	.479	.504
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1029659588.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.396 ^a	16	.845	.864 ^b	.855	.873			
Likelihood Ratio	10.692	16	.828	.874 ^b	.865	.882			
Fisher's Exact Test	15.584			.833 ^b	.823	.842			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.243 ^c	1	.265	.299 ^b	.287	.310	.161 ^b	.151 .170	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1029659588.

c. The standardized statistic is -1.115.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.288	.234	-1.152	.249	.321 ^c	.309	.333
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1029659588.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.785 ^a	16	.823	.919 ^b	.912	.926			
Likelihood Ratio	12.848	16	.684	.948 ^b	.942	.954			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.115			.953 ^b	.948	.958			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.086 ^c	1	.769	.792 ^b	.782	.803	.404 ^b	.391 .416	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1029659588.

c. The standardized statistic is -.294.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.049	.201	-.242	.809	.819 ^c	.809	.829
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1029659588.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.429 ^a	16	.843	.837 ^b	.827	.846			
Likelihood Ratio	10.835	16	.820	.850 ^b	.841	.859			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.540			.843 ^b	.833	.852			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.130 ^c	1	.718	.773 ^b	.762	.783	.399 ^b	.386 .411	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 483047110.

c. The standardized statistic is -.361.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.013	.267	.048	.962	.955 ^c	.950	.960
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 483047110.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	12.484 ^a	16	.710	.847 ^b	.838	.856			
Likelihood Ratio	13.679	16	.623	.780 ^b	.769	.790			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.162			.781 ^b	.770	.792			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.342 ^c	1	.559	.581 ^b	.568	.594	.296 ^b	.284 .307	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 483047110.

c. The standardized statistic is .585.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower	Upper	
						Bound	Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.191	.228	.825	.410	.401 ^c	.388	.414
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 483047110.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	8.699 ^a	16	.925	.819 ^b	.809	.829			
Likelihood Ratio	10.616	16	.833	.689 ^b	.677	.701			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.518			.813 ^b	.803	.823			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.062 ^c	1	.803	.867 ^b	.858	.876	.452 ^b	.439 .464	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 23 cells (92.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 483047110.

c. The standardized statistic is -.249.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.		
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.058	.240	.241	.809	.850 ^c	.840 .859
N of Valid Cases	25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 483047110.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.931 ^a	16	.272	.274 ^b	.262	.285			
Likelihood Ratio	16.899	16	.392	.456 ^b	.443	.469			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.384			.448 ^b	.435	.461			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.386 ^c	1	.535	.571 ^b	.558	.583	.286 ^b	.275 .298	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 483047110.

c. The standardized statistic is .621.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.163	.215	.743	.458	.480 ^c	.467	.493
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 483047110.

*Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG*

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	25.170 ^a	16	.067	.093 ^b	.086	.101			
Likelihood Ratio	25.799	16	.057	.021 ^b	.017	.024			
Fisher's Exact Test	24.168			.018 ^b	.015	.022			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.803 ^c	1	.370	.417 ^b	.404	.429	.216 ^b	.206 .227	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 487259226.

c. The standardized statistic is .896.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.242	.244	1.001	.317	.286 ^c	.275	.298
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 487259226.

Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	25.941 ^a	16	.055	.033 ^b	.028	.037			
Likelihood Ratio	29.689	16	.020	.021 ^b	.017	.025			
Fisher's Exact Test	22.811			.012 ^b	.009	.014			
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.058 ^c	1	.080	.086 ^b	.079	.093	.046 ^b	.041 .052	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 487259226.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.749.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.356	.212	1.680	.093	.085 ^c	.078	.092
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 487259226.

Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C PRC * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.994 ^a	16	.453	.369 ^b	.357	.382			
Likelihood Ratio	14.431	16	.567	.456 ^b	.443	.469			
Fisher's Exact Test	18.881			.429 ^b	.417	.442			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.091 ^c	1	.763	.800 ^b	.790	.810	.415 ^b	.402 .428	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .04.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 487259226.

c. The standardized statistic is -.301.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.207	.274	.766	.444	.475 ^c	.462	.488
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 487259226.

Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C_PRC * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S_SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	17.710 ^a	16	.341	.376 ^b	.364	.389			
Likelihood Ratio	17.633	16	.346	.570 ^b	.558	.583			
Fisher's Exact Test	14.412			.638 ^b	.626	.651			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.144 ^c	1	.704	.731 ^b	.720	.742	.381 ^b	.369 .394	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 487259226.

c. The standardized statistic is .380.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.102	.234	.433	.665	.632 ^c	.620	.645
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 487259226.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S BDG

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	18.192 ^a	16	.313	.334 ^b	.321	.346			
Likelihood Ratio	18.473	16	.297	.329 ^b	.317	.341			
Fisher's Exact Test	17.685			.316 ^b	.304	.328			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.384 ^c	1	.536	.573 ^b	.561	.586	.304 ^b	.293 .316	
N of Valid Cases		25							

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 364826326.

c. The standardized statistic is -.619.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.089	.241	-.368	.713	.694 ^c	.683	.706
N of Valid Cases		25						

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 364826326.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S DRT

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	27.103 ^a	16	.040	.031 ^b	.027	.036			
Likelihood Ratio	30.507	16	.016	.030 ^b	.026	.035			
Fisher's Exact Test	20.958			.027 ^b	.023	.031			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.101 ^c	1	.751	.764 ^b	.753	.775	.409 ^b	.396 .421	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 364826326.

c. The standardized statistic is -.317.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.054	.239	-.225	.822	.795 ^c	.785	.806
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 364826326.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S_SC1

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	20.975 ^a	16	.179	.202 ^b	.192	.213			
Likelihood Ratio	14.203	16	.584	.520 ^b	.507	.533			
Fisher's Exact Test	16.216			.616 ^b	.603	.628			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.292 ^c	1	.589	.641 ^b	.629	.653	.343 ^b	.330 .355	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 24 cells (96.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 364826326.

c. The standardized statistic is -.540.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	.008	.283	.029	.977	.981 ^c	.977	.985
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 364826326.

Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C CMM * End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S SC2

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	15.762 ^a	16	.470	.532 ^b	.519	.545			
Likelihood Ratio	18.451	16	.298	.627 ^b	.614	.639			
Fisher's Exact Test	13.580			.668 ^b	.656	.680			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.598 ^c	1	.439	.466 ^b	.453	.479	.246 ^b	.235 .257	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 25 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .24.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 364826326.

c. The standardized statistic is -.773.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^b	Approx. Sig.	Monte Carlo Sig.			
					Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Ordinal by Ordinal	Gamma	-.146	.204	-.715	.474	.489 ^c	.477	.502
N of Valid Cases	25							

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 364826326.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.206 ^a	12	.598	.691 ^b	.679	.703			
Likelihood Ratio	10.895	12	.538	.684 ^b	.672	.696			
Fisher's Exact Test	11.117			.647 ^b	.634	.659			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.370 ^c	1	.543	.599 ^b	.586	.611	.307 ^b	.295 .319	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1723355057.

c. The standardized statistic is .609.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
					Bound	Bound		Bound	Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	11.279 ^a	12	.505	.567 ^b	.554	.580			
Likelihood Ratio	12.693	12	.392	.704 ^b	.692	.715			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.696			.708 ^b	.696	.720			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.034 ^c	1	.854	.874 ^b	.865	.882	.455 ^b	.442 .468	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1723355057.

c. The standardized statistic is .183.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	10.109 ^a	12	.606	.686 ^b	.674	.698			
Likelihood Ratio	9.800	12	.634	.748 ^b	.737	.759			
Fisher's Exact Test	10.759			.787 ^b	.776	.797			
Linear-by-Linear Association	.137 ^c	1	.711	.812 ^b	.802	.822	.411 ^b	.398 .423	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 19 cells (95.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1723355057.

c. The standardized statistic is .370.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Monte Carlo Sig. (2-sided)		Monte Carlo Sig. (1-sided)			
				Sig.	99% Confidence Interval		Sig.	99% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pearson Chi-Square	9.785 ^a	12	.635	.708 ^b	.696	.719			
Likelihood Ratio	13.140	12	.359	.659 ^b	.647	.671			
Fisher's Exact Test	9.546			.740 ^b	.729	.751			
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.252 ^c	1	.263	.293 ^b	.281	.305	.150 ^b	.140 .159	
N of Valid Cases	25								

a. 20 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .36.

b. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 1723355057.

c. The standardized statistic is 1.119.

Normality of variables (“check the skew and Kurtosis”; Markham, n.d.)

	Allocation of resources to cope with resistance to change from the internal staff - O_RES	Clear definition of the boundaries of outsourcing (repeatable processes/functions/...) - O_BND	Allocation of resources to avoid the risk of lock-in - O_LKN	Allocation of resources to cope with the risk of hidden costs - O_HDC
Valid N	25	25	25	25
Missing	0	0	0	0
Skewness	-.126	-.108	.317	.085
Std. Error of Skewness	.464	.464	.464	.464
Kurtosis	-1.180	-1.355	-1.117	-1.602
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.902	.902	.902	.902

	Allocation of resources so to avoid an loss of control via an implicit handover to the Service Provider - O_IHV	Allocation of resources to transform internal staff - O_STR	Clarification of the scope of the project with internal staff - O_SCP	Allocation of resources to provide decisional autonomy to the project team - A_AUT
Valid N	25	25	25	25
Missing	0	0	0	0
Skewness	-.152	-.193	.428	-.437
Std. Error of Skewness	.464	.464	.464	.464
Kurtosis	-.850	-.957	-.962	-.946
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.902	.902	.902	.902

	Allocation of resources to foster co-located teams - A_CLT	Allocation of contingency reserves to cope with flexible schedule, budget and risks - A_CTR	Allocation of resources for ad-hoc documentation - A_AHD	Allocation of resources to empower trust - A_TST
Valid	25	25	25	25
N				
Missing	0	0	0	0
Skewness	-.389	-.500	.030	.008
Std. Error of Skewness	.464	.464	.464	.464
Kurtosis	-.564	-.371	-1.508	-1.319
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.902	.902	.902	.902

	Allocation of resources to motivate internal staff - C_MTV	Allocation of resources to review internal processes, roles and responsibilities - C_PRC	Allocation of resources to create proper channels of communications - C_CMM	Allocation of resources to plan a Inog time collaboration with the Service Provider - C_LTC
Valid	25	25	25	25
N				
Missing	0	0	0	0
Skewness	.177	-.114	.097	-.786
Std. Error of Skewness	.464	.464	.464	.464
Kurtosis	-1.266	-1.300	-.703	-.129
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.902	.902	.902	.902

	Use of qualitative metrics to evaluate the service levels - C_QTY	Cost of the HW - C_OTH_HW	Cost of the SW - C_OTH_SW	Cost of internal staff (FTE) - C_OTH_STAFF
Valid	25	23	23	22
N				
Missing	0	2	2	3
Skewness	-.282	.377	.527	-.238
Std. Error of Skewness	.464	.481	.481	.491
Kurtosis	-.717	-.335	-.249	-.859
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.902	.935	.935	.953

	Cost of the Training - C_OTH_TRAIN	Cost of the Service Provider - C_OTH_OSP	Cost of the Architectural Analysis - C_OTH_ARCH	Cost of the Knowledge Transfer - C_OTH_KT
Valid	22	23	1	1
N				
Missing	3	2	24	24
Skewness	.413	.281		
Std. Error of Skewness	.491	.481		
Kurtosis	-.757	-.356		
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.953	.935		

	Cost of the review of the Processes - C_OTH_PROC_REV	Cost of the Plans to maintain alignment to Strategies - C_OTH_PLAN	Costs of management of resources during the project - C_OTH_RES	Cost of the project management - C_OTH_PRJ
Valid	1	2	1	1
N				
Missing	24	23	24	24
Skewness				
Std. Error of Skewness				
Kurtosis				
Std. Error of Kurtosis				

	Cost of final technical check-out and UAT - C_OTH_UAT	Deviance of the actual project budget from the planned one - S_BDG	Deviance of the actual project duration from the planned one - S_DRT	Deviance of the actual scope from the planned one - S_SC1
Valid	1	25	25	25
N				
Missing	24	0	0	0
Skewness		.643	.234	1.853
Std. Error of Skewness		.464	.464	.464
Kurtosis		.381	-1.237	5.009
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.902	.902	.902

End users unplanned requests to review the deliverables - S_SC2 S_SC1 + S_SC2 - S_SC1_PLUS_SC2

Valid	25	25
N		
Missing	0	0
Skewness	-.102	.510
Std. Error of Skewness	.464	.464
Kurtosis	-1.336	.514
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.902	.902
